

Conceptual Design for EarthCube: Market Manifesto for Science

Version 1.0

A product of the EarthCube 'Enterprise Architecture for Transformative Research
and Collaboration Across the Geosciences' Conceptual Design Project

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The set of deliverables includes:

- Conceptual design (this document)
- Executive summary
- Proposed EarthCube Information Model
- EarthCube Semantic Wiki
- Initial EarthCube inventory of high-level infrastructure resources

Project web site with links to these resources is:

<http://earthcube.org/group/transformative-research-collaboration>

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1 Executive Summary

1.1 Vision

EarthCube is an evolving socio-technical system that enables interactions between geo, computational, and information scientists to advance geoscience research and discovery, by reusing existing, developing new, and integrating geoscience cyberinfrastructure resources for the geosciences (TAC Architecture WG roadmap). The EarthCube system must capture and articulate technical capabilities useful to or required by the geoscience research community for system managers and funding authorities to direct evolution of the system. To improve the efficiency and effectiveness of research activities, the technology needs to match technical capabilities and expertise, on the one side, with needs of geoscientists expressed through a variety of use cases and research scenarios, on the other side. This matchmaking system is the technical essence of EarthCube. In a broader sense, EarthCube will also include the set of technical capabilities themselves, and provide mechanisms for managing and maintaining them through their lifecycles.

Databases, software services, and community facilities must be built on the existing foundation of cyberinfrastructure and community knowledge created over the past two decades. This will require years of development, investment, and community engagement to foster convergence towards an integrated system that supports the entire geosciences community. The success of EarthCube will depend on identification of solutions and best practices within the current infrastructure, and strategic testing and adoption of new technology and approaches. This can only occur through an evolutionary process in which dialogue and collaboration between system developers and system users identify and select the 'fittest' solutions. The conceptual design we present here takes a complex federation of systems approach, focused on key requirements to support evolution of community practice, emergence, and adaptability in the face of technological innovation, addressing both technical and social considerations.

As a socio-technical federation of systems, EarthCube will be immersed in an existing network of systems. The primary stakeholders in EarthCube are Earth Science academic researchers funded by the National Science Foundation. Members of this community typically need to meet teaching and operational demands of a university environment as well as conduct research under the auspices of various sources of funding. This community must interoperate with various other communities across fuzzy boundaries. Much information for the Earth Science enterprise is collected and managed by government agencies that have various mandates and are subject to changes in political priorities. The consumers of scientific research results for business purposes include government agencies engaged in regulatory or resource management and private enterprise seeking return on investment. Each of these communities is itself a heterogeneous collection of entities and systems for which there is no centralized management. In order to be successful, EarthCube must be engineered to promote interoperability and synergy between all of these communities by recognizing and building upon their shared interests.

Analogies are useful for understanding complex concepts. Two analogies are salient in our thinking about EarthCube—a marketplace and a workshop. The analogy of EarthCube as a market place is based on the concept of product providers and product consumers. The products in this market include information (datasets), technology (software, experimental practice), and expertise. Many of the products in the market place will be available to consumers without cost ('free') because they are the output of public-funded projects with requirements for open access to the products. The economic benefits to producers in this market are thus indirect, in the form of something like 'reputation' that is garnered in sys-

tems like [Quora](#), [Stack Overflow](#), or [Yahoo Answers](#). In the funded-research arena, the benefit of accruing reputation is increased success in obtaining funding, greater job security, and personal recognition/social status. The cyberinfrastructure is the technology necessary to support operation of the marketplace, but the products available in the market, and choices about which products will be used are made independently by the producers and consumers participating in the market. Regulations overlain on the market by funding providers or other authorities might be significant factors in these decisions.

EarthCube provides a workshop for finding, building, and using software and data to do Earth Science research. The workshop contains tools (software, data) that are ready to use, and a warehouse loaded with materials for making things. The workshop also provides a collection of tools and practices used to construct new tools if there is not one available already for a particular purpose, and for adding new materials to the warehouse stock. There are a variety of general purpose tool ‘frameworks’ like drill-presses, dremel tools, and lathes that can perform many different functions based on interoperable ‘plug-in’ attachments. The culture of this workshop is to reuse an existing tool or practice, with material already in the warehouse if applicable. If something new is developed or acquired, that is done with the intention of following existing patterns to make the tool or material available for a future worker to use. A hammer, saw, nails and wood might be necessary, but are not sufficient, to build a house – a construction worker has to know how to use these things in order to make that happen.

To reiterate, EarthCube is a managed platform for matching technical capabilities and expertise with needs of geoscientists expressed through a variety of use cases and research scenarios. Such match-making platforms present a new business model in a growing number of fields, for example shopping (Amazon and eBay), transportation (Uber), and relationships (eHarmony), with markets emerging in other fields including education and health care. The foundation of such platforms is a virtual marketplace where different types of capabilities are advertised, matched with needs (e.g. transportation or housing requests), and the quality of experience is evaluated (with reviews, reputation points, scores, etc.). The science enterprise is similarly going through fundamental changes in how it operates, with re-assessment of what constitutes science products, success metrics, re-use of science products and knowledge. To adapt to evolving technology and social expectations, the science enterprise needs a new

model for infrastructure that combines scientific, technical, organizational and other considerations.

Our view of EarthCube (Figure 1) centers on the notion of supporting a geoscience technical resource marketplace, where available resources, capabilities and expertise, and research needs of geoscientists expressed through use cases, scenarios and success stories, are presented. Matching existing resources with research needs implies that the former are validated and certified for use, and can be combined into various resource compositions (a.k.a. “architectures”) to address specific needs. The marketplace should be managed to ensure that emerging needs and the current feasibility of addressing them are analyzed, and development priorities are established to guide the evolution of the system. While many core technical capabilities have been implemented, we argue that these capabilities are not reaching their full potential is the absence of an efficient system for expressing the needs of geoscientists and matching such needs with capabilities and expertise. Research needs and technical capabilities are constantly evolving, but this advertising and match-making platform would remain the central “invariant” core of the EarthCube system. Technical capabilities would be registered in this platform, and the list of accessible capabilities (data, software, expertise, processing resources, services...) will evolve with the evolution of the geoscience research agenda and enabling technologies. Thus, the actual technical capabilities to be implemented cannot be prescribed at this level of design and time horizon.

The roadmap for transition of existing infrastructure to this new model includes both adapting existing infrastructure components and establishing new infrastructure. The strategy for EarthCube development should focus on developing the marketplace and match-making platform. A foundation of the platform will be specifications for clearly articulated and machine-processable statements of user needs in research scenarios, and for description of functional capabilities and interfaces of technologic components. These descriptions are a prerequisite for matching requirements and capabilities, and for automating the assembly of workflows that chain existing components in new ways. Such designs cannot be prescribed, but an efficient marketplace will make their rapid development possible. Description of this conceptual approach represents the core innovation introduced by the GEAR team. It has been expressed at all recent presentations starting in March 2015.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. EarthCube design should focus on matching user needs and technical capabilities. A platform for such matching is currently missing, and needs to be developed.
2. Success of matching should determine strategies for evolving EarthCube: from maintaining current and proven systems which meet specific user requirements, to supporting development of new capabilities. A key driver for the latter would be an identified mismatch between user requirements and capabilities articulated in the form of a proposal.
3. New capabilities should be evaluated for their impact on research and scientific progress, and this, in turn, should influence decisions on sustaining the newly developed resources.

1.2 Conceptual Elements

The core elements of the EarthCube technology infrastructure are factored into two major groups of IT-focused abstract components that support the user applications that are used for day-to-day research and learning activities. These IT components include Content-focused Components, and the Management and Operations Components (Figure 2). The system component model must be a dynamic artefact that can be extended or transformed to account for new workflows by specifying new building blocks or interfaces. The barriers to participation should be low so that requirements can be suggested even by a

novice. A key aspect of EarthCube as a federation of systems will be specification of the interfaces that link abstract components and provide guidance for the implementation of new components.

The content-focused components include closely related Resource and Registry systems and the Data Processing System. The Resource System manages information items that describe entities and activities in the world -- geologic features, observations, laboratory measurements, processing methods, system specifications, etc. The Registry system manages information items that document content in the Resource system or are resources like vocabularies, directories of people, projects, organizations etc. that are 'asserted', i.e. given as facts and intended for shared use populating data or metadata records.

The Data Processing System supports components used for the actual analysis and visualization of data. It is the foundation for designing new workflows and supporting repeatable science through reproducible data processing using composition of EarthCube components and workflows. User applications developed for specific research projects are included in this system. This system accesses the registry and repository system for component discovery and documentation-'shopping' in the marketplace analogy. More importantly, it provides the workbench/workspace support for the use of EarthCube re-

Figure 2. EarthCube conceptual design. All components and resources are products in a marketplace, including those that operate the marketplace. The invariants are the information exchanges that link the components and resources and allow them to interoperate.

sources in science research workflows.

The System Management and Operations Components implement a heterogeneous collection of capabilities for community support, usage analytics, system monitoring, conformance testing, and resource marketplace operations.

The User-Facing Applications, the analytical, visualization, resource discovery, resource access, scholarly communication, etc. components that scientists interact with on a daily basis in the course of research, are products registered in the marketplace (Figure 3), developed under the auspices of funded projects, with life cycles determined by project lifetime and possible subsequent adoption for wider use and maintenance. All the components and resources in this scheme are products in the marketplace, including those that enable operation of the marketplace. The EarthCube community of practice defines the framework for developing these resources following practices that promote their interoperability,

reusability, and future value. What is invariant and defines EarthCube are the specifications that define these practices—particularly:

- How resources are documented and registered with the system (added to the inventory),
- The information exchanges adopted for accessing the inventory and matching resources with requirements
- The information exchanges used to collect and report on resource impact, user satisfaction, missing capabilities, and resource usage.
- A shared high level information model that enables cross-domain communication and discovery.

The actual components and interfaces that implement these practices will change over time as technology evolves.

Figure 3. Infrastructure components for EarthCube. The Registry, Catalog, and Monitoring subsystems support the operation of the resource market place. Research assemblies of software and data resources have life cycles dependent on usage and impact-based funding

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. EarthCube CI should emphasize modular component development, and allow development of components that are not re-usable only in exceptional cases, e.g. when they represent prototypes leading to a modular component.
2. The modular CI components should be registered in a resource inventory.
3. EC should enable composing new infrastructures from registered components in a loosely coupled system, while allowing tight coupling as required for efficiency.
4. Any composition of components would be valid as long as it responds to a science research need and meets principles of EarthCube, including reproducibility, scalability, and modularity of components.
5. Components and their compositions should be evaluated for compliance with EarthCube-adopted standards and best practices as defined by the EarthCube Registry.
6. Monitoring all aspects of EarthCube operation, with quick feedback to governance, system managers and other users, is a critical component of the envisioned system

1.3 Metrics

The key to managing an evolutionary federated system of systems and directing its behavior towards the desired goal is the development and acquisition of performance metrics as a basis for objective selection and cultivation of components that are the 'fittest'. The goal of EarthCube is increasing the efficiency and productivity of the Earth Science research enterprise, so selected performance metrics need to quantify progress towards this goal.

EarthCube performance metrics will need to be based on tangible products like publications, running software, data in repositories, and satisfied customers, as well as intangible products like solved problems, learning, hazard mitigation, better data management, better quality of life. Some possible measurement approaches include impact factors, altmetrics, user polling, and review panels (expert opinion). Assessment of these metrics will be used to influence management decisions. The business model for EarthCube, with its foundation on funding through the NSF process, is different from most operational systems, and the management scheme for EarthCube is itself a work in progress. Exactly how system metrics and user feedback will be applied is not a technology issue and for the purpose of this design we can only say that a process needs to be in place and functional.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. EarthCube should use several approaches to continuously monitor and assess performance, availability, relevance and other characteristics of capabilities of components, individual systems and compositions, including user satisfaction.
2. Specific EarthCube metrics will emphasize how successfully given capabilities matched user needs, and thus contribute to the sustainability assessment.
3. While science impacts are often difficult to measure in the short term, a system of proxy measures based on tangible products and their characteristics, in particular reflecting how these products meet EarthCube architecture principles, will provide the basis for continuous monitoring.

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1 Preamble

This document presents our vision of EarthCube – a transformative concept of a unified, scalable and extensible cyberinfrastructure (CI) for Earth science research and education, which will evolve with the advancement of new research resources and data, new research hypotheses and designs, new ways to collaborate and disseminate research findings, and new geoscience communities.

This design incorporates extensive discussions within and between the earth sciences and information sciences communities over the first several years of EarthCube development, and experience gained in the course of several EarthCube projects. The document to a large extent is based on our previous development of EarthCube Cross-Domain Interoperability Roadmap (2012). The Roadmap provided a starting point, yet this design work allowed us to step back and re-evaluate our conceptualization of user needs, geoscience community building efforts, and technical infrastructure development trends. In the time since the Roadmap was written the EarthCube program has seen accelerated development. The key to this development has been formulation of CI needs across geoscience domains – via a series of EarthCube end user workshops and Research Coordination Network (RCN) projects. Major activities include organization of community governance through an EarthCube test enterprise governance project, and commencement of several building blocks efforts. The end user workshops yielded a wealth of information about research designs, needs and expectations of a number of geoscience domains. In addition, results of EarthCube member surveys conducted by the Stakeholder Alignment project have been critical in capturing subtle aspects of user expectations and pointing to differences across communities in terms of the infrastructure they need. The two years after the Roadmap development have also seen rapid technological progress, with emphasis on Big Data processing, cross-linking data from different sources, open data sharing, and novel information integration approaches. These elements allowed us to crystalize different perspectives on EarthCube and provided the basis for moving beyond the Roadmap to a more consistent design and its validation across a number of communities and research use cases. We thank all EarthCube members who actively contributed their vision of a comprehensive CI for the geosciences and understanding of how the CI can be accomplished, which we have attempted to incorporate in this document.

2 Introduction

Geosciences are at the forefront of responding to fundamental challenges including climate change prediction, water sustainability, analysis and management of hazards, and CO2 sequestration (NSF 2011). New insights into the earth system dynamics are required to respond to these challenges, which

Grand Challenges are inherently...

- Interdisciplinary, complex
 - Involves not just science and engineering, but also policy, government, and geopolitics
- Plans to tackle grand challenges should include:
- Systematic training for future scientists and engineers to take on these challenges

transcend disciplinary, organizational, political and other boundaries. Economic, social and environmental implications of inaction on climate change and related challenges will be enormous. Reliable, trustworthy descriptions and models of earth processes in the past, present and future are essential for deciding what action to take. This is only possible if the science enterprise becomes more efficient in integrating resources, knowledge and talent

developed across the geosciences. Geoscience cyberinfrastructure is a key instrument supporting such integration and enabling effective solution-oriented response to the main challenges and societal priorities.

Open, transparent, accessible and collaborative scientific modeling and analysis are crucial to the continued integrity of scientific conclusions and their perception by the public. This requires improving capabilities for scientifically-sound information sharing and reuse, increased reliance on standards for data discovery, retrieval, interpretation and analysis, and efficient processing of large volumes of data. It should become commonplace to re-generate simulation results, independently validate modeling conclusions, or re-run models with new data obtained from different geoscience domains. New solutions and approaches are especially needed in the context of exponentially increasing data volumes and the number and variety of data users and stakeholders, including the geoscience researchers who are involved in relatively small projects – the so-called “long tail of science.” We envision, using examples from the earlier Roadmap and summaries of domain end-user workshops, that:

- A critical zone scientist will be able to quickly retrieve information for an area of interest from several hydrology, geochemistry and microbiomics databases, organize it into a dataset suitable for online analysis, and share it with other researchers;
- A hydrology student needing climate data to run her model will be able to find, understand, evaluate the fitness of, and retrieve the data quickly, in a suitable format;
- A groundwater hydrologist will be able to retrieve all relevant 3D and 4D sub-surface data from multiple data sources, and organize it into permeability model inputs;
- A climate scientist will be able to use longer time series of key climate variables reconstructed from all available observations and in format ready to be included in a regional climate change assessment model;
- A biologist needing stream discharge and precipitation data will be able to find these data or data products in the appropriate spatial and temporal resolution and for the needed spatial feature (e.g. watershed), or use simple tools to convert it to the needed resolution;
- A surface water hydrologist will finally trust precipitation products generated by others. They will be able to trace and interpret the provenance of the data in understandable terms;
- A geologist will be able to map new observations onto a comprehensive 4D model of the earth to explore long-term geological processes in space and time;
- An oceanographer will be able to use new information from recent expeditions to re-compute several oceanographic models and compare results with earlier model computations, including simulations done by other research teams;
- Researchers will be able to not only find relevant data and models, but also to figure out whether these data and models have been used successfully for a similar problem, and by whom;

Some of the above scenarios appear mundane, yet the tasks take a lot of time to accomplish *every time they are done*. Many research scenarios cannot be foreseen, especially those emerging at cross-disciplinary boundaries. The ultimate purpose of EarthCube is to enable such established and emerging science scenarios, leveraging accessible data and unified infrastructure from previously disconnected earth science domains, institutions and researchers.

2.1 The Goal

The purpose of the EarthCube system is to stimulate scientific discovery, education, and development of the Earth Science workforce over the next decades. EarthCube is envisioned as a cyberinfra-

structure that fosters new, transformational geoscience by enabling discovery, evaluation and access to formerly unconnected resources, software, models, repositories, and computational power (Richard et al., 2014). This cyberinfrastructure will meet the information management challenges implicit in the GEO Vision (NSF, 2009) call to engage geoscientists in "data intensive science and investigation, data management, and long-term storage and access issues including the full data lifecycle" to promote more comprehensive, data-intensive research designs and knowledge sharing. EarthCube will be grounded in interoperability and communication with a human-centric focus that enables researchers and educators to work across thematic domains and levels of data or information granularity. New modes of learning and training will result in more informed citizens and policy-makers while simultaneously broadening participation in the creation of a sustainable Earth information system.

One of the key objectives is to enable more efficient and extensive use of data and other resources which are already being collected in various branches of the geosciences, and make them available for re-analysis and re-use in research and education contexts different than those in which they were collected or developed. SINTEF [2013] estimated that 90% of all data in the world have been collected in the previous 2 years. Although data are being collected at constantly increasing rates, major scientific breakthroughs are expected in interdisciplinary research based on information integration across domains. The availability of data collected at wider ranges of temporal and spatial scales, accessible via standard protocols and in standard formats, make it increasing likely that researchers in different domains can find data with matching spatial and temporal resolutions to describe physical process across disciplinary boundaries and instantiate or validate integrated models. Structural and semantic consistency present additional opportunities to re-use existing datasets to explore scientific hypotheses that may be related to completely different problems than the data were originally intended to address.

Significant investments in the development of geoscience CI have been made by the National Science Foundation (NSF) and other agencies, but the developed systems have different architecture, functional components, levels of maturity, management and access protocols, and policies. Leveraging these existing systems along with ongoing technical development within EarthCube is a key component of the design presented here. Unfortunately, a typical feature of many existing systems is their lack of inter-connection. Lack of cross-system integration in this stove-piped environment has made cross-disciplinary and cross-organizational data-intensive research extremely challenging. Overcoming this challenge has both technical and social dimensions. It will require not only transformative advances in information management, discovery, analysis and integration approaches and technologies, but also facilitating cross-domain and cross-institution collaborative research teams and fostering better understanding and communication among professionals of different backgrounds, as well as educating new Renaissance-type scientists for whom cross-disciplinary research is a common, recognized and rewarded activity. Therefore, a key requirement for EarthCube design is the integration of technical development, social, institutional and governance aspects of collaboration, and geoscience education and workforce development to promote a technology culture of resource sharing and reuse.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Consider increased scientifically sound re-use of data, software and expertise as the main short- and medium-term criterion in evaluating EarthCube progress.

2. Consider success in solving grand challenges, nurturing a new generation of geo data scientists, and institutional and cultural change, as the key long-term criteria in evaluating EarthCube progress.

2.2 EarthCube as an Evolving Socio-Technical System: a Market Vision

Recent studies related to Cyberinfrastructure that have informed this design.

There have been multiple studies of CI in recent years, emphasizing different perspectives and aspects of CI, and challenges of creating a CI supporting science enterprise:

- Atkins, D., & al., e. (2003). NSF-AP Report: Revolutionizing Science and Engineering Through Cyberinfrastructure: Report of NSF Blue-Ribbon Advisory Panel on Cyberinfrastructure.
- NSF. (2007). Cyberinfrastructure Vision for 21st Century Discovery *Cyberinfrastructure Council*.
- Edwards, P. N., Jackson, S., Bowker, G., & Knobel, C. P. (2007). Understanding Infrastructure: Dynamics, Tensions, and Design. Ann Arbor: NSF.
- Edwards, P. N. (2003). Infrastructure and modernity: Force, time, and social organization in the history of sociotechnical systems. In T. J. Misa, P. Brey & A. Feedberg (Eds.), *Modernity and technology* (pp. 185-225). Cambridge: MIT Press.
- Edwards, P. N., Jackson, S. J., Chalmers, M. K., Bowker, G. C., Borgman, C. L., Ribes., . . . (2013). Knowledge Infrastructures: Intellectual Frameworks and Research Challenges. Ann Arbor: Report of a workshop sponsored by NSF and the Sloan Foundation, Deep Blue.
- Jackson, St. J., et al. "Understanding infrastructure: History, heuristics and cyberinfrastructure policy." *First Monday* 12.6 (2007).
- Hey, T., & Trefethen, A. E. (2005). Cyberinfrastructure for e-Science. *Science*, 308(5723), 817-821.

We envision a system that streamlines geoscience data and information curation and management, access to data and information, and provides interfaces that expose resources for data-enabled research and knowledge creation. Component databases, software services, and community facilities must be built on the existing foundation of cyberinfrastructure and community knowledge created over the past two decades. This will require years of development, investment, and community engagement to foster convergence towards an integrated system that supports the entire geosciences community. Its success will depend on identification of solutions and best practices within the current infrastructure, and strategic testing and adoption of new technology and approaches. This can only occur through an *evolutionary process* in which dialogue and collaboration between system developers and system users identify and select the 'fittest' solutions. The conceptual design we present here takes a complex federation of systems approach, focused on key requirements to support evolution of community practice, emergence (Keating, 2009), and adaptability in the face of technological innovation, addressing both technical and social considerations.

As a socio-technical federation of systems, EarthCube will be immersed in an existing network of systems. The primary stakeholders in EarthCube are Earth Science academic researchers funded by the National Science Foundation. Members of this community typically need to meet teaching and operational demands of a university environment as well as conduct research under the auspices of various sources of funding. This community must interoperate with various other communities across fuzzy boundaries. Much information for the Earth Science enterprise is collected and managed by govern-

ment agencies that have various mandates and are subject to changes in political priorities. The consumers of scientific research results for business purposes include government agencies engaged in regulatory or resource management and private enterprise seeking return on investment. Each of these communities is itself a heterogeneous collection of entities and systems for which there is no centralized management. In order to be successful, EarthCube must be engineered to promote interoperability and synergy between all of these communities by recognizing and building upon their shared interests.

In support of the science enterprise (see section 2.4.4), EarthCube must thus promote and facilitate engagement and interaction between a wide spectrum of communities, domain systems, and previously disconnected CI components, people, and organizations. The system must support a broad geoscience and CI community to discuss shared research interests, nurture cross-disciplinary teams, and build trust in shared data, resources and knowledge to foster long-term trusted collaborations. Newly emerging components of online scholarly communication and networking such as research profile networks and reputation scores, Q&A, and open annotation systems can make collaborative research more transparent and inclusive, assist in finding members with matching or complementary interests, and foster a growing community knowledge base. It is our premise that such community-oriented components should be central to the conceptual design for implementing the vision of EarthCube as a community-guided system and an environment supporting multiple channels of scholarly communication. In our view, these components are critical for both everyday science engagements and for long-term self-sustainability of the system.

Based on existing experience with systems of systems, it is clear that an *evolutionary, adaptive, open system approach* is necessary. Like any complex system, *emergent behavior* is to be expected, so the architecture needs to focus on meta-level structures to promote information flow between the component systems, at both the scientific level (data flow) and the management level (design and operational decisions). The purpose of this document is to articulate the needs of such a system, and based on the needs, define metrics for system performance to support robust and scalable decision-making that guides system evolution for the benefit of stakeholders.

Analogies are useful for understanding complex concepts. EarthCube provides a workshop for finding, building, and using software and data to do EarthScience research. The workshop contains tools (software, data) that are ready to use, and a warehouse loaded with materials for making things. The workshop also provides a collection of tools and practices used to construct new tools if there is not one available already for a particular purpose, and for adding new materials to the warehouse stock. The culture of this workshop is to reuse an existing tool or practice, with material already in the warehouse if applicable. If something new is developed or acquired, that is done with the intention of following existing patterns to make the tool or material available for a future worker to use. A hammer, saw, nails and wood might be necessary, but are not sufficient, to build a house – a construction worker has to know how to use these things in order to make that happen.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) Adopt evolutionary, adaptive and open system approach to building and operating EarthCube as a federation of systems.
- 2) Treating EarthCube as a federation of system, conceptual design shall not prescribe specific capabilities of individual systems, beyond recommending them to be compliant with specifications defined in EarthCube Registry. EarthCube merely registers these capabilities and ensures that they are monitored and evaluated.

- 3) To adapt to emergent needs and system behavior, conceptual architecture needs to focus on principles, meta-level structures, main information flows, and interfaces.

2.3 Specific objectives for EarthCube: Key Projections

Table 1 (below) summarizes goals and strategies that are to be enabled by the EarthCube design. These are categorized to reflect key EarthCube-related transformations in technical, community development and education aspects of geoscience enterprise. We identify high-level gaps between the desired state and the current mechanisms supporting geoscience cyberinfrastructure, and point to the main strategies to address such gaps. The respective strategies and roadmaps are explored in more detail later in the document.

Table 1. EarthCube objectives: current state, target state, transformation strategies

Aspect	Current process	Goal	Main Strategies
Smart infrastructure for federation of systems	Little guidance to create federations of systems ensuring performance and sound research designs	Information systems are inventoried and documented, with clear access protocols and policies at the component level. Evolutionary interoperability agreements across systems are in place.	Create and document component inventories including APIs and policies; demonstrate how systems and components can be federated on demand and co-evolve using a limited number of standard reference points with clear governance.
Continuous integration of new capabilities into research designs	Geoscience models take significant time to reconfigure and validate for new data and modules	Models self-instantiate as new data and other resources become available and continuously integrated; results are compared with earlier runs. Linked components share their status and capabilities in a manner similar to Internet of Things.	Develop standards-based validation and status reporting services to be included in all components; leverage continuous integration models from software development.
Re-use of resources across information systems	Typically complicated and ad hoc, requiring a number of case-by-case domain-specific translations; with unknown quality especially when translating across spatial, temporal and semantic frameworks and resolutions. Components are typically “baked into” existing information systems and hard to modularize for re-use	Transparent, scientifically-sound and reproducible resource discovery and re-use, with recorded provenance and use track record of each component, and a community maintained library of transformations across recognized information models, formats and protocols	Inventory and integrate available software libraries and resource catalogs, develop provenance recording, use monitoring and annotation services for common re-use patterns; continuously assess “readiness for re-use” of resources throughout their lifecycle
Extending information systems to handling bigger data volumes, more data streams, diverse data, at finer resolution, acquired or generated more frequently (Big Data manage-	Multiple Big Data projects exist but they are poorly integrated and far from mainstream science enterprise. A now common issue of extending operational information systems by adding more sensors, increasing resolution of the data, generating higher-dimensional model output – does not have a general solution	Information systems of different types can be seamlessly extended/scaled on demand, by engaging elastic storage and computational resources, and considering scalability issues in all components of individual systems and EarthCube federation of systems	For common situation that require scaling data acquisition, processing, storage and other resources, identify key bottlenecks and develop architecture design patterns that can be used as a reference for designing scalable information systems

Aspect	Current process	Goal	Main Strategies
ment) Communication and feedbacks	Typically confined to individual domains and domain information systems, no interoperable mechanism for tracking system-wide communications	Communications, in the form of research products, Q&As, support forums, annotations, analysis of system logs, are interoperable and used to adjust the functioning of EarthCube federation and subsystems	Develop federation-level feedback mechanisms and metrics, based on standard protocols and identifiers for research products
Role of architecture and conceptual design	Formally done in isolated projects in selected geoscience disciplines, but mostly information system architectures are developed ad hoc, with little coordination	The need for compatible design is recognized in all geoscience branches; individual projects are developed as components in a system of systems, and follow re-usable architecture design patterns ("reference architectures") reflecting core principles and interfaces of EarthCube	Develop exemplar conceptual designs, relying on common design specifications; modular approaches; broad community of practice that track a number of key system metrics; design activities are recognized and supported by funders
Documentation of information systems	Documentation of requirements and capabilities is disconnected from system engineering tools, and is inconsistent across research and development teams. Research papers remain the main documentation mechanism	Users evaluate, document, and use systems for research as an integrated part of EarthCube design and development practice. Research papers are also transformed to expose formal documentation and provenance of the results, and allow reproducibility.	Develop and promulgate documentation standards and best practices for information systems, resources, and research products; integrate with resource life cycle and product evaluation.
Effective decision-making based on information and analysis	Limited number of architecture design alternatives (patterns) explored, with a limited number of decision-making and infrastructure composition tools to aid in developing custom solutions. Science marketplace is under-developed, in particular with respect to information for decision-making	Decision-making support tools and up-to-date information/documentation provide an ability to assess multiple alternative designs for a specified research problem, and arrive at an optimal solution (composition of resources), selecting from a large pool of registered resources, thus enabling efficient marketplace	Develop ability to virtually compose CI components, and generate and evaluate alternative designs, based on standards-based information about available re-usable components, technical trends, grand challenge research problems
Management of technical CI risks, resiliency	Fault detection and recovery is fragmented; resilience is accomplished at the level of individual components (and not always); lack of monitoring results in slow and inadequate response to faults and risks	Management of system faults and recovery will be dynamic, and trigger revisions and adjustments throughout the reference architecture; resilience is accomplished at the federation of systems level	Include feedback tracking, standardized fault reporting, and analysis in all phases of system development and operation; feed analysis of both technical and research design failures into architecture design

Aspect	Current process	Goal	Main Strategies
Security and trust in a federated system	Security is an afterthought, security experts work on individual systems, and are hard pressed to keep up with intruders. Federating systems with different and inconsistent security models is a serious challenge.	Security considerations are integral to systems design; different systems adopt interoperable approaches to authentication and authorization management, to implement federation-wide access policies; system monitors for security flaws.	Develop authentication and authorization systems to share credentials and access federated repositories; clarify boundaries between security domains; develop components to continuously test security; implement rule-based authorization
Support for interdisciplinary, collaborative teams	Project and team management, system development and research processes are separate activities with separate information support; currently require manual coordination	Architecture integrates collaborative research with software development, management and monitoring of workflows and resource life cycles	Develop use cases demonstrating linked research, development, management, and open scholarly communication, in particular feedback across all phases of research and product life cycle
Infrastructure for supporting a diverse community of researchers and their needs	Community information and knowledge is hidden in various disparate databases: federal, institutional, personal. Community structure and affiliations only available through related journals and publications.	Community collaboration environments organize science resources including data, software, researcher profiles, Q&A and other support tools, to support collaborative work across domain systems	Advance and integrate early attempts to develop such generic collaborative environments (eg leveraging SciCrunch, VIVO, StackExchange.)
Integrating stakeholder interests and concerns	Limited explicit accounting of stakeholder concerns and interests, integration is ad hoc; lack of infrastructure and institutional support for building communities of practice and stakeholder alignment	Stakeholder concerns are explicitly defined; CI assists stakeholder alignment; a system of policies and rewards for cross-stakeholder communication is explicit	Maintain public stakeholder maps; develop dependency graphs to ensure system integrity and traceability from stakeholder concerns to system components.
EarthCube education and workforce development	Education is typically confined to disciplinary domains	New generation of scientists is trained using a core EarthCube curriculum, which emphasizes cross-domain science and infrastructure use	Develop curriculum modules centered around cross-domain collaborative research using advanced geoscience CI
EarthCube system engineering: new job descriptions and competencies	No such specialization apart from ad hoc system integration	Federation of systems becomes a core competency, including integration tools and standard information models, as well as socio-technical and domain understanding	Early career researchers and developers are trained in understanding federation of systems theory and practice, and cross-domain standards

RECOMMENDATIONS:

1. EarthCube design shall clearly outline the key improvements it will offer beyond the current state of the art in research cyberinfrastructure, and measurable and relevant strategies required to achieve EarthCube goals.
2. EarthCube design is a large-scale multi-faceted effort, which involves a number of technical, social, organizational, and educational aspects (15 of them are demonstrated in the table). General EarthCube CI development strategies are derived from comparing the desired state of geoscience CI in 20 years with the current status.

2.4 Clarifying key design terms

Converging on the meaning of key design terms among broad groups of EarthCube stakeholders is critical for effective communication of design ideas and development patterns, in particular to geoscientists. Several of the terms we discuss below have been already used in the preceding sections. For consistency purposes, in the rest of the design document, we provide their definitions and discussion with respect to EarthCube. The selected concepts discussed below are most central to this document, starting with 'architecture' and 'enterprise'. For other terms readers are referred to the information model presented in section 6.4 Information view, and to the semantic wiki developed by the GEAR project with guidance from the EarthCube Science Committee.

2.4.1 Conceptual design and architecture

“Look at all the efforts that have been launched under the idea of architecture and all the money that has been spent under the umbrella of architecture that has all resulted in unusable shelfware.”
— Paul Brubaker, co-author of the Clinger-Cohen Act, 2005

In the EarthCube context, terms “conceptual design”, “architecture”, “conceptual architecture” and “enterprise architecture” have been often used interchangeably; we provide an explanation here of how we are using these terms. **Conceptual design** is a high-level abstraction of a system primarily concerned with translation of user requirements and context into language understood by both EarthCube science users and EarthCube technical development stakeholders, with explanation of new ideas that would bring conceptual visions of different groups of stakeholders together. The next system design step, often referred to as “**logical design**,” usually involves a more detailed elucidation of component functionality and the protocols and information models needed for communication between components to organize them into a functional system reflecting the requirements developed at the conceptual level. As opposed to “conceptual design”, “logical design” is articulated in technical terms, to ensure completeness and consistency of the proposed solution with respect to high-level design, technical standards, and operations. Further, “**physical design**” articulates specific implementation details that can be translated into running code and application configurations.

Several viewpoints for describing an information system are identified in the **Reference Model for Open Distributed Processing** (RM-ODP, ITU-T Rec. X.901-X.904 and ISO/IEC 10746 (<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/RM-ODP>)). They include 1) The *Enterprise View*, focused on vision, mission, policies, and business requirements (similar to the conceptual design); 2) *Information View*, focused on structures and semantics, the information content of the system; 3) *Computation View*, focused on decomposing the system into functional units and the interfaces and workflows through which they interact (similar to the logical design); 4) *Engineering View*, focused on the processing and mechanism used by the system to implement functionality; and 5) *Technology View*, focused on the specific technology used to implement system components and function (similar to the physical design). The Enterprise and Information views are dictated by use cases and requirements emerging from the EarthCube Roadmaps, Charrettes, domain workshop meeting reports, and other input from domain and computer scientists, and other EarthCube stakeholders. The conceptual design document primarily presents the Enterprise view of EarthCube, while we include elements of other viewpoints to define functional organization, information models and protocols to be used within the system. These other viewpoints are presented at an abstract level because specific protocols and formats are likely to change as EarthCube will evolve over the expected design timeframe (10-15 years) – yet the design should be able to accommodate protocol changes within defined functional components and interactions.

The term **Architecture** may be used to refer to any of these design viewpoints, emphasizing the system’s internal organization and behaviors, and its structure as a collection of functional components presented at different abstraction levels and their communication mechanisms. **Enterprise architecture** describes an “enterprise” (to be defined for EarthCube below), articulating its organization and functions and focusing on common goals and strategic outcomes for all stakeholders. In case of a single company, enterprise architecture is “the organizing logic for business processes and IT infrastructure reflecting the integration and standardization requirements of the company's operating model”, where the latter represents “the desired state of business process integration and business process standardization for delivering goods and services to customers” [Weill, 2007]. Significant work on Enterprise Architecture has been done in the federal government (see <http://www.whitehouse.gov/omb/e-gov/fea>), with Federal Enterprise Architecture covering over 300 organization entities, over 2.6 million people, and over \$80 billion of annual federal spending on information technology. Here, Enterprise Architecture is defined as the “the management best practice which can provide a consistent view across all program and service areas to support planning and decision-making” (The White House, [Approach to federal enterprise architecture](#)), enabling four primary outcomes: service delivery; functional integration; resource optimization, and authoritative reference; at eight levels of scope: international, national, federal, sector, agency, system, application and segment (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. The common approach to Federal Information Architecture

In this conceptual design document we follow the definitions and approach of the FEA, using it as a) an example of an extensive enterprise architecture design, and b) as a system with which EarthCube will need to interoperate. At the same time, we need to acknowledge extensive critique of the FEA experience, in particular the vagueness and wide misuse of the term “architecture” in FEA (see [Why Doesn't the FEA Work](#)), which possibly complicated common understanding of information system design. FEA experience presented a number of lessons learned, including:

- the need to analyze and track performance and determine causes of failures;
- disambiguating “reference models” to be used across agencies, following consistent semantics and simple resource taxonomies to avoid terminological confusions;
- focusing EA design on standards, best practices and decision-support;
- emphasizing common repository aspects of EA;
- distinguishing between “technology architecture” and “enterprise architecture”, where the latter includes organizational, planning, resource management and related business aspects, and explicitly addressing non-technical aspects of the design ;
- favoring a limited set of key indicators to assess progress rather than unnecessarily-complex “maturity frameworks”;
- having a clear conceptual framework rather than a series of overlapping enterprise frameworks.

The EarthCube conceptual design presented in this document, follows the above recommendations. At the same time, we acknowledge that the “science enterprise”, which is to be supported by Earth-Cube, is significantly different from the enterprise of the federal government, which FEA is designed to support, or from the enterprise of individual federal agencies or large organizations, for which enterprise frameworks have been developed. The latter include The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF, <http://www.opengroup.org/subjectareas/enterprise/togaf/>), The Department of Defense Architecture Framework (DoDAF) - both initially developed by the US Department of Defense, and the original Zachman enterprise ontology developed by John Zachman at IBM [Zachman, 1987, 1997]. It is not clear to what extent such organization-focused enterprise frameworks apply to the “science enterprise”, with its specific development models involving multiple stakeholders, rapid evolution of research needs and technical capabilities, and absence of a single procurement authority. While there are a lot of commonalities between our approach and these frameworks (in particular, emphasis on the layered view of enterprise architecture design, standards-compliance, well-defined and documented data models, service orientation, metrics and maturity models, resource life cycles, common resource taxonomies), they don’t address several critical components of EarthCube long-term functioning which are in the center of our model, such as supporting science enterprise, supporting scholarly communication across domains and enabling science marketplace. These key notions are discussed later in this section.

2.4.2 Marketplace

A recent disruptive shift in several economic sectors is a strong movement towards a “shared economy” business model where providers and consumers of information or services meet in a virtual transparently managed marketplace. While it’s been most visible in transportation services (Uber, Lyft), hotel accommodations (AirBNB) and office space rental (Breather), and online retail (Amazon, eBay), other key sectors, such as manufacturing, education and health care, are increasingly undergoing transformation. AirBNB is the world’s largest accommodation provider, but it doesn’t own or manage real estate - apart from indirectly influencing management by providing renter satisfaction scores and feedback. Uber is the world’s largest taxi provider but it doesn’t own vehicles. In manufacturing, the advance of 3D printing and the ability to share printing patterns is threatening manufacturers that follow traditional business models. In the core of this new “collaborative economy” is a match-making platform where services and capabilities are advertised, matched with needs (e.g. transportation requests), and the quality of experience is evaluated to inform future transactions.

Similar changes have been happening with the science enterprise as well. For example, there is a long established practice in the software world for copyrighting digital materials, managing intellectual

property rights, and different types of licenses have been in use. Shared use models for high-performance computing resources, pooling resources within universities and emerging virtual organizations, and the move to the cloud, manifest proliferation of pay-per-use service provisioning model in hardware infrastructure, especially for unique resources and expertise. Moving to such a marketplace in the science domain requires clarification of several issues that may not have been explicitly addressed earlier, such as the issues of ownership of different types of resources, ownership transfer across different layers of the system, licensing use of such resources, registering, advertising and discovering resource capabilities, and reporting their use.

Following this model, we can envision EarthCube as not the owner or generator of research content and research resources, but a platform where such content (datasets, research products, service capabilities, expertise and other resources) becomes easy to discover, interpret, access and re-use in new research projects. While in a science enterprise the demand and supply (needs of scientists and available resources) would be infinitely more complex and diverse than in the case of transportation services, the key issues of information support, maintaining trust in the marketplace, awareness of the available products and requests, engagement between providers and consumers, and continuous monitoring and feedback about this experience remain key common components. A platform for enabling geoscience-wide resource marketplace has not yet been conceptualized or developed. This document puts it in the center of conceptual design.

2.4.3 What is a resource

Throughout this document we talk about geoscience information resources of different types. These include data resources, knowledge bases, models, people and organizations, software tools, use cases, publications. They have both common metadata, and type- and domain-specific descriptions. To support efficient management, discovery and re-use of geoscience resources, and enable resource marketplace, the design should be able to characterize them based on the following questions:

- What is the type of the resource?
- How to publish, share and advertise the resource for different audiences, including the entire EarthCube federation?
- How to describe resources, to let members of EarthCube find them, evaluate different resource versions, and assess their quality and fitness for purpose?
- How to manage resource lifecycle, communicate lifecycle status and changes to EarthCube members, and ensure that resource information on EarthCube marketplace is current?
- How to find policies associated with the resource?
- How to access the resource from software environment adopted in user's domain?
- How to provide feedback to resource publishers and potential resource users, to steer further resource development, its sustainability, and build a body of knowledge about the resource?
- How to describe connections between a current resource and other resources?
- How to manage resource identity and consistently reference the resource, to ensure reproducibility of associated research workflows and results?
- How to enhance and evolve resource descriptions and resource discovery and access mechanisms to ensure that they remain useful as research designs and supporting architectures changes?
- How to transform resources for use with processing services, analytical software, models, visualization tools, etc. in an efficient and scientifically-sound manner?

- How to get credit for publishing resources?
- How to manage and reconcile different versions and copies of the resources, and sustain them?
- What is resource governance, and mechanisms for changing resource publication, management, access etc. policies?

The notion is closely related to the concept of “research objects”, as a new approach to aggregating related research resources, referencing them using a single identifier, and exchanging such aggregates on the web. Similarly, our concept of resources and their aggregations (resources compositions, or objects), emphasizes resource identity, ability to be aggregated with composite resources, and ability to annotate resources. Emphasis on a marketplace where different types of resources can be shared, discovered, and matched with needs of researchers, is a contribution of this document.

2.4.4 The Science Enterprise

The basic activity of traditional scientific enterprise consists in asking questions, collecting information, formulating hypotheses, testing those hypotheses to determine which (if any) provide a satisfactory answer to the question, and finally documenting and disseminating the results to enable others to benefit from the research. The initial stages of this process are commonly founded on information collected during previous studies, made available through published literature, conference presentations, or through discussions between practitioners. This learning and exploration phase must be supported by resources to locate and access existing information and to network with other practitioners. Hypothesis testing requires the collection and analysis of new observation data, or the re-analysis of existing data in a new way. Publication of results requires communication channels that are accessible, enable users to locate relevant information, and conduct discussion of results to further their science. The purpose of the EarthCube cyberinfrastructure is to increase the efficiency and productivity of these activities, to extend our knowledge of the Earth, help address key societal values and priorities related to functioning of the earth system, and advance geoscience research and learning community. At the same time, the traditional hypothesis-driven science enterprise model has been increasingly supplemented by a new “data-driven” model, where new large datasets are being developed, and their availability, in turn, drives research questions. EarthCube CI should enable the different routes to scientific productivity, by articulating science needs to data and technology providers – and also by presenting the newest data and technical advances to scientists. Fostering the two-way exchange between geoscience researchers and data and information scientists is the key feature of the EarthCube initiative, and supporting such two-way matching would be a central function of the EarthCube platform.

The NSF research enterprise is unlike traditional large-scale engineering projects. Research priorities are established by program managers and advisory committees, but allocation of resources is based on a proposal review process that depends on who submits proposals, the scientific merit of the proposals received as assessed by peer review panels, and the reputation of the proposal submitters based on publications and social networking. Fostering innovation and the development and testing of new scientific ideas is a paramount goal of the enterprise. The scope of EarthCube science enterprise extends beyond NSF-supported activities, and includes geoscience-related efforts supported by other agencies, universities, companies, and individual researchers - as reviewed in the EarthCube stakeholder section (Section 2).

There are different perspectives on science enterprise, and on how it can work as a system – with a strong framework that considers science as ultimately disjoint, disrupt-

Figure 5. The science enterprise.

tive activity, multi-level, unbounded. This means that not all components of the enterprise can be, or would be meaningful, to formalize. Need to keep it from getting rigid.

Science enterprise is commonly depicted as a cyclical activity describing the path from ideas, formulating hypotheses and building research teams, to publications, with a series of research data collection, processing and analysis steps, and feedbacks at each step (e.g. Figure 5). This model of knowledge production (science) becomes more distributed, open, faster and collaborative. The distinct structures and trends in the science enterprise determine features of supporting cyberinfrastructure.

2.4.5 Domain, and cross-domain

Figure 6. Geoscience sub-domains for EarthCube (source: NSF)

The term “**domain**” (or “scientific domain”) denotes the community of researchers who identify themselves with a particular branch of science enterprise, are intimately familiar with a range of datasets and applications, hypotheses generation and testing procedures, and adhere to specific science communication and dissemination arrangements and other professional practices. This includes an understanding of the data acquisition process involving instruments, measurement protocols, data processing, assumptions and background knowledge, typical problems that arise in the acquisition and processing workflow, and interpretation procedures. Such knowledge is typically considered a prerequisite for scientifically reliable

use of the data and software tools and models, and the development of sound conclusions based on it. An NSF view of geoscience domains to be engaged in the EarthCube CI is shown in Figure 6.

One of the key goals of EarthCube is to enable research and learning across geoscience domains, while establishing a common set of abstractions and policies supporting different domains in their participation in the EarthCube enterprise. Several closely-related notions exist, including *multidisciplinarity*, *transdisciplinarity* (Somerville and Rapport, 2000), *interdisciplinarity* and *cross-disciplinarity*, which emphasize different aspects of research activities that span two or more domains. The concept of ‘**cross-domain**’ typically refers to interpreting aspects of one domain in terms of another. It can be thought of in terms of a conceptual knowledge distance, which is measured relative to some ‘local’ (familiar) sphere of activity. Conceptual distance arises from:

- Differences between research intents, assumptions, terminologies and methods in different disciplines

- Differences between practitioners, or between scientists and the public
- Changes in assumptions and methods over time, even within a single discipline.

To enable cross-domain interoperability, processes and infrastructure to minimize this conceptual distance need to be defined. EarthCube should include infrastructure strategies to mitigate potential losses in understanding and translation of meaning between domains.

2.4.6 Federation

There is an ongoing discussion on whether to consider EarthCube a “**system of systems**” (SoS) or a “**federation of systems**” (FoS). The terms are similar, and both have been a subject of recent studies (Maier, 1998; Cuppan, 2001). A system of systems is a composite system in which the component parts are heterogeneous, independently managed, and independently operable on their own, but are networked to achieve shared goals. An open system is a system that can exchange energy, material, and information across its boundaries. Characteristics of an engineered system of systems include (Azani, 2009):

- The system cannot be understood by studying the component parts in isolation. The whole is greater than the parts.
- Requirements and behavior are both emergent and pre-specified. The entire system cannot be designed a priori.
- has an encapsulated, self-contained, and cohesive structure
- network-centric: network-based discovery and dynamic adaptation capabilities of system components
- Subject to predetermined blueprints and interface standards. Can't start from scratch, have to build on existing resources and institutions.
- Depends on symbiotic relationship and open interfaces to function and evolve in an uncertain environment. Participants must get value in return for effort.

In the context of EarthCube, we prefer to use the term “federation of systems”, which is a type of a system of systems that has greater value levels on three dimensions: autonomy, heterogeneity and dispersion (Krygiel, 1999) and has qualitatively different governance and management mechanisms at the “federation” as opposed to the “system” levels. In the case of EarthCube, these would include NSF-supported data and computation facilities, other information systems and projects, agency systems, university research centers and libraries. The vision is not a single managed system that would emerge from interconnecting such individual information system, but an environment conducive for individual systems to declare and federate their resources, for various emerging purposes, and without necessarily entering into long-term formal or systemic relationships. This approach is reflective of how science enterprise works, and is more consistent with treating EarthCube as a federation, where each agent is free to decide which resources to announce and make available, with which other agents to engage, and what level of interoperability to support.

2.4.7 Self-evolving system

The concept of an evolutionary system is based on analogy of a technology environment with the natural biological system. The system consists of a collection of interacting agents, which in this case are information and processing components, organizations and people, and other resources. The success of a particular agent is determined by how well it engages users to support its maintenance and further development. Genetic variability corresponds to the variety of different solutions that are implemented

and available to address particular scientific workflow challenges. The system adapts to the requirements of the users as they select the technology that most effectively meets their needs. The system depends on a constant source of new innovation (genetic variants), and a selection process that steers the system towards continued 'survival' (operation). We envision an EarthCube environment conducive of self-evolution, as enabled by different agents advertising their capabilities and entering into joint projects, continuous feedback on key success metrics to all stakeholders, periodic updates of key integration points (information model and protocol standards), and a system of rewards and governance that encourages efficient, productive and scientifically-sound re-use of information and other resources.

2.4.8 Information model

An information model is a representation of a domain of interest that provides a basis for shared understanding of the meaning of concepts used in that domain, and to describe that understanding in formal technical terms that can be converted into machine-actionable representations. Typically the model will include a definition of the entities of interest in the domain, the properties that are bound to the entities, rules specifying data types and cardinality for properties, and relationships between entities. The high-level information model for EarthCube federation adopted in this conceptual design, will be presented in section 6.

2.4.9 Scope and system boundaries

To support the science enterprise, EarthCube technology should promote careful curation of datasets, support for online archives, sharing of software development effort, sharing and reuse of data and software, documentation and acknowledgement of resource usage, and participation in the community social network. In the narrow sense of EarthCube scope, EarthCube resources will be focused on those required to support the NSF Earth Science enterprise. As a federation of independently managed systems and a resource marketplace, in this narrow sense the EarthCube scope will be confined to specific infrastructure services, agreements and interfaces that enable the evolving federation and the resource marketplace. In other words, from the perspective of this conceptual design, the narrow EarthCube scope won't include development and management of data and other resources created by various EarthCube stakeholders beyond those resources needed to support the resource marketplace.

In other words, EarthCube scope would include a service platform that will let users to discover, interpret, evaluate, access and combine various technical capabilities and expertise, but not the capabilities themselves. In this narrow "federation of systems" view, capabilities of sub-systems (data management services, processing services and models, cloud infrastructure, visualization tools, HPC services, etc. etc.) are outside EarthCube scope if they don't directly support the cross-system platform for discovery, assessment and re-use of technical capabilities. A corollary of such narrow view of EarthCube is that the scope of EarthCube funding should also be limited to direct support of such a platform. In other words, it would exclude development of capabilities that would be primarily at the level of individual systems: these are expected to be developed and maintained with other funds, focused on development of specific software capabilities. Instead, the narrow EarthCube focus would be on a limited set of capabilities organized into a platform that directly enables cross-system discovery, assessment and re-use of information resources, efficient matching them with needs of the geoscience community, and evaluating success of such match-making.

In the larger framework of scientific cyberinfrastructure, other systems are being developed in plant science, bioinformatics, environmental science and other related fields that are providing similar services for those communities. Further, a number of international, national, regional and agency projects

are focused on various aspects of geosciences. To position itself in this information ecosystem, EarthCube must define itself in a narrow and precise manner; this will lead to definition of external interfaces with these other systems, in addition to internal interfaces discussed later in this document. Such a consideration of external interfaces at system boundaries is missing in the traditional RM-ODP model used by most system designs; it is not explicitly required at the enterprise level, while the information and computational levels focus on internal communications. **It is a view of this conceptual design that converging on a narrow definition of EarthCube is critical for outlining its scope, operational mandate, funding priorities, development strategy, and relationships with other systems.**

Keepers of EarthCube institutional memory will attest, however, that EC scope has been discussed since the very beginning of EC, without much forward movement. Therefore, in addition to presenting our view of the scope of EarthCube and the interfaces at system boundaries, we also discuss a governance process of refining the initial scope. We also approach the issue empirically, in a bottom-up manner, by inventorying a list of capabilities developed by EarthCube participants and other projects, and considering criteria for their inclusion as EarthCube resources.

2.4.10 Scholarly Communication

Assuming EarthCube is a research enterprise, scholarly communication is vital for EarthCube to thrive. Growth and expansion of scholarly communication is a key goal of EarthCube, as it is the foundation of knowledge generation and learning. There is no single definition of the term “scholarly communication.” It is sometimes narrowly defined to include only the peer-reviewed literature published upon completion of research [Rowlands et al., 2004] but a broader definition includes all communication among peers [Harnad, 1995] including development and sharing of research products and datasets. Borgman [2000] summarizes scholarly communication succinctly as “the study of how scholars in any field (e.g. physical, biological, social and behavioral sciences, humanities and technology) use and disseminate information through formal and informal channels”. Formal means of communication include publication in peer-reviewed journals, and informal means of communication imply use of channels, such as emails and electronic listservs. In the context of EarthCube, we use the term “scholarly communication” broadly, inclusive of all channels and forms of information and research product dissemination, exchange of requirements and capabilities between members of the EarthCube federation, and the system of feedbacks which is critical for EarthCube evolution and self-adjustment. As in the earlier discussion, we’d like to stress that scholarly communication within EarthCube would need to support both hypothesis-driven research design (where new research questions and requirements are communicated to technology and data partners so that appropriate technical components are assembled or created in a technical design that meets research design requirements) and data-driven research (where new datasets and technical capabilities become the trigger for developing new research questions as scientists explore and mine the data).

2.4.11 Reproducible Science

The effectiveness and performance of models often can only be validated via computational experiments. In most of these cases, the computational results depend on the input data, settings for input parameters, and potentially on characteristics of the computational environment where the experiments were designed and run. Unfortunately, most geoscience models and experiments are specified only informally in papers, where experimental results are briefly described in figure captions; the code that produced the results is seldom available; the data used in the computations may not be precisely referenced or maintained; or full description of the computational environment is missing. In the absence of results that are fully documented, reproducible, and generalizable, it becomes hard to re-use

and extend these results. Besides hindering the ability of others to leverage work produced by other researchers, and consequently limiting its impact, lack of capability to reproduce experiments puts researchers' reputation at stake. At the same time, making an experiment reproducible forces the researcher to document steps in execution workflows in a manner that is transparent to others. This in turn enables the pathways to be analyzed (and audited) and it also helps newcomers (e.g., new students and post-docs) to get acquainted with the problem and tools used. Reproducibility also forces portability which simplifies the dissemination of the results. Last, but not least, preliminary evidence exists that reproducibility increases impact, visibility and research quality.

However, attaining reproducibility for computational experiments is challenging in the geosciences and in other fields. It is hard for authors to derive a compendium that encapsulates all the components (e.g., data, code, parameter settings, environment) needed to reproduce a result, for reviewers to verify the results and the sufficiency of the description, and for potential users to re-create the experiment and the results. There are also other barriers, from practical issues – including the use of proprietary data, software and specialized hardware, to social – for example, the lack of incentive for authors to spend the extra time making their experiments reproducible.

Several EarthCube building block projects have focused on reproducibility and respective technical aspects and workflows. However, a wider conversation is needed in terms of incentives, use cases, working sets, and infrastructures. With reproducibility being one of the core principles of EarthCube design, analysis of technical requirements for enabling cross-domain reproducible science, and development of EarthCube components for documenting, cataloguing and managing reproducible workflows becomes critical, given different reproducibility requirements and data management practices across geoscience domains. Finally, the conduct of reproducible science needs to align itself with scholarly communication for general awareness, education, and communication.

2.4.12 Reference Architecture

Reference architecture is a collection of architecture design patterns documenting common principles, semantics, interfaces and policies for publishing, sharing, discovering, interpreting, monitoring and evaluating different infrastructure capabilities. It is developed to present models (templates) for efficient re-use and composition of such modular capabilities into operational infrastructures to address evolving geoscience research designs. In addition, it provides a common terminology, in which such a design can be described. Discussion of these terms has been the primary goal of subsection 4.4. Further discussions are organized at the EarthCube semantic wiki site developed by the GEAR project. Reference architectures can be developed at different abstraction levels; discussion in this document is confined primarily to the conceptual level, i.e. without references to specific building block or interface implementations (with the exception of a section where we describe the emerging set of EarthCube capabilities developed with EC and closely related funding.)

NSF ACI division has been fostering development of a reference architecture to support academic research. In the case of EC, it represents a multi-tier process to organize and connect a number of key CI building blocks, whose development and maintenance is supported by NSF. These include, for example, iRODS for storage federation, XSEDE for computation, workflow management systems, and a lot of domain specific data analysis, modeling, visualization, etc. tools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. EarthCube has been described from several perspectives, at least as a community process, a software platform, and a funding program. While it is all of the above, converging on a defined

vision will be essential to zero in on expected functionality, scope and boundaries, and other key characteristics of the system to be built.

2. EarthCube shall establish its terminology to clarify usage of key terms and avoid using ambiguous terms (such as “architecture”) without reference to a definition that clarifies meaning. A possible way to maintain recommended terminology with definitions and to track associated discussions is via an EarthCube Semantic Wiki (e.g. http://earthlexicon.sdsc.edu/wiki/Main_Page)
3. Critical notions to clarify for conveying the message of this document include: conceptual design/conceptual architecture, reference architecture, science marketplace, science enterprise, federation of systems, EarthCube resource, EarthCube information model, scope of the design, scholarly communication, reproducible science, and self-evolution. Converging on the meaning of these key terms is critically important for a cross-domain socio-technical system such as EarthCube.
4. Design roadmap for EarthCube should involve both top-down and bottom-up approaches, and take into account both established architecture practices and emerging shared economy principles. To integrate the two approaches, the design can be conceptualized as a high-level composition of functional components and implementation processes – but not prescribe a single top-down architecture. Identifying and abstracting a number of common, widely used compositions (bottom-up) would guide top down design. Components and design patterns that recur in many research component compositions (many of these components are listed and characterized in our component inventory) should be captured and optimized to support sustainable designs.
5. The design would focus on three layers:
 - Inventory of resources (software, hardware, data, expertise) implemented as a community-managed catalog, based on spatio-temporal, syntactic and semantic frameworks that include specifications of recognized information models, vocabularies and other assets needed to interpret resource descriptions in the inventory (information model registry), as well as a testing framework that validates claimed conformance with system practices to assure reliability.
 - Compositions (assemblies) of resources (including people) used to address research program requirements, enabled through a sort of dashboard for scientists, where such compositions can be constructed from components, and managed.
 - A monitoring and evaluation system for components and compositions that implements key EarthCube principles, and assesses components based on several dimensions of compliance. Such dimensions would include assessment of a) whether expressed user requirements are met, b) metrics based on usage logging, community feedback, incidents of cross-domain information re-use, as well as user perception of interoperability, reproducibility, discoverability, interpretability, and c) ethical use of data, including honoring ownership and licensing.
6. At least initially, the design should adopt a narrow and concrete view of EarthCube, so that its development priorities, scope, operational capabilities and external interfaces can be defined in a way that makes it possible to specify EarthCube reference architecture, and create a phased development plan.
7. The design shall be compatible with the reference architecture components already being developed and supported through NSF ACI activities, and support both hypothesis-driven and data-driven workflows

2.5 EarthCube principles related to architecture and data management

There has been an extensive discussion of core principles of EarthCube, within the EarthCube TAC and its work groups, and among broader groups of stakeholder. These principles commonly include, in various combinations: interoperability, extensibility, scalability, sustainability, reliance on information models, efficient re-use of resources and infrastructure established to date, provenance tracking, federation, openness, security, trust, integrity of resources, standards-compliance, and community governance. Several other organization have been working on related principles as well. At the 2015 GEO-XII Plenary and Ministerial Summit (11/2015), the following 10 data management principles were presented, along with implementation guidelines and metrics (GEO Data Management Principles Task Force, 2015)

DMP1: Metadata for Discovery

DMP2: Online Access

DMP3: Data Encoding

DMP4: Data Documentation

DMP5: Data Traceability

DMP6: Data Quality Control

DMP7: Data Preservation

DMP8: Data and Metadata Verification

DMP9: Data Review and reprocessing

DMP10: Persistent and Resolvable identifiers

The explanation of principles was followed by a survey of data producers, data managers and data consumers who were asked to identify practices, difficulties, and implementation challenges for each of the 10 principles (see <http://maxim.ucsd.edu/suave/index.html?file=GEODataMgtPrinciples.csv> to explore responses using the SuAVE (besuave.azurewebsites.net) survey analysis system). As another example, a related list of data principles has been recommended for adoption by the Belmont Forum (<http://www.bfe-inf.org/info/data-principles>). According to them, data should be discoverable, accessible, understandable and interoperable, manageable, and supported by a skilled workforce (the Belmont Forum Open Data Survey is also available using the SuAVE viewer at <http://maxim.ucsd.edu/suave/index.html?file=BFSurvey2.zip&type=csv&view=map>). In systems engineering, such dimensions are often referred to as “system quality attributes”, or “non-functional system requirements”, and include over 50 measures (e.g. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Non-functional_requirement.) Further, some of these measures have been standardized as characteristics of software quality in ISO/IEC 25010:2011. In addition, data management principles and guidelines have been developed by governments (e.g. the U.S. President's Executive Order introducing the new open data policy, <https://www.whitehouse.gov/the-press-office/2013/05/09/executive-order-making-open-and-machine-readable-new-default-government->). Eight principles of Open Government Data (<https://opengovdata.org/>) include data being 1) complete, 2) primary, 3) timely, 4) accessible, 5) machine processable, 6) non-discriminatory, 7) non-proprietary, and 8) license-free. The principles developed in the course of recent GEO and Belmont Forum work would apply in the EarthCube context, while government open data principles would apply partially to the science enterprise, where researchers rely on data from multiple government, commercial and other sources.

With such significant prior work focused on system quality attributes and principles of data management and software engineering, and respective quality metrics, we believe that EarthCube should recognize and re-use the already established frameworks instead of offering yet another set of general principles – especially where such principles are accompanied by metrics and assessment procedures. Therefore, we recommend adopting relevant principles and metrics from those listed above, to specific architecture implementations. At the same time, we emphasize those principles that pertain to our specific vision for EarthCube, as related to development of a science marketplace, federation of systems, and development of a platform for matching user needs and technical capabilities, as the core mission of EarthCube.

In the most recent development (March 2016), the Committee on Environment, Natural Resources, and Sustainability of the National Science and Technology Council, OSTP, Office of the President, published a “Common Framework for Earth Observation Data.” This framework provides guidance for federal agencies that produce and publish earth observation data and derived data products. It envisions a lightweight standards-based ecosystem of services supporting data search, discovery and access, emphasizing data documentation and capability of formats and vocabularies. These four framework layers support a variety of user-focused tools, including portals and analysis and modeling software, at the same time providing a common view over multiple federal data repositories. This conceptual model is presented in Figure 7 (which is Figure 1 in the original document). It follows the data management principles proposed for implementation in the earlier GEO document and listed earlier in this section. This conceptual framework and the proposed components match closely our conceptual design. As will be shown in subsequent sessions, in addition to standards-based data discovery and access components, documentation and shared formats and vocabularies, our design advocates development of a market platform, monitoring and evaluation components, treatment of other geoscience information resources in the same manner as data (i.e. making them discoverable, accessible, documented, and compliant with known formats and semantic, spatial and other conventions), monitoring evolving research requirements, and ability to compose (and possibly sustain) resources answering specific research problems. These additional capabilities derive from analysis of EarthCube communities and their needs presented in section 3.

Figure 7. USGEO Conceptual Model (source: OSTP: Common Framework for Earth Observation Data, 2016)

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Adopt system design and data management principles already developed in related projects or outlined in governance documents, as relevant to use case-specific architecture implementations. In particular, ensure compatibility with relevant US Government initiatives focused on consistent management, publication and integration of earth observation data, since leveraging these data sources is a key requirement of geoscientists.
2. As additional core EarthCube design principles, emphasize development of a science marketplace supporting science enterprise and matching user needs with available technical capabilities in a federation of systems. This requires a clear outline of frameworks for registering and understanding of available resources, including their fitness for use in research designs, a dynamic inventory of such resources driven by research demands, and a system for monitoring

and assessing the use and performance of the resources, and for composing working systems from the resources.

2.6 Specific capabilities and features of Geoscience CI

While EarthCube cyberinfrastructure will generally follow and implement principles, interfaces, semantics and policies characteristic of state-of-the-art system of systems design in other science domains, there are several features that geosciences are specifically concerned about. Such features and capabilities will be emphasized by EarthCube CI design, and will define its specialization among cyberinfrastructures supporting the science enterprise in other disciplines, and connection points with the latter.

Specific concepts inherent in geospatial research have been systematized in literature on spatial information systems. For example, Kuhn (2012) proposed 10 core concepts of spatial information, including the concepts of *location*, *neighborhood*, *field*, *object*, *network*, *event*, *granularity*, *accuracy*, *meaning*, and *value*. In his model, these concepts would help establish community consensus, and also enable scientists in other domains to find connection points to the Geographic Information Science community. Additional summaries of core geospatial concepts have been outlined in (<http://teachspatial.org/resource-browser>) and (http://gis.lanecce.edu/gtft/gtft_readings/gtft_reading_wk2-1/SpatialThinking_Summary.pdf.) Such concepts percolate through the entire stack of geoscience infrastructure components and capabilities, including:

- 3D/4D/5D information models describing geospatial data in time and space, as well as in the context of dynamic processes studied by geoscientists
- Integration models that emphasize space and time as universal bridges linking together disparate geospatial information
- Variety of semantic convention, which should be clarified and formalized, in particular, with respect to core concepts such as “*location, neighborhood, field, object, network, event, granularity, accuracy, meaning, and value*” (Kuhn, 2012)
- Ability to explore geoscience processes across spatial and temporal scales, i.e. inclusion of various techniques for upscaling, downscaling, aggregation and disaggregation
- Special visualization capabilities to co-locate geoscience information and depict processes in space and time, in particular through maps, virtual globes, map-based animations, etc.
- Special types of discovery queries, based on spatio-temporal joins and predicates that reflect the core concepts mentioned above
- Information inventories that characterize observed geospatial features from several perspectives defined in geoscience information models and include common observations parameters that reflect space and time of the observation, observed variables, geoscience processes and features of interest, methods for observing and transforming the results, etc.
- Emphasis on observations in space and time (as opposed to experimentation) and significant role of field data collection.
- The complex logic of correlating observed spatial relationships to infer temporal relationships and for establishing geochronologic positions using radiometric and other methods.

While EarthCube CI will likely leverage designs and components developed in other disciplines, it is expected that its core competency, specific scope and contribution will be in development of capabilities described above.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. For EarthCube CI to be efficient, it must focus its efforts on capabilities that are specific to the needs of geoscientists, while leveraging, to the extent possible, CI infrastructure components developed in other disciplines.
2. CI development and funding decisions should include assessment of not only whether a proposed capability fills an identified gap, but also whether it is specific to and within the scope of geoscience CI.
3. Clearly outlining unique capabilities of EC will help define its interfaces and synergies with systems in other domains, avoid duplication of effort and overlaps, and support collaborations.

3 EarthCube communities and their needs

While there are common cyberinfrastructure issues that information systems need to address, different research designs, data collection and management practices, processing and analysis routines result in different user needs across groups and domains. In this section, we present various perspectives on EarthCube requirements, user interests and needs, and identify common requirements expressed by different groups.

As this section demonstrates, the requirements are of several types, including those that are fairly concrete and can guide integrated system development in the short-term; high-level expectations that can be converted into specific requirements for medium-term development; and general vision of EarthCube future pointing to a need for a system that can adapt to new challenges and research designs. We first present a sampling of observations from different domain scientists within EarthCube, organized by phases of the science enterprise.

Table 2. EarthCube communities with example requirements and interests based on EarthCube domain workshop summaries and survey results. Columns represent phases in the science enterprise

Domains	Sample Science Driver Questions	Data Collection	Research Design	Testing Hypotheses	Information Sharing and Discovery
Structural Geology and Tectonics	How do mantle processes influence crustal deformation?	Integration of disparate data sets across disciplines Tools to handle format conversion issues	Better research design can be performed if vast number of geological maps can be converted into a functional digital form.	Need a science workbook tool to gather all relevant data together for co-viewing and analysis	Google Earth-like Data Clearinghouse with search facilities along spatial, temporal and thematic axes
Early Career	No Science Driver Questions. Most issues related to existing practices, reward schemes for data sharing, and more involved role of funding bodies and professional societies so that data-related efforts of early career scientists are recognized	Accessible data submission interface Need for data security	Predictive modeling tools Access to “Big Data” tools and techniques Infrastructure for storage and data access Alignment of data with ontologies for interoperability	Need mechanism to associate data with citations such that the more accessed data can be considered more valuable	One-stop shopping for improved access to data Support for Hackathon-style workshops

Domains	Sample Science Driver Questions	Data Collection	Research Design	Testing Hypotheses	Information Sharing and Discovery
Earthscope	What is the present-day active deformation of the North American continent and how is this deformation related to the seismic activity, the growth and activity of faults, and volcanism?	Flexible way of specifying, capturing, querying of metadata for earth science data objects Data format management and conversion facility Data integration for complex geoscience data	Estimation of errors in data, and curation Need to partner with HPC systems to perform scalable computation Matchmaking between earth scientists and Computer/ Computational Scientists Web accessible platform for computational tasks API for “standard” earth science data manipulation, query and analysis	Analyses will be facilitated by the ability to access older data EarthScope investigators need to import data from outside of their immediate area of specialization. They need tools and methods to judge and assess errors, uncertainty, reproducibility and consistency associated with raw data and data products at all levels	An enhanced, but simplified, open source platform for the 3D and 4D spatial integration of geological volumes, points, lines, and surfaces
Experimental Stratigraphy	Relationship between phenomena like sea-level rise and coastal change, natural hazards, and natural resource exploration	Mechanisms to collect and harmonize data that have been collected by international groups	Infrastructure for managing and collaborating on data issues	A common accessible testbed where data can be placed and computational experiments can be carried out	Framework and model that allow scientists to gather and distribute large experimental data volumes for broad use beyond the original investigation
Data Assimilation and Ensemble Mediation	What observations are critically needed to enhance atmospheric predictions, and where?	Data integration platform Platform and services to plug data into predictive models	Data set repository	A place for advanced software, tool kits and services for quality control, data analysis, visualization, verification and mining	An active forum for cross disciplinary interaction and matching research needs with existing capabilities
Critical Zone	How do tectonics, lithology, climate and biology co-determine the evolution of critical zone structure and function?	Integration with wireless sensor networks for measurement	Mechanism to assess, record and interpret uncertainty and variability among data items	A “toolbox” to enable scientists and data managers to more easily manage local data, publish data to repositories and access existing data resources using web ser-	One stop shop (resource discovery platform) for data and tools for scientists

Domains	Sample Science Driver Questions	Data Collection	Research Design	Testing Hypotheses	Information Sharing and Discovery
Envisioning a Digital Crust	How to develop a synthetic understanding of forcing of groundwater flow over many scales? How can we quantify the distribution and magnitude of fluxes from the brittle to the ductile regime?	One cannot create a simple data set without integrating and interpreting associated data from other subdisciplines	The constant challenge is how to represent different interpretations and capture the knowledge of the scientists that created them, and to quantify and deal with uncertainty.	vices APIs Ability to represent multiple interpretations or sets of geovolumes	The mechanism of data sharing should be flexible enough to enable scientists of different subdisciplines to access and interpret the data (perhaps through data annotations?)
Cyberinfrastructure for Paleogeoscience	Establishment of a 4D framework for life and its environment on Earth Assimilate paleo observations into process-based Earth System Models to reconstruct Earth history Determine climate/ocean/biosphere interactions during times of great change	Consolidation or federation of databases of the same kind	Coupled earth-life system models that have good two-way, "live" integration with distributed data resources Ways to prioritize/incentivize verification of contradictory information	Ability to handle unstructured data Intuitive 4D access to all existing knowledge products and underlying data/metadata and methods used to generate those knowledge products	Difficulty of discovery and vetting legacy data and their associated metadata; lack of funds for digitizing legacy data
Petrology, Geochemistry & Volcanology	Integrate observations at volcanoes (e.g. seismic activity, ground deformation, emissions, magma chemistry and petrology, magma physical properties, plate tectonic parameters) in order to (1) forecast and mitigate natural hazards (2) understand and communicate volcanic impacts on society, and (3) to search for natural resources. • Map the feedbacks between planetary evolution, plate tectonics, volcanic	Data and metadata should be captured at the point of acquisition in a way that they can seamlessly be managed throughout their life cycle, including upload to repositories in order to satisfy data management requirements	Ancillary contextual information such as science objectives, data provenance, and uncertainty estimates at each step in workflow needs to be included with the data	Software packages utilized during data acquisition should be transparent to data analysis and visualization software Systems should be in place to promote spatial contextualization	Improved infrastructure (search engines, catalogs) is needed that facilitates discovery of data, samples, models, and management tools.
Sedimentary Geology	Securing the energy and water resources needed for an increasing global population while balancing resources for a sustainable Earth	Quality, authenticity, coordinate systems, collection methodology etc. must be properly docu-	Uncertainty in observational data like measured stratigraphic sections No easy way to integrate subsur-	Inadequate documentation of data (lack of location data, meaning of data, unstated uncertainty and re-	Knowledge regarding what database and tools exist Interoperability between data sources due to

Domains	Sample Science Driver Questions	Data Collection	Research Design	Testing Hypotheses	Information Sharing and Discovery
		mented for primary data collection and for secondary data access	face and surface data Drill hole that integrates or links across state boundaries	producibility, no stratigraphic/facies context, incomplete age information, is it raw or corrected data, how was it corrected).	vendor's proprietary data formats A Google Earth-like interface is envisioned with topography, surface, and subsurface geology. The interface would (i) allow a wide range of queries, (ii) compile and visualize a variety of data for different time intervals and geographic locations, and (iii) have the ability to create cross sections from designated line paths and make maps for designated areas and time/depth intervals.
Modeling	How do we integrate the large degree of spatial and temporal variability in our models? How do we determine model uncertainty and communicate it to both scientists and lay persons?		Need the confluence of models of multiple phenomena like geology, geophysics, natural hazards landscape evolution, hydrology, climate, and ecosystems, How should models link to data integration, multi-scale phenomena, and the dynamics of coupled Earth systems	Metadata for both data and models, interoperability and assessing fitness for use across disciplines Access to advanced computing resources	The burden of supporting a code once it has been released to the community How to adequately describe a model and its limitations so that others can assess and use it
Inland Waters Geochemistry, Biogeochemistry & Fluvial Sedimentology	How do seasonality, magnitude and duration of events influence biotic responses? What is the impact of groundwater connectivity on stream process-	Need to assemble a large set of high-quality reference databases for items like: Water and sewage treatment plants,		Understanding and dealing with data quality issues	Data discovery is lacking. Challenge in finding linked data - spatially and temporally Clearinghouse function of Earth-

Domains	Sample Science Driver Questions	Data Collection	Research Design	Testing Hypotheses	Information Sharing and Discovery
Deep Seafloor Processes and Dynamics	es?	groundwater chemistry, watershed activity, ...			cube? Semantic search to handle vocabulary variation
	What is the architecture of the oceanic lithosphere (including magma processes), and what happens to the plate as it ages from spreading center to subduction zone, as a function of spreading rate, environmental variability, variable crustal architecture?	Need to make spatially and temporally co-registered chemical and biological sampling Homogenization of the spatial and temporal scales of data collection	Both the discovery of the required data and synthetic analysis Tools to find what you aren't looking for, e.g., what data are missing that will make analysis much more robust? Data documentation tools	Analysis of data getting increasingly difficult due to the ever-increasing volume of data. Solving data movement is becoming important for analysis of newer data sets	Cross-disciplinary data integration, linking and methods to ensure compatibility Co-operative construction of multidimensional data sets
Real-Time Data	How can we better use real-time data to understand the processes of high impact events or phenomenon like early detection of harmful algae blooms and translate that knowledge to better response procedures?	Tools for integrating and assimilating real-time observations: from differing geospatial and temporal resolutions Frameworks and secure mechanisms for remote operation of instruments	Since there is too much data coming in, what kind of dynamic sampling strategy should be used to collect, analyze, and respond to real-time data How should tasks like instrument validation, awareness of instrument status be integrated into research design?	Analysis will be facilitate if real-time data streams are integrated with downstream decision support systems for use by emergency managers, etc.	Data, hardware and software discovery and access including data sub-setting of large bandwidth streams Rendering of observations with widely different time scales for real-time Displays
Education	What are the attributes of a data-savvy college graduate, skilled at using data and models to answer difficult questions and solve hard problems, facile with systems thinking and interdisciplinary problem solving?	Mechanisms of data collection on education and outcomes of education are not very well established. Methods of assessment of students about their proficiency on data and method related expertise are not well defined	How to design tools and interfaces (normally designed for experts) such that they don't pose a significant barrier for students	Tiered approach to data quality (allowing quality student data to be added, while keeping out inadequate data) Assessment techniques for student mastery of data and modeling practices	High quality instructional materials around models and data Support for citizen science

3.1 Requirements synthesis

Based on the domain workshop summaries (see representative examples in Table 2, above), we can identify a number of critical requirements from most potential users, and other requirements from specific subsets of communities. The key requirements spanning several domains can be summarized as follows:

- With respect to data collection:
 - The size of the data to be collected is getting larger – tools are needed to handle smooth ingestion.
 - Curated, integrated data sets are needed by researchers as a reference against which to compare their own data.
 - Acquisition of data quality, context, and provenance information need to be part of standard data collection workflows.
- With respect to research design
 - Data integration is a primary requirement for researching complex phenomena, but appropriate data integration tools are not available.
 - Understanding and modeling complex phenomena require cross-disciplinary investigation. However, the social mechanism to facilitate such investigation as well as the availability of cross-disciplinary data access capabilities are missing.
 - Research design involves understanding the variability and uncertainties related to data. However, strong models for them and tools/techniques for modeling them are not available.
- With respect to analysis and modeling
 - Big data and HPC tools for large-scale analysis need to be accessible.
 - Facilities to run models online based on user-provided data (model gateways) need to be accessible.
 - Need to have a community repository of analysis tools and models available for reuse.
- With respect to data sharing
 - Standardization of several levels and forms of metadata to promote data sharing.
 - Need an EarthCube portal that provides basic data visualization capabilities and access to EarthCube resources.
 - System needs standard, machine-actionable services to search and find data at multiple levels of granularity.

3.1.1 Underspecified requirements

Geoscience research agendas evolve rapidly as new types of measurements become available, new methods and procedures are developed, and a combination of advances from neighboring research fields brings to life new ideas and projects. It is impossible to precisely anticipate future system requirements and use them in system design. Nor is it possible to design a system that would be prepared to accommodate all new requirements in the long run, without a re-design. Because it supports a constantly evolving research enterprise, the requirements to support research capabilities are inherently time-varying and typically underspecified.

To account for this moving target, the system must be designed for adaptability. The flexibility and configurability of the system can be increased significantly by addressing underspecified requirements in several ways: (1) designing the system in a modular and layered manner, with abstract components that

can be refined, extended, or replaced as new functionality is required; (2) identifying abstract building blocks and layers in the overall EarthCube CI that are responsible for a general class of capabilities (e.g. data discovery, data interpretation, subscription to information feeds, high performance computations) and ensuring that the components that implement these are scalable, configurable, extendable, and accessible via documented and standardized APIs, such that they can be replaced with other implementations without disrupting the system; (3) following standards and best practices for information exchange, in particular standards that have shown their longevity and are managed by respective standards development organizations (SDOs) ensuring that there is a process for amending specifications when new use cases and application needs become available, (4) creating a “continuous design system” in which newly developed building blocks and their capabilities can be seamlessly added and become available to the community for testing and assembly into workflow compositions; (5) supporting continuous annotation of resources by users highlighting successes and failures of using these resources in various research contexts, (6) ensuring that feedback about new requirements and use cases is easy to provide via the community-focused infrastructure building blocks. It is our strong view that these building blocks must not only support scholarly communication and interaction but also make the system more flexible and responsive to change.

3.1.2 User Requirements around scholarly communication

As our Education specialists and Early Career researchers have noted, “keeping up” with scholarly products and following their significance is a crucial and often time-consuming part in a science scholar’s work process. EarthCube can address this need by viewing the needs around scholarly communication as a specific application of the linked data framework.

We define scholarly communication as a combination of broadcasting (e.g., by publishing/disseminating a paper or data or placing documented code in a public repository), targeted communication (e.g., a forum discussion), citation and annotation (e.g., a commentary on someone else’s paper without actually communicating with the authors). Today, a large fragment of scholarly products, and the different forms of communication are already in a digital form, and therefore, are poised to be interconnected creating the linked network of scholarly communication. Fortunately, a number of service organizations has started filling in the ecosystem of scientific interchange. Identity services provided by Vivo and ORCID, repository and bibliographic services provided by organizations like Mendeley and ResearchGate, crowdsourcing methods applied by these organizations for identity-to-digital-object mapping, visibility and influence measurement services from Altmetric, enable users, researchers and publishers to understand, follow, analyze and interpret the space of scholarly communications.

While it is too early to commit to specific set of API from any group, we envision that EarthCube will be built over these repositories and services and possibly create a level of abstraction for finding scientific niches, tracing the origins of an idea by tracing through citations, evaluating impact of a paper inside a specific subdiscipline, getting recommendations for the most suitable scholarly product and so forth. This component of EarthCube will view the data as a graph and use modern semantic graph data management technologies to build a new set of API and utility functions to serve the scholarly needs of the EarthCube community. Based on our experience with both SPARQL engines like Virtuoso, and SciGraph, our own semantic data management system developed over Neo4j, we will propose a draft API for these services.

3.1.3 Communication Feedbacks

EarthCube CI needs to be built around community scholarly interaction modules that are seamlessly-integrated components of geoscience workflows and community organization. Recent thinking on emergent self-organization and evolutionary problem solving by large groups of semi-autonomous individuals identifies key interactions that enable such a system (e.g. Johnson, 2001). Abundant new ideas must be fostered, metrics need to be defined and applied to distinguish and reward ideas that are 'fitter', and feedback between people is necessary to exchange ideas, reinforce good ideas, and pass them to the next generation. Thus, a key role of the communication network is to enable feedback between people in various parts of the system. This may include communication of available information products from data providers to data intermediaries and data consumers, and receiving feedback in terms of usage patterns, annotations, questions and issues; communication of research results from scientists to other scientists through publications and presentations, with feedback in terms of reviews and questions; communication of ideas and results from researchers to funding agencies in the form of proposals and reports; communication of science scenarios from geoscience researchers to computing experts, with feedback about feasibility and costs of implementation, etc. In our approach to EarthCube, sufficient flows of information about available and emerging capabilities, current and forecasted needs, and successes and failures of matching needs and capabilities, are a foundation of a functioning marketplace and for making funding decisions related to sustaining existing or development of new capabilities.

A variety of systems are now available that offer new approaches to community networking, such as GitHub, StackOverflow, MyExperiment, Globus Online, and nanoHub, research profile networks like ResearchGate, academia.com, or Mendeley, semantic web technology like OpenAnnotation and Domeo and impact metrics systems like Altmetric.com and ImpactStory. These systems are currently disconnected, each with their own interfaces and access protocols, and their own learning curves required to realize their potential. These problems are particularly acute when working across traditionally stove-piped communities studying different geoscience subdomains. We are interested in leveraging these new enabling technologies to reward users for engaging with the community to answer questions and share knowledge, and for providing input and feedback as participants in cyberinfrastructure evolution, without overwhelming people with new demands on their time. This will allow EarthCube to support emergent self-organization and evolutionary problem-solving approaches to the challenges facing our science and society.

Therefore, the conceptual design developed by this project focuses on a technological framework to promote networked, cross-discipline, community engagement in EarthCube. The architecture should enable EarthCube system evolution based on innovative ideas from multiple stakeholders and perspectives including science, technology, and governance, with selection and refinement based on end-user guidance and feedback.

From the communications point of view, a successful geoscience cyberinfrastructure is characterized by the effectiveness of communications among stakeholders in the federation of systems. While a detailed characterization of stakeholders is presented in the following section, at a conceptual level we are primarily concerned about communication between scientists and capability providers, mediated by EarthCube governance structures. The following questions are critical to consider:

- Do scientists communicate current and expected needs to scientific governance?
- Does scientific governance communicate these needs to technical governance, in order to match needs with available or emerging capabilities, identify gaps, and develop strategies for

addressing them? Does technical governance efficiently translate the needs and gaps into requirements and appropriate instructions for data providers and capability developers?

- Is communication within science teams between researchers with different skills and backgrounds efficient, and is there a clear mechanism for enabling such teams?
- Do the development community, data providers and intermediaries appropriately communicate resource shortfalls and needs for decisions to technical governance?
- Is there sufficient information in the market place to enable efficient matching of needs and capabilities, and informed selection of the most appropriate capabilities for given science needs?
- Are successes and failure of technological solutions applied to solving science problems documented, and communicated to both scientists and capability developers in a way that enables funding decisions and development of both geoscience research and technical components?,
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RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) EarthCube conceptual design should focus on efficient communication between stakeholders, in particular on the processes of communicating science needs, technical capabilities and constraints, evaluating whether science needs are met, and identifying gaps and further development strategies.
- 2) Communication paths would include verbal communication or rely on exchange of documents, use of services, tools and EarthCube products (which also represent forms of communication.) Specific communication mechanisms should be defined for each channel at the logical design phase.
- 3) Whether the overall pattern of communication advances science is a key EarthCube metric.
- 4) Appropriateness and efficiency (functionality, clarity, expressiveness, timeliness, robustness, completeness, affordability, transparency, accountability, etc.) of communications between stakeholders within a federation of systems is another key metric for EarthCube success.

3.1.4 Capabilities identified by 2011 Charrette

At one of the first EarthCube 'visioning' events, a series of breakout sessions and group discussions led to compilation and synthesis of a list of capabilities that EarthCube was expected to enable. The document is no longer easily accessible, but as of 2015-08-28 was online and downloaded from <http://www.iooc.us/wp-content/uploads/2012/02/EarthCube-CapabilititesallDec16.docx>. The provenance of the list has been lost, but it remains an excellent compilation of expectations for EarthCube that inform system requirements. The reference numbers for the capabilities at the end of each section refer to an original list of 99 from the Charrette and from the virtual sessions, which has apparently been lost.

A. Dataset and Workflow Discovery

- A1. Registration of datasets or workflows (with input parameters) into shared collections or global catalogs
- A2. Upload & publish workflows and data sets
- A3. Search across multiple granularity levels & disciplines for workflows and datasets (using semantic metadata and provenance information when appropriate)
- A4. Data subscription services

Summarized from 6, 63, 67, 76, 80, 89, 93, 98, V3, V27, V28

- B. Metadata for Workflow and Data Sets
 - B1. Automated provenance tracking and tracking of data updates (versioning)
 - B2. Commenting, annotating, rating, and categorization of workflows, data sets, or models (both automatic and manual)
 - B3. Computational environment provenance stored including code, configurations, input and metadata, with a goal toward reproducibility

Summarized from 11, 14, 21, 22, 27, 43, 47, 68, 69, 70, 73, 74, 82, 86, 88, 95, 97, V1, V6, V9, V26
- C. Data Security and Trust
 - C1. Provide single sign-on environment for shared collections spanning administrative domains
 - C2. Flexible access & sharing controls (licensing) of data, models & workflows
 - C3. Issue tracker for problems with data or workflows
 - C4. Protect individual property rights
 - C5. Data trust: ability for users to track data that needs further explanation or is suspect, fault tolerances, automated tools for validation

Summarized from 16, 18, 57, 64, 75, 76, 84, 92, 96, V7, V20; closely related to items in F. Data Management within Workflows and M. Policy Enforcement Processes
- D. Data Access Services
 - D1. Reusable/shared/standard software interfaces for disparate data types
 - D2. Brokering interfaces to manage access to data using disparate storage and all protocols
 - D3. Deliver data in user-requested format and translation between standards
 - D4. Real-time access to data and facilities even in low bandwidth settings
 - D5. Networking and linkage of existing data sets
 - D6. Data curation: Long term preservation, integrity, authenticity & chain of custody

From capabilities list: 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 13, 17, 62, 63, 65, 66, 72, V1, V2, V20, V30, V31. Closely related to items in I. Numerical methods and software engineering
- E. Workflow Execution Management
 - E1. Manage workflow execution in distributed environment – conditional execution, integration with server-side and compute side, interactive
 - E2. Combine components from multiple existing workflow systems or models

Summarized from 29, 33, 47, 77, 78, 79, 83, 85, 90, 94, V10, V24, V30
- F. Data Management within Workflows
 - F1. Caching of intermediate workflow results
 - F2. Automatically propagate uncertainty through workflows
 - F3. Move workflows to data when more sensible
 - F4. Automation of QC/QA procedures where feasible

Summarized from 81, 87, 91, V25. See also C. Data Security and Trust
- G. Modeling Standards and Frameworks
 - G1. Joint 4D framework for interdisciplinary models, data & information
 - G2. Community-based/policed repositories, standards and governance structures for EC compliant tools, and applications that are promulgated
 - G3. A means to discover, publish and reuse computational models within the EarthCube framework

- G4. The ability to compose and integrate models or to extend models into scientific workflows
 - Summarized from capabilities: 25, 26, 28, 34, 35, 37, 42
- H. Modeling Capabilities within Cloud, Grid, HPC, and Science Portals
 - H1. Web service creation and publishing
 - H2. Intelligent data query, retrieval, download and interaction
 - H3. Interacting gridding/regridding, visualization and other manipulation and analysis tools
 - H4. Real-time simulation capabilities and flexible access to high performance computing
 - Summarized from capabilities: 30, 31, 36, 39, 40, 41, 45, 46
- I. Numerical Methods and Software Engineering
 - I1. Experimental facilities and data for model validation
 - I2. Automated software building and validation to ensure stable software releases (e.g. the NMI build-test lab)
 - I3. Standard APIs and model description standards that enable the creation of better and more reliable tools
 - I4. Fault tolerance and reliability built into archival and other systems
 - Summarized from capabilities: 23, 38, V13, V14, V15, V16. Closely related to items in L. Best Practices and D. Continuity, sustainability, and evolution
- J. Tools to Probe, Validate, Verify, and Visualize Data
 - J1. 4D integration of high resolution topography scans & geodetic data
 - J2. Integration of geologic data in deep time
 - J3. Fusion tools that support integration, assimilation & regridding
 - J4. Data mining tools and techniques
 - Summarized from capabilities: 4, 8, 9, 10, 12, 48, 71, 72
- K. Broad Participation: Enable Collaboration and Participation from International, Industry, Academic, NGO and other Domain Partners
 - K1. Linkage with NEON, LTER, state geological surveys, and other communities
 - K2. Low barrier to participation and mechanisms to ensure individual/small voices are heard
 - K3. Outreach to encourage new collaborations
 - Summarized from capabilities: 32, 52, 54, 59, 60, 61, V18, V19, V29, V31
- L. Best Practices & Governance Models for the Development of Definitions & Standards
 - L1. Community identification & commission of programs of work that are deemed important
 - L2. Standards for gridding in models/datasets
 - L3. Standards and best practices for formal data publication and citation
 - Summarized from capabilities: 55, 58, 99, V4, V5, V8. Closely related to items in I. Numerical methods and software engineering
- M. Policy Enforcement Processes
 - M1. Archival policies for integrity, authenticity, versioning, provenance
 - M2. Quality assurance policies
 - M3. Role of publishing houses of scientific literature and engagement to drive compliance with community agreed-upon standards

- M4. Role of funding agencies in driving compliance with community agreed-upon standards
- M5. Ensure community consensus
- M6. Consensus driven decision making

Summarized from 5, 15, 19, 20, 22, 43, 50, 53, 56, V22. Closely related to items in C. Data Security and Trust

N. Continuity, Sustainability, & Evolution

- N1. Social networking sites to support knowledge sharing between disparate teams of computer science/geo scientists
- N2. Global catalogs /directories for data, software, models, workflows, etc.
- N3. Linkage with NEON, LTER, state geological surveys, and other communities
- N4. Fault tolerance and reliability built into archival and other systems
- N5. Usage tracking for tools and datasets
- N6. User support services
- N7. Reward systems for all project roles and contributions
- N8. Long-term financial sustainability planning

Summarized from capabilities: 6, 23, 44, 49, 50, 51, 54, V11, V12, V17, V21, V23

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) Analysis of this list, as well as of early EarthCube Roadmaps, makes it clear that even at the early stages of EarthCube the community has developed a significantly detailed vision of patterns and capabilities of the emergent geoscience CI. However, these descriptions have not been systematized into a system of inter-related capabilities and communication mechanisms. Conceptual design goal is to bring such different capabilities into a consistent design, identifying services that should be central to the system.
- 2) The list of expected capabilities can never be exhaustive, and changes over time.

3.1.5 EarthCube as part of global CyberInfrastructure ecosystem

Various international, large-scale projects and data-sharing communities, including aligned stakeholders and legal arrangements, are currently existing or being developed. A few examples include INSPIRE, NEII, Future Earth, GEOSS, and RDA. In the US, NASA, NOAA, and the USGS all have operational and evolving data distribution systems. The White House has recently released directives aimed at open access to available data and services from all federal agencies. EarthCube will operate within this larger system of systems, and it is considered essential that compatibility with these systems is a design requirement.

3.2 EarthCube scope and stakeholder interests

Considering the list of stakeholders, specialization of EC in a global set of infrastructures, and geoscience user requirements, we arrive at the following statement of the scope of this initiative.

As mentioned above, from our perspective the scope of EarthCube has several levels and depends on the types of engagement of different stakeholders. We will summarize it in the following table

Table 3. Stakeholder interests in EarthCube compiled based on “Earthcube Stakeholder Map” (2014)

Stakeholder group	Considerations
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Stakeholder group	Considerations	
1. EarthCube leaders, developers, participants from academia, whose participation is funded by NSF	Contribution to EC	Glue between systems: principles of EC as a system of system; registry of specifications and interoperability agreements between them; alignment between science needs and technical capabilities, identification of gaps and priorities: the core of EC
	Benefits from EC	Advanced science at intersection of domains; solving challenging computational problems advancing the frontiers of computer science; solving challenging science problems. Recognition; making the difference; networking; funding support.
	Expected alignment/ scope	Commitment to EarthCube goals despite often volunteering expectations and time burden
	Governance mechanisms	Direct governance, via TAC and SC and their subcommittees. Alleviating the burden of unfunded commitments through a system of rewards and recognition.
2. Geoscientists not funded through EarthCube	Contribution to EC	Guidance, evaluation, feedback, research use cases and requirements, opportunity to articulate research needs and find appropriate technologies and expertise EC-wide; point out gaps and influence priorities
	Benefits from EC	Use of EC tools to address research challenges, consult EC-assembled use cases, search EC inventories, follow EC information exchange protocols, find technology partners among EC members; get training in data science and computing
	Expected alignment/ scope	Varying, increasing with the volume of services from EC, participation in pilots and collaboratives
	Governance mechanisms	Via engagement team, professional associations, visiting and project arrangements, competitions, workshops and bootcamps, advisory boards, surveys, etc.
3. Cyberinfrastructure experts working on geoscience-related information systems but not funded through EarthCube	Contribution to EC	Develop components and platforms to be advertised, discovered, tested, used and customized within EC, communicate technical capabilities to a wide group of EC users.
	Benefits from EC	Following EC-endorsed standards and best practices for component interfaces; following EC innovations in data integration, use EC technologies in other infrastructures, improved connections with end-user scientists and ability to find science partners for use cases; better software re-use and feedback; appropriate balance between open source and commercial capabilities; increased opportunities to advance the frontiers of cyber technology
	Expected alignment/ scope	Varying, increasing with the growth of EC and with EC embracing open development and state-of-the-art technologies. Improved access to talent in universities
	Governance mechanisms	Via technical conferences, associations, expert participation, ambassadorships/evangelists, standards bodies, etc. Coordinated by EC TAC and its WGs

Stakeholder group	Considerations	
4. Professional associations	Contribution to EC	Creating opportunities for inclusion in EC, organizing community feedback on development priorities, develop community consensus on grand challenges, contribute to use cases, domain semantics, summarize best practices to be adopted by EC
	Benefits from EC	EC would provide a review of technical capabilities and feasibility of addressing high-level research issues, identify gaps and miscommunications between science and technical agendas, technically enable new modes of engagement, publication and scholarly communication
	Expected alignment/ scope	Strong engagement to catalyze involvement of members; part of its core mission; organizing working groups on advanced data publication, technical EC and standards literacy
	Governance mechanisms	Mediated by engagement team and the science committee
5. HPC facilities	Contribution to EC	Providing access to cutting edge computing and professional programming cadre, communicate big data and computing capabilities, limitations and costs in solving grand challenges; participate in and host experimental EC infrastructure
	Benefits from EC	Explore grand challenges at the intersection of science and technical agendas which require advanced computing, demonstrate efficient solutions; funding for hosting EC resources and cross-domain testbeds
	Expected alignment/ scope	Expected alignment by spawning working groups and exploratory projects focused on advanced geoscience computing
	Governance mechanisms	Via TAC and its testbed and standards working groups
6. Data Facilities	Contribution to EC	Provide data and curated metadata compliant with EC standards, to support data-intensive research across facilities; organize compilation of data resources from “long tail” science projects; provide DOIs/other IDs; manage long-term preservation of data important for cross-domain research
	Benefits from EC	Increased impact of data facilities, re-use of the data in other domains, benefiting from common data curation tools, increased efficiency, better tracking of data re-use across domains, following EC-wide standards; better training for end-users
	Expected alignment/ scope	Alignment in terms of using EC-produced software, sharing best data management and curation practices, converging on protocols and standards for data access across domains
	Governance mechanisms	Via CDF and leadership council, joint user training, participation in standards development organization through EC
7. Social scientists studying EC, and other social Scientists	Contribution to EC	Integration of geoscience data with social science data, particularly with respect to human impacts on the natural environment. Opportunities to understand and enable social, organizational, and institutional transformation in science. Continuous monitoring of expectations, engagement, satisfaction and needs via surveys
	Benefits from EC	Study EC as a community-driven experiment in aligning social and technical research agendas, identifying alignment risks and opportunities, matching sci-

Stakeholder group	Considerations	
		ence needs and capabilities. Study of ethnography of geoscience communities as a factor in CI development
	Expected alignment/scope	Focus research agenda on cross-disciplinary and cross-organizational alignment.
	Governance mechanisms	Via the Stakeholder Alignment project, Engagement team, surveys
8. Standards organizations	Contribution to EC	Follow use cases from EC, facilitate standards development to be used in EC
	Benefits from EC	An expanded set of use cases to consider for standards development, opportunities to re-use EC infrastructure for interoperability experiments and pilots, ability to leverage EC communication with a large group of stakeholders
	Expected alignment/scope	Consider EC standards and best practices for information exchange, align them with existing standards, develop relevant standard development priorities
	Governance mechanisms	Through the standards and semantics infrastructure WGs of TAC, including standards development experts in EC architecture development and reviews, to establish standards governance
9. K-12 educators and students	Contribution to EC	Nurturing new generation of professionals well versed in both geoscience and computing, supporting continuous advancement of geoscience CI
	Benefits from EC	Improved connections and training at different levels, leverage EC learning resources, stay up-to-date with science advances, stay on top of rapidly improving digital skills of students
	Expected alignment/scope	Include EC materials in geoscience and computing curricula, establish connections with EC stakeholders to support project participation by students
	Governance mechanisms	Via the engagement and training components of EC, TAC and SC WGs, a forum of teachers, engagement of students in forums and pilot projects
10. Citizen Scientists	Contribution to EC	Advancing science, contributing data collection and other resources, providing additional dissemination channels for EC technologies and results
	Benefits from EC	Easier access to advanced infrastructure and science expertise; easier integration and cross-validation with institutionalized science efforts; better training
	Expected alignment/scope	NGOs and citizen scientists bridge EC agenda and results with the general public, align their data collection and research with EC priorities
	Governance mechanisms	Via the communication and dissemination activities of TAC and SC; data engagement with data facilities via CDF
11. Libraries, Museums and Archives, Journals	Contribution to EC	Support learning, manage collections and other resources used by geoscientists, implement curation best practices, provide feedback to EC
	Benefits from EC	Follow EC best practices on resource curation, data citation, reproducibility, ontology development, and on linking data with publications and other types of products; support for cross-disciplinary work
	Expected alignment/scope	Hosting workshops, providing repositories for data and other resources, experimental work on integrating across data holdings, connecting with stakeholder via EC channels
	Governance mechanisms	Via CDF, SC and TAC activities focused on long-term preservation, best practices, standards compliance, semantics and big data management

Stakeholder group	Considerations	
12. Funding Agencies, Policy Makers	Contribution to EC	Funding, support in developing priorities and long-term agenda; compliance guidelines; guidelines on interaction with government and international partners
	Benefits from EC	Evaluate a new model of community-driven research, CI development and science governance; better understanding what is available and strategies for re-use of existing resources and CI; tracking accomplishments; avoiding misuse of funds; clear, demonstrable results that justify continued investment; progress in addressing grand challenge issues; improved use of resources; better ability to make science-informed policy-decisions
	Expected alignment/scope	Inter-agency coordination to support cross-disciplinary research, for better use of funds; matching existing decision-making and advisory bodies at the agency and government levels with EC structures; participation in shared governance; increased ability to harness accomplishments and developed resources for commercial interests
	Governance mechanisms	MOUs, initially working with closely aligned agencies
13. Commercial companies	Contribution to EC	Technologies and resources to be leveraged by EC infrastructure; project participation, advising
	Benefits from EC	Access to talent; increased visibility; funding
	Expected alignment/scope	Partnerships, R&D exchange; advertising technical capabilities and expertise EC-wide; joint open source software development; alignment of research priorities and staff
	Governance mechanisms	Engaging companies that are closely aligned and have a similar user base (eg Mathworks, ESRI); industrial forums, joint proposals and projects
14. Media	Contribution to EC	Dissemination of EC results; making general public and decision-makers aware of the accomplishments and challenges
	Benefits from EC	Source of good stories, highlighting collaborative work and new technologies
	Expected alignment/scope	Advertisement, good stories of collaborative R&D between geo and CS; focused publications and special issues
	Governance mechanisms	Should be part of EC communication and dissemination plans

3.2.1 Interests of End User Scientists

1. **Shared interests across most end user scientists** (Atmospheric and Space Weather scientists, Biologists/Ecosystem scientists, Climate scientists, Critical Zone scientists, Computer Scientists, Geologists, Geophysicists, Hydrologists, Information Scientists, Oceanographers, Physical Geographers, Polar Scientists, Social Scientists, and others):
 - 1.1. Discovery – data, models, software tools
 - 1.2. Access/use – data, models, software tools
 - 1.3. Trust/provenance (history, intended use, limits) – data, models, software tools
 - 1.4. Workflow integration – time/resources/ease in metadata/curation for use by others
 - 1.5. Credit/feedback – on reuse by others of data, models, software tools

- 1.6. Teaching/mentoring – students and colleagues
- 1.7. Impact – enabled by new data, models, software tools – within and across fields/disciplines
- 1.8. Compliance – open data/data plan requirements of funding agencies
- 1.9. Community – new connections to data centers, communities of practice, professional associations
- 1.10. Input/voice – opportunities for inclusion/input, transparency, feedback with initiatives such as EarthCube
- 1.11. Funding/pay – continuity of support for science and employment
- 1.12. Identity – the various ways that work in our fields/disciplines defines who we are
- 1.13. Creativity/inspiration – seeing things in new ways on small problems and grand challenges (such as global climate change, severe weather prediction, etc.) facing science and society

Additional discipline/field specific interests among sub-sets of end user scientists:

- 2. Atmospheric and Space Weather scientists, Oceanographers, Hydrologists, Biologists/Ecosystem scientists, Climate scientists, and Physical Geographers
 - 2.1. Streaming data from satellites, sensors and other sources – discovery, access, provenance, use, re-use, feedback, etc.
 - 2.2. Enhanced utilization of GIS technologies
 - 2.3. Access to high performance computing resources
- 3. Geologists, Geophysicists, Critical Zone scientists, Hydrologists, Biologists/Ecosystem scientists
 - 3.1. Physical samples, cores, and other discrete data types – increased ability to see what is termed “dark” data
 - 3.2. Enhanced utilization of GIS technologies
 - 3.3. Computer scientists
 - 3.4. Challenging computational problems advancing the frontiers of computer science
 - 3.5. Not being seen as “plumbers” serving the work of other sciences
- 4. **Social scientists** (Anthropologists, Economists, Psychologists, Sociologists, Human Geographers, and others)
 - 4.1. Integration of geoscience data with social science data, particularly with respect to human impacts
 - 4.2. Opportunities to understand and enable social, organizational, and institutional transformation in science

3.2.2 Interests of Cyberinfrastructure and Science Infrastructure Experts

- 5. Data facility leaders, managers, curators, and user support personnel
 - 5.1. Increased impact of data facilities
 - 5.2. Increased efficiency and scope of operations through shared resources and infrastructure
 - 5.3. Establishment of standards and protocols to guide the discovery and reuse of data, models, and software
 - 5.4. Improved connections/training of end-user scientist communities of practice
 - 5.5. Opportunity to develop ontologies to facilitate cross-disciplinary data integration
- 6. Cyberinfrastructure and high performance computing experts
 - 6.1. Increased opportunities to advance the frontiers of cyber technology
 - 6.2. Improved connections/training of end-user scientist communities of practice
- 7. Software engineers

- 7.1. Increased opportunities for the sharing and reuse of middleware and software
- 7.2. Establishment of standards and protocols to guide software development
- 7.3. Appropriate balance between open source principles/values and commercial capabilities
- 8. Designers/developers of geoscience instrumentation
 - 8.1. Increased opportunities to advance the frontiers of instrumentation technology
 - 8.2. Improved connections to end-user scientist communities of practice

3.2.3 Interests of Additional Societal Stakeholders

- 9. **Elected Policy makers** (international, federal, state, local)
 - 9.1. Progress in addressing “grand challenge” issues such as global climate change, severe weather prediction, natural resource discovery, and related matters
 - 9.2. Enabling science-informed policy decisions
 - 9.3. Avoiding waste and misuse of government funds
- 10. **Science funding agencies** (international, federal, state)
 - 10.1. Clear, demonstrable results that justify continued investment
 - 10.2. Integration and use (where appropriate) of past funded initiatives and resources
 - 10.3. Progress in addressing “grand challenge” issues such as global climate change, severe weather prediction, natural resource discovery, and related matters
 - 10.4. Effective models for infrastructure development and shared governance
- 11. Regulatory/Service Government agency leaders/staff (international, federal, state, local)
 - 11.1. Interagency coordination and cooperation to better utilize public funds
 - 11.2. Distinct agency accomplishments associated with agency-specific funding streams
 - 11.3. Enabling science-informed policy decisions
- 12. **Environmental resource managers** (international, federal, state, local)
 - 12.1. Increased ability to protect natural resources in the public interest
 - 12.2. Increased ability to harness natural resources for commercial interests
 - 12.3. Enabling science-informed policy decisions
- 13. Commercial industry
 - 13.1. Improved discovery/use of natural resources
 - 13.2. Enhanced innovation in research and development
 - 13.3. Increased access to talent in universities and other sources
- 14. **Professional associations/NGOs** (international, federal, state, local)
 - 14.1. Increased ability to advance the mission/serve members
- 15. **Standards organizations** (international, national)
 - 15.1. Facilitate development, adoption, compliance, and evolution of data standards
- 16. Scholarly journals
 - 16.1. Advancing the frontiers of knowledge and enabling replicability of science
 - 16.2. Improved workflow for inclusion of data/models with submissions
- 17. K-12 educators
 - 17.1. Transformational learning about geoscience (all ages)
 - 17.2. Enabling authentic science involving K-12 students
- 18. Citizen scientists
 - 18.1. Opportunities to advance science in tangible ways
 - 18.2. Life-long learning through science
- 19. Museums & Archives
 - 19.1. Facilitating learning in a digital age

- 19.2. Visibility and use of collections, including digital representations of materials
- 19.3. Enabling the curation/preservation of collections
- 19.4. Increasing the value and impact of curated collections

20. Libraries

- 20.1. Enhanced impact in a digital age
- 20.2. Promoting digital literacy
- 20.3. Facilitating discovery, access, and use of digital materials

We expect that EarthCube will foster various communities of practice that bring together groups of researchers who share interests spanning disciplinary, organizational, and role-based boundaries.

We also recognize that EarthCube is just the US-based component among an emergent web of international scientists and other stakeholders. While NSF funding would not extend to cover international contributions to EarthCube, any such coordination (e.g. via such efforts as the Belmont Forum, Research Data Alliance, Future Earth) is encouraged to strengthen global interoperability.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) EC will coordinate across several groups of stakeholders and communities of practice. These are dynamic, and have overlapping interests and capabilities they may offer to EC. We recommend that EC maintains a dynamic and flexible multi-tier membership system, aligned with access control and service agreements describing different levels of stakeholder participation in EC.
- 2) EC governance and engagement mechanisms with respect to such groups should be different.
- 3) The ultimate goal is efficient resource and expertise sharing in a multi-stakeholder system, and an efficient mechanism for stakeholder to create, advertise, and market their capabilities and interests within EarthCube marketplace.
- 4) While it is important that all stakeholders needed in the system see benefits of participation, it is also clear that not all of their needs will be addressed simultaneously. EC shall develop a phased system development plan outlining how each phase will meet expectations of different stakeholders.

4 Enterprise View: Key perspectives on EarthCube

This section introduces a high-level view of EarthCube organization and function, derived from user needs and expectations described above. Given the complexity of EarthCube, the number and diversity of stakeholders, and the wide scope of expected functions to be supported, we present the enterprise viewpoint from several interconnected perspectives. Some of these perspectives organize EarthCube functions that are common for large information system development (e.g. efficient execution of research workflows, information integration), while others focus on social, organizational and sustainability dimensions of EarthCube CI (e.g. the views of EarthCube as a communication system, a federation environment, and an environment for stakeholder alignment). Figure 8 presents our view of the high-level functional components mentioned by geoscience users. These include components that are commonly used in architecture designs supporting geoscience research projects (shown in blue): data and data management and access services, various format and protocol translation tools, repositories, models and workflows. For a number of such components, significant implementation experience has been accumulated in the community, and there is a higher degree of convergence on information model and protocol standards and best practices related to the use of these components. There is also a large number of emerging functional components (shown in green). These functions have been also men-

tioned as desirable for EarthCube, yet experience including them in CI designs is limited and implementations are often ad hoc. While components such as social networking, annotation, usage information management, conformance testing, research profile systems are being explored in multiple projects, they typically are not integral to infrastructure design, and often appear as additions after the “core” components have been built. We argue that for EarthCube to fulfill its promise as an integrated social-technical federation of systems, these components should be considered as part of design from the beginning, and their interfaces with other sub-systems shall be made explicit. In addition, the diagram points to EarthCube development context which needs to be monitored or interfaced with EarthCube components to ensure that geoscience CI is responsive to science and technology trends and social and natural events. Note that the assignment of functional components to the “established” and “emerging”

categories is approximate and generic at this point: it is likely to change as additional components are developed and standardized, and will also depend on specific experience of users and developers.

This section focuses on several key perspectives on EarthCube as it may be viewed by different user groups, and associated functionality. Each perspective is scoped with an example of use scenarios and the actors involved. Further, we discuss additional perspectives (proverbial elephant’s body parts) that may be brought in by additional stakeholders.

4.1 EarthCube as an open federation of systems

Scenarios:

- Software developer is tasked with building a component to integrate with EarthCube cyberinfra-

Figure 8. Key perspectives on EarthCube, and common and emerging functional components. “Established” components are shown in blue, and “emerging” components are shown in green. This categorization is approximate and generic at this point.

structure;

- Scientist is needing new functionality to support their geoscience research, and according to recent publications, similar functionality has been implemented in another organization.

Because of the loosely knit nature of the geoscience community, its large size, complex organization and multiple stakeholders and partners (many of which are not under NSF purview), and a growing number of geoscience data facilities, software developers and service providers, EarthCube will inherently be a federation of independently managed systems (see Az and Sage, 2009). Designing for the necessary flexibility and scalability dictates a service-oriented architecture that supports varying degrees of coupling between components, based on technology, requirements, and governance decisions made within and between communities. The federation must integrate and leverage existing systems to maximize benefits of previous investment, while being able to integrate new and novel technologies.

Several components are necessary for such a federation to be effective, including declared and **advertised capabilities and policies**, and a shared set of federation-wide **standards** that different systems support. The European INSPIRE project provides an example of specifying and maintaining a common set of specifications, requiring registration of resources in a **common registry**, and creating a **legal and policy environment** for enforcing compliance. Federation-wide **authentication and identity services**, an integrated **resource inventory**, tools for **compliance testing**, as well as infrastructure for **evaluating usage** of different system components, are important parts of a federation. Because top-down design control is limited, documentation of the various components, emphasis on educating developers about existing specifications and implementations, making it easy to find and reuse these, and cultivating and rewarding a 'don't re-invent the wheel' approach to system evolution will be critical to increase the benefits of the federation.

In addition, design of EarthCube as a federation must include mechanisms for evolving **specifications of the "connection points"** between systems, via a consensus process similar to what has been adopted by the Open Geospatial Consortium for geospatial standards. Within this process, a number of use cases and draft specifications are considered to develop a consensus specification, validate it through interoperability experiments and similar tests, and follow a formal transparent process of community discussion and adoption. EarthCube initiative would benefit from collaborating with existing standards development organizations such as OGC, rather than attempting to replace them with similar bodies. To leverage this established standards development infrastructure in EarthCube, we envision an ongoing EarthCube activity focused on inventorying of existing standards, assessing their applicability, collecting and organizing use cases that span multiple systems, gathering requirements to present them to the standards bodies for consideration, and conducting interoperability experiments to validate the use of standards within the federation. An additional key activity is **validation** of developed components against existing standards.

For an authorized scientist or software developer, such a federation will represent a collection of resources provided by each system, with associated resource descriptions, lifecycle, compliance test results, policies, usage patterns and annotations, etc. Within such a federation, implementing the above scenarios would involve:

- Software developer will consult specifications of the federation-wide standards and best practices to settle on the APIs; check policies, usage patterns and annotations of advertised resources available from different members of the federation; develop code to comply with the stated interfaces; validate compliance with tools provided within the federation; deploy the

code on hardware resources available within the federation; register the new code in a registry accessible to others in the federation (e.g. via a broker.)

- Scientist will navigate from publications to associated resources (modules, datasets, and researcher profiles of other scientists involved); evaluate the found modules and data for fitness for use; post questions in a federated Q&A space as needed.

4.2 EarthCube as a cross-domain integration environment

Scenarios:

- Researcher constructing Earth system model and desiring to integrate tectonics into climate models operating on geologic time scales;
- Plant scientist researching relationship between solid Earth substrate (material composition, nutrients, soil development, structure and composition, hydrologic characteristics) and plant community ecosystem.

Although physical processes are not confined to disciplinary or jurisdictional boundaries, scientific research has become increasingly specialized in modern times, as a result of the disciplinary organization of scientific publications, the educational system, funding streams and other institutional arrangements. A major functional requirement for EarthCube is to enable interoperability and resource reuse across the various Earth Science research domains. While results of the survey of EarthCube members conducted by the Stakeholder Alignment project point to high importance of using data, tools and models from other domains expressed by most respondents (with the mean of 0.75-0.80 in a scale of 0...1 where 1 stands for “highly important”), the “ease of re-use” of such data, tools and models across domains received consistently low ratings (with a mean value between 0.2-0.3, for different domain workshop audiences).

EarthCube will be expected to enable cross-domain information exchange, and promote the creation of cross-domain information objects such as integrated datasets or linked resources to be used in the above scenarios. The key challenge is diversity across domain information systems, which focus on different types of data and functions, use different information models and data exchange protocols, different vocabularies, follow different policies, etc. Active community engagement and guidance are required to develop any infrastructure for use across the federation or parts of the federation. For example, if a subset of domains wants to implement a specific privacy and security solution, but other groups believe that the solution will be too stringent to allow collaborative research, it might lead to a conflicting policy decision which an EarthCube governance body must mitigate, and will impact how such a solution is implemented in the architecture.

We consider several key components of EarthCube design to support cross-domain interoperability:

- A systematic collection of research scenarios illustrating cross-domain data discovery and integration. Such scenarios shall highlight common technical issues in cross-domain interoperability including semantic mismatches, differences in protocols and information models, discovery mechanisms, policies and access patterns, etc.
- An inventory of **vocabularies** that organize terminologies used in different domains, and mappings between terms in different vocabularies
- A collection of **catalogs** providing views into different types of domain resources, including mechanisms for cross-harvesting metadata and brokering resource discovery across the catalogs. This requires development of federated catalog schemas, mappings between individual

metadata registries and the federated schemas, metadata enhancement to correct common errors, and re-publishing rectified metadata to support fast resource discovery based on common facets and taxonomies used across domains before redirecting search to domain information systems.

- **Collaboration environments** which can be used by project teams with different domain expertise to organize data and other resources, match their key characteristics based on time, space or observed properties, and develop integrated datasets or other composite resources

The ability to efficiently and effectively re-use resources available in different parts of EarthCube federation is the central value proposition of EarthCube. Data are often expensive to obtain and validate (and sometimes impossible to re-acquire); software tools and models may take multiple man-years to develop and test. In addition to increasing the return on initial investments, on-demand re-use of information resources across jurisdictions, institutions, scientific disciplines – and also across different time frames – enables new kinds of science that are technically or financially impractical within a single system or without large-scale collaborations, and allows for reproducibility of science results, their additional validation, and ultimately increased trust and positive socioeconomic and environmental impacts. Such “re-packaging” for cross-domain information re-use, by creating standardized and documented versions of existing information sources, including datasets and software tools, is the key element in EarthCube, and may require a significant commitment of effort by the publishers, developers or curators.

With respect to implementation of the above scenarios, the cross-domain integration components of EarthCube should enable:

- Discovery of appropriate information sources for the scenarios, based on the specified models, and/or by browsing a high-level inventory of resource catalogs from each of the domains
- Interpretation of the found resources based on domain vocabularies that these resources are explicitly linked to, finding definitions and usage examples for key terms from another domain, exploring or constructing mapping between related terms in different vocabularies
- Exploring all data in a single Google Earth-like interface, or in a series of interlinked domain interfaces which can exchange visualization viewpoint and context parameters
- Finding (in a resource inventory) or developing tools to adjust spatial and temporal resolutions and extents, and otherwise match different data (e.g. geologic and climate; plant characteristics, nutrient fluxes, hydrologic and soil properties), using gap-filling, interpolation, upscaling/downscaling, etc.
- Creating composite datasets and other integrated objects for further analysis; registering these objects in the EarthCube resource inventory.
- Keeping track of all dataset transformations, use of models and other tools, to ensure that results can be traced to original data, and that research workflows can be reproduced;
- Documenting and sharing the workflow and results with experts from different domains, within and beyond the research team.

A question that will need to be addressed as concrete implementation steps are planned is “what are the costs and return on investment (ROI) from interoperability and resource re-use?” There are studies that show enormous costs of making data open, but not much focus on the economics of making data easier to discover and integrate. CI models (centralized, federated) for the EC sub systems need to be evaluated to determine what approaches will lead to better ROI now and as the system evolves.

Another complication is that domain boundaries are quickly eroding: new branches of science appear, and the traditional science enterprise can find itself out of alignment with research interests and disciplinary allegiance. Multiple categorizations exist - based on university department names (e.g. NRC study of department ranking, 2010: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/United_States_National_Research_Council_rankings), curriculum divisions, NSF directorates, AGU sections. In our own experience with the EarthCube Member Connections applications, it appeared that researchers, when allowed to define their domain affiliations, would do it at different levels of granularity and not in accordance with given categories. Since disciplinary categories are changing, the notion of cross-domain may need to be redefined to mean “out of context relative to original purpose and procedures, without intimate familiarity with the purpose, research paradigms, constraints, and other elements that unite and separate groups of researchers”. This makes it less important to design CI in a domain-specific manner. On the other hand, understanding different CI patterns established by different domains and tracing them to how different research groups self-organize (“domain ethnography”), would allow us to create a more flexible design. This has been done for hydrology, demonstrating how domain patterns influence design of a hydrologic information system [Zaslavsky and Maidment, 2011].

4.3 EarthCube as an environment for alignment of stakeholder interests

Scenarios:

- An institution engaged in geoscience-related research and development (academic, governmental, commercial) is planning its strategy with respect to key societal challenges, mandates and technical trends
- PI is developing a large collaborative project, and needs to assemble a team of experts representing key technologies and use cases

EarthCube CI will be successful and sustainable only if it is aligned with the needs and interests of stakeholders, and the value propositions it offers are attractive for large segments of the community. Communities to be served by EarthCube CI differ by discipline, organization type, role in information lifecycle, and other characteristics. Surveys of EarthCube participants indicate that these community sub-groups have different needs and expectations, and have different levels of involvement in EarthCube. The surveys and the domain workshop results also demonstrated the need to clarify interests and expectations of stakeholders, and in particular the importance and challenges of intra-institutional change in the context of a large-scale initiative such as EarthCube. While such institutional changes are usually slow, there is already ample evidence that such changes do happen, as universities and research labs, federal agencies and private companies revisit their development plans and funding strategies to determine which themes can be delegated to joint development within EarthCube.

EarthCube cyberinfrastructure should provide information, services and success stories that would facilitate both internal alignment (within organizations) and external alignment (between organizations). This can be done by conducting EarthCube surveys and developing stakeholder maps, organizing inventories of stakeholder capabilities, disseminating information about specific interests of different stakeholders and about successful partnerships (in particular with respect to pooling resources to achieve research and education outcomes), and monitoring joint use of EarthCube resources by different partners. For example, the survey we conducted among participants in the data facilities workshop helped prioritize the scope functionality of a federation-level metadata catalog with respect to the scope of domain data centers. Most often cited common interests of data centers – which can be delegated to an EarthCube resource inventory – included (in the order of preference): a) Identifying issues related to data

and metadata quality and completeness; b) Making metadata from the facility available for search using standard metadata, via standard APIs; c) Connecting data from the facility with people, publications, models, and projects; and d) tracking domain-specific search requests. One of the functions of EarthCube CI would be to track priorities of stakeholders with respect to EarthCube components providing federation-wide support to users.

Further, analysis of common interests among EarthCube stakeholders is the basis for defining the scope of EarthCube CI, which is an important determination for any information system design. A shared understanding of what is part of EarthCube is critical to the sense of identity and community ownership necessary to distinguish EarthCube as a system. While initial entry is based on awarding of NSF funding under the EarthCube program and through the NSF GEO directorate, continuing participation may be based on funding from other sources. The list of EarthCube stakeholders in Section 2 demonstrates a wide variety of interests and degrees of participation. Thus, the corpus of specifications for EarthCube information exchanges supported by the membership, recommended standards, and best practices documents will be a key element in defining the identity of the system.

To facilitate the scenarios listed above, EarthCube would need to maintain a stakeholder map, as well as various communication channels enabling exchange of needs and capabilities among stakeholders, establishment of partnerships, and monitoring and reporting joint work.

4.4 EarthCube as workspace for scholarly communication and collaboration

Scenarios:

- Researcher compiling data for an ocean circulation model needs to understand and evaluate datasets for quality and reliability, and wants to share this evaluation with others. Further datasets must be available in a reproducible manner, with sufficient docu-

Communication may take place through a variety of channels. Some examples include:

- Person to person spoken communication in real time. This may be face to face in a formal setting, or informal social situation, by telephone, or online audio/video conferencing.
- Written messages between individuals, ranging from postal correspondence, to e-mail, text messaging, or interactive online chat.
- Formal help desk or ticketing systems that generally involve written problem statements and written interaction with a potentially anonymous problem solver.
- Online social networks, forums, wikis or other collaborative environments that involve written communication between users who are typically registered in some fashion as part of a community.
- Documentation written for intended users with no specific recipient in mind. Such documentation may describe interchange formats, service protocols, or specific data.
- Example data or code in files, possibly accessed via the internet or obtained on some sort of media.
- Datasets, software tools, models (these so called “research products” are also a form of scholarly communication)
- Reports and publications in professional and public media
- Conference presentations and discussions, professional meetings
- Surveys
- Outreach activities

mentation so that it is easy to generate them again.

- Educator preparing course notes needs information on a circulation model and its use in different contexts

Communication mostly in a reproducible form between data generators, data providers, data consumers, funding agencies and the science community in general is a key ingredient for successful operation of EarthCube as an evolutionary, marketplace-driven system. Evolution of the system is driven by new ideas that emerge from interaction and collaboration between individuals. Social networks that share information about products available in the marketplace of science resources are major drivers that determine the success or failure of a product (idea, datasets, component design) in the market. Trust assessment of system resources by potential users will be based on availability of reproducible datasets and software, reputation, currently established through publication and face to face interactions. In a global, networked future where collaborators may rarely meet face to face, reproducible software and data on GitHub and Altmetric-type reputation will be mined from social interactions on the network (e.g. blogs, twitter etc.).

A significant driver for progress in solving increasingly complex and interdisciplinary questions about the earth system is open, transparent collaboration between researchers across various disciplines. An important aspect of these interactions is the assignment of credit and attribution both as a source of authority and as a form of currency important to provide value to participants in the collaboration who contribute resources. From a social science perspective, these interactions realize the value of investment in social capital created by connecting groups of people or organizations enabling the flow of information and emergence of ideas not available to individuals without the interaction of the group (Helbing et al., 2011). For any CI machinery to function, it is crucial that human network activities are understood and factored into the system, and the system is organized to promote, encourage, reinforce and reward social behavior leading to EarthCube success and sustainability.

To realize the social network function of EarthCube CI, scholarly communication components must ensure that information produced by individuals and teams is disseminated openly, transparently, and in a reproducible manner so that the rewards are attributable to originators in the form of increased reputation and professional advancement. In order to be compatible with practices of individual domain groups, information exchange protocols and practice, and efficient tools for conducting reproducible research must be established such that all information exchanged carries necessary and sufficient information for it to be correctly interpreted and consumed by the receiving community. This is especially challenging when information is exchanged between different organizations and disciplinary domains that have different channels for distributing information about resource usage and information exchange interactions.

EarthCube must also ensure that communication networks in the system are appropriate and functional, i.e. don't experience bottlenecks, information losses or distortions. This will require development of mechanisms to monitor and assess the efficiency of communication channels, address malfunctions, monitor fair-play between involved parties, test conformance to communication protocols, and monitor connectivity in the system.

A key role of the communication network is to enable feedback between people in various parts of the system and to support quantitative metrics on usage and impact of system resources (Figure 9). EarthCube members should be able to access publications and dataset descriptions related to models they are interested in, as well as explore earlier uses of these models and data as reflected in user annotations, forum discussions, mailing lists, and other linked materials, as well as analyze simulation logs

and model outputs. Data originators and distributors can use feedback in terms of usage patterns, annotations, questions and issues. Scientists sharing research results receive feedback in terms of reviews and questions. Funding agencies receive ideas and results from researchers to in the form of proposals and reports, and seek feedback in terms of metrics for the impact of results. Communication of science scenarios from geoscience researchers to computing experts elicits feedback about feasibility and costs of implementation.

Therefore, the evolutionary, market-oriented conceptual design proposed by this project will focus on a technological framework to promote networked, cross-discipline, community engagement in EarthCube. All contributions to and uses of the system should be monitored, logged and analyzed as part of system operation, to provide recommendations to users and to inform EarthCube governance about impacts, priorities, and system bottlenecks.

Figure 9. System monitoring to provide feedback and guide system evolution.

4.5 EarthCube as an environment for efficient execution/re-execution of research workflows

Scenario:

- A hydrologist working on flood prediction wants to use high-resolution watershed information to do flow forecast using a range of watershed models.

With the growing volumes of data and complexity and computational requirements of analytical tools and models used by geoscientists, efficient processing of geoscience information becomes a key requirement. Recent technological advances, in Big Data analytics, cloud infrastructure, sensor data processing, social computing, high-performance high-throughput computing, etc., have already led to significant transformations in geoscience research, where new data- and computationally intensive models, at higher spatial and temporal resolution and larger extents, have become more common. Despite these advances, many challenges remain, in particular the widening gap between organizations and domains

who have the capabilities to accumulate and process big data volumes, and those who have not. Executing scientific workflows may involve many distributed systems with differing quality of service levels, especially when such workflows implement cross-disciplinary research scenarios.

We envision that within the EarthCube federation several strategies will be used to ensure that federation members have access to active and efficient data management and analytical processing, and that lack of local computational power or expertise does not become a barrier for reproducible science. The following components are needed:

- Registry of computational resources, including their characteristics, availability and quality of service
- Registry of data available via services, and of data brokering/transformation services
- Registry of model characteristics, including if a model or workflow step is data bound or compute bound.
- Pooling cloud resources to manage peak computational demands
- Coupling process models based on information model and protocol standards, to ensure that similar configurations can be run on different physical infrastructures
- Bringing computation to data, to minimize expensive data movement, and staging data from multiple systems to prepare input into computational models
- Monitoring the use of computations, and logging modeling results, to determine usage, efficiency, and provide feedback to both users and to managers of computational resources and data
- Continuous integration environments, to monitor changes in data and software resource, identify changed resources, and possibly automatically trigger effected workflows.
- Early assessment of computational needs and costs based on formal representation of integrated objects, workflows and models

Most hydrologic models are data bound. In the context of the above scenario, the researcher may discover and assemble information for a watershed in preparation to running a Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) model. A specific model implementation may be also discovered through a registry of available models. The process would include collecting data from multiple sources; organizing them into a digital watershed formalism that can be analyzed for completeness, consistency, and any spatio-temporal resolution and extent mismatches; transforming the data into the expected formats for the SWAT model, and running the model on computational resources, either local or available through EarthCube. Model output may be stored locally and/or shared with the research team or a wider community, along with provenance information, processing logs, and any user-entered notes describing the model run.

4.6 EarthCube as a vehicle for career advancement

EarthCube will play an important role in developing and nurturing the next generation of scientists as a shared platform that promotes making connections, finding resources, and collaborating. By participating in the EarthCube community, scientists will benefit from the match-making and recommendation functions of EC so that they are more productive in their own research, and their products will be brought to the attention of those most likely to utilize and build on them. Increased efficiency and impact will help with career advancement, performance evaluation, and reputation. As additional perspective on EarthCube as a program/initiative is as a vehicle for identifying, nurturing and rewarding EarthCube implementation champions in different domains, especially among early career scientists. This

perspective, in turn, implies understanding of challenges that early career researchers have to face, helping them reconcile various demands on their effort, and ensuring that EarthCube participation helps rather than hinders their career.

4.7 A unifying perspective: EarthCube as a marketplace

Scenarios:

- Research project needs a workflow to link sensor data stream to a real time visualization system, searches catalog to evaluate existing technology that might meet requirements;
- Program manager needs to evaluate requests to fund development of a new component, investigates marketplace to see if capabilities are already implemented and how much they are used or requested.

A market is a structure that provides the means for the exchange of goods and services as a result of producers and consumers being in contact with one another, either directly or through mediating agents or institutions (<http://www.britannica.com/topic/market>). The analogy of EarthCube as a market place is based on the concept of product providers and product consumers. The products in this market include information (datasets), technology (software, experimental practice), and expertise. Many of the products in the market place will be available to consumers without cost ('free') because they are the output of public-funded projects with requirements for open access to the products. The economic benefits to producers in this market are thus indirect, in the form of something like 'reputation' that is garnered in systems like [Quora](#), [Stack Overflow](#), or [Yahoo Answers](#). In the funded-research arena, the benefit of accruing reputation is increased success in obtaining funding, greater job security, and personal recognition/social status.

One of the persistent, intractable problems in the existing, de facto, ad hoc market place is the business model for maintaining resources once they reach 'in production' status. Project funding based on research goals has been successful in supporting the development of many interesting and useful software applications and databases. Very few of these have survived long after the end of the original project funding. One possible solution is to use data from market monitoring to identify products that are having significant impact on science enterprise productivity as a basis for allocating maintenance funding in the EarthCube budget.

The traditional economic concept of a market includes the connotation of competition, with multiple buyers and sellers. In the EarthCube marketplace many products are likely to be single-sourced, and the pool of potential consumers quite small. The function of the science research resource marketplace is more oriented towards 'match-making'-- bringing producers and consumers together. Consumers realize benefits because they don't have to expend resources to duplicate a product that already exists. Producers get greater recognition for their products, increasing the likelihood of continued funding.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) EarthCube continues to present itself as a multi-faceted system with different perspectives so multiple users can continue to participate and take advantage of it.
- 2) The different perspectives would re-use some of the same common EarthCube components and services provided that semantics of these components is consistent across the perspectives.

5 GEAR's approach

Many of the existing architecture design frameworks are based on the idea of a system that is managed as a single enterprise engaged in one or more clearly defined lines of business. EarthCube as it is currently envisioned and emerging is not this kind of system; there is no centralized command and control, requirements are a moving target, the function and behavior of the system is intended to evolve as new scientific paradigms emerge, and system participants are conducting research, intentionally pushing the envelope and seeking new ways of doing things. EarthCube will be a complex system of systems that must address evolving user requirements and enable domain and project systems developed under different management and for different purposes to work together in a reproducible, open, and transparent manner. The EC architecture must focus on identifying and specifying the invariant elements of this technical environment that enable new capabilities by combining existing and newly developed resources in various ways and encouraging development of new resources designed for re-use and interoperability. In a sense, instead of a single architecture design, GEAR provides a way to accommodate multiple designs tuned to different tasks. This agile, adaptive, evolutionary software development style is based on a continuously updated portfolio of user stories determining requirements, and motivating development of new components that enable new sub-system architecture. At the same time performance, satisfaction, and impact metrics are collected to continuously evaluate components and guide resource allocation decisions on the one hand, and decisions by users on which components to use on the other hand. We propose a market place as the key analogy for understanding the system. Research data, software components, and documented community practices are the goods traded in this market. The currency is innovative research results, solution of cross-domain challenges, professional reputation and advancement and successful funding for development and maintenance of inventory items.

The role of enterprise architect is inherent to more traditional architecture designs for individual domain system. Rather than the typically conceived role of “chief architect” overseeing a singularly-focused architecture development, the helm of the EarthCube technical system is a market manager. System governance relies on a continuously updated collection of user stories, iteration (change) management, and community engagement mechanisms to establish priorities and allocate resources, and ensure handoffs are made in a reproducible manner. EC is of necessity a loosely-integrated and controlled system that must be adaptable to new requirements, designed as a federation of independent systems, and although the coordinator of the EC system may be named an enterprise architect, his/her fundamental role is different. The focus of the role need to be organizing resources, assessing their readiness for interoperability with the existing EC component inventory, managing dependencies between transient subsystems, mechanisms of stakeholder engagement and inclusion, and negotiation of standard interfaces, rather than actual specification of components. Compositions will be developed by projects that involve both domain scientists and CI experts. We thus consider separate concerns that may be managed by technical parts of governance through its working groups, rather than by a system architect. We believe such an agile approach is an essential architectural strategy for EarthCube – and it is indeed being implemented through recent efforts and organizational structures created by the Governance project.

Federation: an entity formed by uniting partially self-governing entities under a central (federal) governance, to create stability that encourages other common interests, and gives participating entities more common ground. The component entities are in some sense sovereign.

5.1 Agile architecture development

The term 'agile' is usually not applied to architecture, but this is in fact what we have observed again and again when looking at architecture developed for project-oriented research. Architecture management in this context requires rethinking roles. Instead of a traditional waterfall architecture document and a chief architect overseeing its implementation and adjustment, system management would consist of processes for registering EC components and subsystem, assessing aspects of readiness for integration with other components, and steering development towards a common set of information exchange standards. System operation and reliability would depend on mechanisms for maintaining subsystems that utilize multiple components, especially those that address core needs of the community. This approach is a better match for the heterogeneous nature of EC CI, in which sub-systems are motivated by different stakeholders, models of resource ownership and management, licensing and resource sharing models, and lifecycles generally outside of control of EC governance. The goal is to support assembly and integration of independently developed components to address use cases not anticipated in the original component development, demonstrating the value of following standards and the effects of resource compositions being more than sums of their parts.

Given the current common use of terms, calling this conceptual design, where different instantiations of architecture would be created based on this set of common principles, is more appropriate, while reserving the word architecture to various resource compositions created for different purposes

5.2 Centralized and distributed services

A key question is whether EarthCube information resources should be distributed, residing on a collection of servers with different stewards in different locations, or centralized, with all information assets being aggregated and managed in a central location. The answer to this question depends on current technical trends, organization of the science community to be supported, and especially on costs, associated cost-recovery models, and specific efficiency targets of the components. We advocate a hybrid solution, expecting that that subsystem implementations will fluctuate between extremely centralized and extremely distributed models. In particular we focus on functions that would make sense to centralize, and those that would form local information management nodes in EC system. The key points are:

- 1) Being conceived as a federation of relatively autonomous systems, EC is inherently a distributed system because ownership of intellectual and physical assets resides with the organizations hosting various component sub systems. These organizations typically have heterogeneous funding streams and responsibilities, such that EarthCube participation is only one facet of the business that their sub-systems need to address.
- 2) Experience has shown that performance and accessibility suffer in a fully distributed system, in which queries are distributed to multiple servers and responses aggregated before returning to users. Operational systems such as the Neuroscience Information Network that were originally conceived as fully distributed have migrated to a model in which distributed resources are aggregated and cached by a system that provides a data search and access portal, allowing for greater reliability (fewer points of failure), and better performance (less network latency).

5.3 Standards-compliance of key CI components across disciplines

The number of official and de facto standards developed in and across different domain is large and growing (Figure 10). Surveys show that geoscientists prefer following adopted standards to development of EarthCube-specific standard-collections, by a wide margin (e.g. <http://maxim.ucsd.edu/suave/survey1544.html>). Existing domain data systems exhibit varying levels of community convergence to standards for interoperability of components, such as catalogs, vocabularies, services and information models. The degree of convergence is a key indicator of domain system readiness for cross-domain data discovery and re-use. In some information communities, like the NASA DAAC's, data centers collect, catalog, and distribute data products. They may also provide basic processing service to subset the data delivered to the user. Communities such as CUAHSI or USGIN provide software and/or specifications to participating organizations, and a central organization aggregator provides services to search and access the entire system. In other communities, there may be no common cyber-infrastructure or a managed standards convergence process.

The CINERGI EarthCube Building Block project is compiling an inventory of domain system components, with contributions from many domain system experts (e.g. <http://earthcube.org/workspace/cinergi/cinergi-viewers>). The inventory also indicates whether a community supports a consensus effort focused on standardizing domain information models and data access protocols. Analysis of this inventory reveals that the communication protocols (Application Programming Interfaces-API's) and the formats to access data vary across domains. Advances in cross-domain interoperability require a mix of data products that satisfy a spectrum of needs between:

- a. **Generalized, overview** needs (broad, shallow), which are common to a broad spectrum of scientists,
- b. **Targeted reproducible products** that provide data in a particular format to support specific applications or use cases (detailed but narrow scope), and
- c. **Information-rich, comprehensive** needs of a select few scientists who push the limits of existing data and methods.

EC Standards Working Group is inventorying standards used in the geosciences. The goal is to make the standards registry machine-actionable, prepare a foundation for automatic annotation of information resources with references to standards they support, and develop mechanisms for validation of resources against standards. The universe of geoscience standards is changing quickly. Successes of comprehensive approaches inform scientific governance and naturally lead to changes in the definition of what constitute the generalized approaches. One such example is WaterML 2.0, which is now being developed into a Time Series markup language (TimeSeriesML) with the Hydrology and Meteorology communities involved. Scientific governance mechanisms are needed within EarthCube to balance the needs of the few with the needs of the many.

Figure 10. Representation of standards universe (Source: Seeing Standards, A Visualization of the Metadata Universe, by Jenn Riley, Indiana University (<http://www.dlib.indiana.edu/~jenrile/metadatamap/>))

5.4 EarthCube as a collection of specifications

The essence of EarthCube as an entity will be a collection of specifications for functional components, interfaces, and information exchanges. Products in the resource market place will implement one or more of these specifications. These specifications will range from proposals that document newly developed practices to adopted standards from communities outside of EarthCube (e.g. ISO metadata standards, OGC service standards). Other specifications might document best practices vetted by the community and governed by EarthCube review and adoption processes. Because of the constantly changing technology landscape, the portfolio of EarthCube specifications must be viewed as a constant work in progress. One of the functions of EarthCube governance will be to balance stability necessary for adoption of new practices against innovation that takes advantage of new technology opportunities. The EarthCube cyberinfrastructure plays an important role in this evolving dynamic to provide discovery of and easy access to documentation for adopted practices and support for community processes to develop, select, and adopt new practices.

Specification types:

- **Protocols:** low level, domain independent schemes for connecting information systems generally develop by organizations outside EarthCube. E.g. HTTP, FTP, DAP, TCP, IP
- **Information models:** a representation of a conceptualization of some knowledge domain. Various diagrammatic or language based systems are used to represent the model. Various levels of abstraction are possible. ISO19115 (Metadata), ISO19136 (Geospatial), NADM C1 (geologic data)
 - System Models
 - Domain Models
- **Interchange formats:** scheme to serialize information for transmission between information systems (e.g. XML, JSON, binary); typically implements some information model that defines the semantics of the encoded content. The information model in many cases is not explicitly presented as a separate artefact from the interchange format.
- **Interfaces:** collection of operations that can be invoked, and the messaging scheme used to invoke the operations.
- **Information Mapping:** mapping of information between information models, and interchange formats.
- **Packages:** Self-contained units containing the necessary elements to be able to re-execute a software or re-generate a dataset. Currently packages typically contain a self-descriptive file described in a BagIt format.

Table 4. Generalized Categories of Resources

Resource Type	Description
Catalogs	A register of resources with some mechanism for searching.
Vocabularies	A listing of terminology utilized by their community.
Information Models	Documented models for content, structure, and encoding of information used in the managing of exchange of data.
Consensus Effort	Organized activity that manages information models, service profiles, catalog, vocabularies and other governance activities.
Identifiers	System to maintain permanent identifiers and bindings to representations for identified resources.

A high-level model (ontology) for EarthCube information resources is required as a basis for accurate communication between stakeholders and operation of the resource marketplace. The model should include available EarthCube resources, including catalogs and data products, services, vocabularies and other system-level objects. Geoscience subdomain models should be easily integrated into the EarthCube system model so that they are visible to the rest of the EarthCube community.

5.5 Utilization of social networking technology

We believe that placing components of the rapidly growing social networking and linked data technology and knowledge base in the center of EarthCube CI will significantly improve researcher productivity and enable a range of research questions that were not possible before, such as:

- Who else in the community is interested in information resources I am using, and what is their background and interests?
- How do I find resources that have documentation of their prior use in the context I am interested in?
- Which data resources that I have generated have been cited, and in which journals and disciplines?
- Which models have used a specified resource?
- What is the “reputation” of a specific data source/data provider?
- What issues have been reported with respect to usage of a given information resource or a model?
- How do I find researchers for my project team who have worked on a specific data or model?
- Have the results reported in a given paper been satisfactorily reproduced?
- Are the information resources that I found appropriate for my use case? What is known about their readiness and fitness-for-use in a similar context?

Answers to these and similar questions require an interconnected system where research profiles, Q&A systems, use cases, publications and other components of scholarly communication are connected linked with each other and with more “traditional” CI components, such as data archives, computing facilities, services, vocabularies, and catalogs, via a comprehensive resource inventory that bridges the different previously disconnected building blocks. Such linkages will enable updates to a resource to be propagated to users, or components, who might be interested in the item. While this linking is partly accomplished for publications by organizations like Mendeley and ResearchGate, the approach needs to be generalized to other research objects and other types of scholarly communications.

Researchers are increasingly utilizing emerging technology in scholarly communication that will be important in scholarly communication and especially for obtaining feedback to gauge the impact of EarthCube resources. These include:

- Multidimensional aggregators ([ALM](#), [citedin](#), [ScienceCard](#), [altmetric.com](#), [F1000](#), [CommentPress](#), [digressit](#), [Mendeley](#), [Zotero](#).)
- Social bookmarking tools: [Delicious](#), [Cite-U-Like](#), [Connotea Papers](#), [Mendeley](#), [ReadCube](#), [Zotero](#), [VIVO](#), [Catalyst Profiles](#), [ORCID](#), [Microsoft Academic Search](#), [Google Scholar](#), [Web of Science](#), [academia.edu](#), [Scopus](#), [Twitter](#), [Klout](#), [citedin.org](#), [sciencecard.org](#), [Total Impact](#), [altmetric.com](#).

The primary trend is the move from the traditional method of peer-reviewed print journals to electronic journals and publishing on the web. Scientists are increasingly being encouraged to take electronic journals seriously as an opportunity for faster, more accessible and even less costly communication.

As print journals have been replaced with the electronic version, most publishers have accepted this model of scholarly communication.

A direct consequence of the transition from print to electronic is the impetus to the open-access literature. The Open Access (OA) movement has had an influence on publishers, causing some to take a look at their pricing and other practices [Bailey 2005]. According to Suber [2003], “open-access literature is characterized by two essential properties. First, it is free of charge to everyone. Second, the copyright holder has consented in advance to unrestricted reading, downloading, copying, sharing, storing, printing, searching, linking, and crawling. The first property solves the pricing crisis. The second property solves the permission crisis.”

The electronic publishing of scholarly research and open-access movement is increasingly allowing us to think in terms of widely disseminating our research in a manner that makes it reproducible for others. In “reproducible research”, data and code (which are normally proprietary or shared with a closed group) are shared and extended by the members of an open research community. However, there are challenged to conducting reproducible research as open-access research. While open access to code and data has been made possible through several version-controlled systems such as Github, publication of code and data is faced with barriers since they require higher levels of validation, privacy and confidentiality. It is indeed more expensive to create, maintain, & distribute data sets than to do the same thing for journal articles.

To provide incentives for adopting the new form of scholarly communication, federal agencies now place software products on equal weight as print journals. Consequently sites such as GitHub, GitLab, and BitBucket are becoming more mainstream with infrastructure specialists. In particular, systems like Git not only incorporate the best features of existing source control systems but also includes unique distributed capabilities that make version control commands available without connectivity, allowing one to choose when to interact with a network. Consequently such systems naturally conform to the loose distributed collaboration settings under which software development takes place.

Scholarly communication is also being informed by informal means of communication as is demonstrated by the use of social media tools such as Twitter, Stack Exchange, Mendeley, etc. Growing numbers of scholars discuss and share the research literature on Twitter, organize it in social reference managers like Mendeley and Zotero, and review it in blogs, article comments, and post-publication peer review services like Faculty of 1000. While this incorporation of social media into the research workflow may improve the overall responsiveness and timeliness of scholarly communication, it also has a powerful secondary advantage: exposing and fixing scholarly processes once hidden and ephemeral. The daily work of scholars is moving online. As it does, the background of scholarship—the dog-eared manuscripts and hallway conversations—is pushed out on to the stage.

Traditionally, this stage has been occupied almost exclusively by citations. Researchers have used citations to help track the flow of scholarly ideas, and assess a researcher’s performance and impact. However, citation tracking has never been able to follow the important, but less visible, network of collaboration woven through personal connections and informal communication. The increasing online reification of these connections gives us a chance to fill this gap, building a deeper, richer map of scholarly information flows.

This deeper map of scholarly information flows is being explored in two distinct ways: one by looking deep into the content of the published scholarly work and determining how articles are being cited and in what context. The other way is by building So-called “alternative metrics” or “altmetrics”, which are built on information from social media use. Altmetrics could be employed side-by-side with cita-

tions—one tracking formal, acknowledged influence, and the tracking the unintentional and informal “scientific street cred”. Though in its infancy and used by some science domains, Altmetrics could deliver information about impact on diverse audiences like clinicians, practitioners, and the general public, as well as help to track the use of diverse research products like datasets, software, and blog posts. The future, then, could see altmetrics and traditional bibliometrics presented together as complementary tools presenting a nuanced, multidimensional view of multiple research impacts at multiple time scales.

The use of social media is still sparse but is growing steadily. Around 95% of sampled articles from the arXiv preprint repository have been tweeted. Usage of scientific terms on Twitter is modest but reveals interesting usage patterns. Social reference manager applications have attracted significant use. Mendeley has been particularly successful, advertising on their homepage that over 1.6 million users have collected 161 million documents; over 90% of Nature and Science articles are included in Mendeley collections (although this high number no doubt in part reflecting the popularity of these publications). In contrast, find only 3.5% of physics articles bookmarked in CiteULike.

Many of the trends inherently depend upon researchers self-identifying their publications, which otherwise can be hard to disambiguate. Efforts like ORCID are bringing upon a researcher identity system, which upon adoption can significantly inform alternative channels of communication to be able to correctly represent a profile of the researcher. Similarly research profile networks such as VIVO, Harvard Profiles are attempting to automate the process by proactively creating a researcher’s profile both at a personal level and at institutional level, while providing a comprehensive overview of formal metrics of scientific productivity and growing number informal metrics as being calculated through social media engagement. Researchers have increasingly subscribing to these profiles to track their citations, monitor social network activity surrounding their research, and manage, track and present their own measures of impact.

5.6 Sustainability and business models

With many different stakeholders involved, EarthCube provides ample opportunities for a sustainable future if interests of these stakeholders are aligned and multiple support venues are explored. Some possible venues of sustainability (ultimately reducing NSF contribution to CI maintenance and expansion) include:

1. Development of common core infrastructure and education outreach for both science and computational users, to lower the barrier to entry for new practitioners and reduce duplicative efforts
2. Development of information and knowledge products for which the community would be willing to pay.
3. Pursuing grant opportunities from other sources
4. Collaboration with government agencies, at the federal level in particular, who have an operational interest in maintenance and expansion of EarthCube capabilities
5. Collaboration with information technology industry to integrate EarthCube products and building blocks into off the shelf commercial software, at the same time continuing support for core EarthCube constituencies
6. Consulting with organizations wishing to customize EarthCube building blocks and knowledge bases, or extend proof-of-concept developments, for their audiences
7. Services for data curation, resource registration in market place, service deployment, or advertising for service providers.

To be sustainable, support for EarthCube system development must be diversified. Inviting industry representatives as external advisors is a way to engage them early in the development process. Engagement of early career researchers in planning and implementing EarthCube is also a component of long-term sustainability. Improved scholarly communication through EarthCube infrastructure can address sustainability by monitoring the citations to EarthCube architecture and resource inventory in technical reports and investigating the increase in cross-disciplinary NSF grants that are enabled by GEO division using EarthCube resources.

EarthCube is following multiple strategies for mobilizing a wide geoscience and CI community in an attempt to create an environment for discussing shared research interests, nurturing cross-disciplinary teams, and building trust in shared data, resources and knowledge – ultimately leading to collaborative community-guided design and construction of EarthCube CI. Approaches to implementing this vision include: posting design materials online; developing webinars and demonstrations, organizing and moderating online discussions about conceptual design; surveying users to elucidate their vision and expectations; consensus-building on key design components; presenting users with easy-to-use and attractive user interfaces; tailoring the message to specific groups of stakeholders, specifically targeting and getting feedback from early career researchers, and from researchers from domains referred to as “long-tail of science”.

6 The EarthCube System

EarthCube is a federation of systems; inclusion in the system is defined by engagement with its shared purpose and goals by implementing system specifications, following adopted practices, and contributing to the community of practice. Without a sense of identity and membership, there is no EarthCube. We propose that the shared goal that unifies the system is to increase the productivity of the science enterprise. The technical means to achieve that goal are constantly evolving due to changing research priorities, scientific paradigms, and technological innovation. The Earth Science community is diverse enough that we assume that there will subdomain subsystems that have unique requirements requiring unique solutions. Our conceptual design is a ‘meta-architecture’ defining key abstract functional components, a community process for defining their behavior and the information exchanges through which they interact, and feedback mechanisms that are used to measure success and establish priorities. A technologic artefact is ‘part of the system’ if it conforms to one or more of the registered specifications that document approaches to implementing the meta-architecture; as part of the system these artefacts become ‘products’ in the EarthCube resource marketplace.

The technology backbone (infrastructure) of EarthCube are those invariant components needed to support the resource marketplace. For the most part, actual Earth Science research will utilize products discovered and selected through this resource marketplace. The lifetime of any particular product will be dictated by the externally driven technology environment as well as its success in the marketplace necessary to garner funding for its operation and maintenance.

Design in the face of underspecified requirements (see 3.1.1 Underspecified requirements) is a sort of puzzle. When a new user scenario is defined, the puzzle is to assemble components that implement required functionality with information exchanges necessary to compose the components into an operational workflow. Assisting users with this resource composition is one of the functions of the EarthCube infrastructure. This requires that the resource composition wizard have access to characterizations of each component in terms of the functions and interface protocols it implements, and the interchange

formats it uses for messaging. Identification of missing components, interfaces, or interchange formats can be used to define new development requirements.

To enable this approach, the system needs to adopt conventions for machine-actionable descriptions of components, interfaces, and interchange formats to enable virtual assembly of system components to model workflows. A dynamic model representing the key system components, their dependencies and interfaces is necessary to support understanding to the chain of updates triggered by introduction of new resources, components, or information exchanges. A configuration management system is required to provide a registry of existing components, interfaces, interchange formats, and network protocols, with tools for developers to understand how to integrate new components and for users to learn how to assemble existing capabilities into workflows. This registry is one of the central unifying elements for EarthCube, providing an inventory of resources and compositions of those resources.

Our system design will be elaborated in three steps. First an overview is provided that defines the functional subsystems. Then the information view is outlined to define the information objects operated on by the system. Next the abstract components are elaborated in a computational view, emphasizing constraints and requirements for the interfaces and messaging protocols necessary to link federated components into a system, and to provide the feedback required for evolutionary adaptive growth of the system. Unified Modeling Language™ (UML) class, package, and component diagrams are used to present modeling concepts (see <http://www.uml.org/#UML2.0>).

The conceptual design builds on our earlier tiered representation of EarthCube as a system of systems (Figure 11). In this view, Earthcube in the narrow sense is the upper “cross-domain integration tier”, which orchestrates use of resources and capabilities provided by various domain systems. Specifically, this tier is responsible for maintaining a cross-domain registry and catalog of resources; ensuring that resources can be discovered across systems and their semantics understood based on vocabulary mappings; enabling composition of discovered resources into trusted, traceable and reproducible research workflows; maintaining various communication channels among researchers and sub-systems; development of composite resources; providing a registry and governance of standards, data types, identifiers, authentication mechanisms and similar cross-domain level functions. In addition, to support composition of resources, this tier should provide a capability to store and manage lifecycle of composite resources, including long-term preservation of resources to be sustained. In addition, the cross-systems tier would enable EarthCube marketplace, as a mechanism for stakeholders to register and advertise their services and expertise. While logically this tier is separate, physically it can reside and be managed by a designated data facility. To be participants in this system of systems, individual systems (eg domain data facilities and other geoscience information system are expected to register their resources publish service interfaces that would make participation in EarthCube possible. In particular, these would include the ability to find, interpret, access and integrate information resources managed at a system level, which implies that each system would at least expose a catalog (to enable finding its resources), vocabularies (to enable interpretation of resources), data archives (to enable data access) and information models (to enable mapping of information model elements to information objects used by the researcher). In addition, such information systems would need to expose authentication mechanisms, policies and local resource life cycles, as well a register user-focused applications (models, data processing and transformation tools, visualization software, etc.), sufficiently documented to allow their discovery and re-use. Thus described information systems (named domain information systems, but can be also domain-agnostic) constitute the second tier on the diagram. Further down are research sites, teams and individual researchers who generate new data via observation or modeling, develop new models and

tools: mechanisms should exist to register such products in appropriate data facilities (e.g. by harvesting data and/or metadata into domain systems).

Figure 11. Three-tier representation of EarthCube as a system of systems (source: EarthCube Cross-Domain Interoperability Roadmap, 2012)

The key tensions in such a system of systems are at the interfaces between the tiers, in particular, convergence on a limited accepted set of well-defined encodings and standards that can be used to publish information models, data, vocabularies and catalogs – but also respective characteristics of software and other resources as well as identifiers, policies, life cycle information, resource usage information, etc. Different governance models at the three tiers of EarthCube makes such a convergence challenging. Examples and characteristics of networks vs inter-network infrastructures are also shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Systems vs. Infrastructures (modified from Edwards, 1998).

	Systems	Infrastructures	
		Networks	Internetworks or Webs
Key actors	System builders Users (adjustment roles)	Gateway builders Standards bodies Corporations & governments Users (transformative roles)	Gateway builders Standards bodies Corporations & governments Users (foundational roles)
Elements	Heterogeneous components and subsystems	Heterogeneous systems	Heterogeneous networks
Gateways and standards	Dedicated or improvised	Generic or meta-generic	Generic or meta-generic
Control vs. coordination	Control Central, strong	Control and coordination Partially distributed, moderate strength	Coordination Widely distributed, weak Reliant on other infrastructures
Boundaries	Closed, stable	Open, reconfigurable	Open, reconfigurable Virtual or second-order large technical systems
Examples	Local electric power company Enterprise computing (e.g. banks, insurance companies)	Railroad; electric power grids Grid computing NEES, GEON National weather services	Intermodal freight Global telephone system (fixed + mobile + VOIP) Internet and WWW World Weather Watch

6.1 System component overview

At the engineering level, EarthCube is defined by an abstract component model, with elements linked through abstract interfaces. This section defines a high-level view of the system as a collection of component system defined by their functional role in EarthCube. This can be thought of as a reference architecture. The core elements of the EarthCube technology infrastructure are factored into two major groups of abstract components—Content-focused Components, and the Management and Operations Components (Figure 12). The system component model must be a dynamic artefact that can be extended or transformed to account for new workflows by specifying new building blocks or interfaces. The barriers to participation should be low so that requirements can be suggested even by a novice. A key aspect of EarthCube as a federation of systems will be specification of the interfaces that link abstract components and provide guidance for the implementation of new components. Although we suggest some possible examples, the development and adoption of interface specifications will require a working governance structure that is not yet in place.

Figure 12. Top level subsystem groups

6.2 EarthCube Content System

The Resource and Registry systems are closely related, in that both are centered on databases that require data entry (acquisition of new content), update, and maintenance functions, as well as applications for searching and accessing content. The difference is in the intention of the content. The Resource System manages information items that describe entities and activities in the world -- geologic features, observations, laboratory measurements, processing methods, system specifications, etc. The Registry system manages information items that document content in the Resource system or are resources like vocabularies, directories of people, projects, organizations etc. that are 'asserted', i.e. given as facts and intended for shared use populating data or metadata records. Some implementations of these systems or parts of them are currently operational and others will emerge over time.

6.2.1 Resource System

The function of the resource system is to acquire, maintain, and provide access to information resources, including a system repository to maintain authoritative documents that specify EarthCube policies and practice. Resource System components are used to maintain information resources and deliver them to users via EarthCube information exchanges. The system has 4 major subsystems:

1. **Data access.** A Subsystem that supports access to information content at the record/individual feature/individual observation level, e.g. observations, time series, feature services, or grid/array data representations. Components provide various services for brokering, extracting, transforming, aggregating, routing data from repositories (Resource Repository subsystem) to user applications (Data processing subsystem), and for schema or vocabulary mapping to facilitate cross domain integration. Example interfaces or APIs include WFS, WMS, OpenDAP, and Microsoft Odata. This subsystem corresponds to ENVRI RM v1.1 [Chen et al., 2013] Data Access Subsystem, which they describe as follows: The data access subsystem enables discovery and retrieval of data housed in data resources managed by the data curation subsystem. Data access subsystems often provide gateways for presenting or delivering data products. ... Data handled by the access subsystem need not be homogeneous. When supporting heterogeneous data, different types of data (often pulled from a variety of distributed data resources) may be converted into uniform representations [defined by information exchanges]. The subsystem may provide ... encoding services for secure data transfer. Da-

ta access is controlled using authentication and authorization policies. Data access components will arrange different resources or their subsets into meaningful digital objects that can be used by EarthCube applications. These might include: a) integrated digital objects representing composite phenomena studied by geoscientists, e.g., digital watersheds; b) workflows, c) spatio-temporal themes and other digital products; d) projects and model input composites; e) curricula (i.e., learning objects). Such configurations may need to be validated for consistency, completeness, compliance, and other characteristics.

2. **Data Acquisition.** System that handles data describing science entities from the point of entry into the system until they are deposited in a repository for subsequent use. Ranges from geologist in field to advanced sensor network or satellite platform. This subsystem corresponds to ENVRI RM v1.1 [Chen et al., 2013] Data Acquisition subsystem. Acquired data may be non-reproducible, associated with a specific (possibly continuous) event in time and place, or it may be the output from some reproducible workflow derived from other data. The assignment of provenance information recording the origin and processing history is essential for future use. Various processing (e.g. sampling, filtering, averaging) may be applied before being passed on for storage. Data collected by the acquisition subsystem is transferred to the resource repository subsystem for preservation and subsequent use. The acquisition subsystem may also provide services for importing legacy data into the infrastructure.
3. **Resource Management.** System that handles resource registration (creation of metadata, generation of provenance records to record updates), tracking of versions of resources, organization of resources in collections, assignment of relationships between resources, deprecation or deletion of resources. This subsystem corresponds to ENVRI RM v1.1 [Chen et al., 2013] Data Curation subsystem.
4. **Resource Repository.** System that includes all components responsible for persistence and retrieval of digital objects (including datasets, workflows, models, publications) to be shared within a research group, with a wide geoscience audience, or the general public. Repositories may be categorized on various facets-- function (annotation, provenance, data, query, document storage), data structure (structured content, document-based, file-based), data type (geoscience object, spatial data, time slice, users), or role (archive, backup, client cache, system specification). An important repository in the EarthCube infrastructure will be a system repository that maintains authoritative documents defining adopted practices and technology for information mobility and utilization, along with any artefacts like XML schema or rules (e.g. schematron, RuleML) that are used for information exchange validation by the Testing System. At the simplest level this repository could be an online library with a collection of documents. We anticipate that more sophisticated approaches will emerge, with the repository providing interfaces to machine-actionable component descriptions to enable automated configuration management and workflow assembly.

6.2.2 Registry System

The function of the registry system is to support listing, documenting, and finding resources. Includes various register types e.g. metadata catalogs for indexing datasets, documents, and other information resources (including other registries); information model registries to support information exchange models; identifier registries used to map identifiers to resource locations; and vocabulary registries to access shared concepts. The Registry System will need to include functional components for creating, reading, updating, and deleting entries in these various registers. Development of community registries of use cases, models, infrastructure components and other resources will support the Analytics

System and provide data on community needs, interests, and functional requirements. From the marketplace perspective of EarthCube, the registry system supports the ‘product catalog’.

The most familiar register is the metadata catalog, which is a collection of information items (metadata records) describing resources available in the system to support finding, evaluating and accessing EarthCube resources. One of the critical information exchanges that enables the federation of systems is the metadata information exchange that supports machine interoperability of metadata records. Query and search tools may be provided that allow users or automated services to discover and access data based on metadata.

Vocabulary services are another component of the Registry subsystem, providing identifiers and definitions for concepts that are the foundation for domain semantics. The definitions will be important for aligning terms from disciplinary controlled vocabularies and ontologies. Modern information systems being developed in multiple geoscience domains (e.g. BCO-DMO, CUAHSI HIS, iPlant) already utilize some formal representations of semantics supporting discovery, parsing and interpretation of information found in domain catalogs, as well as supporting consistent publication, annotation and cross-linking of resources. Several online systems for managing semantic information have already been used in the geosciences (e.g. MMI, SISSVoc). EarthCube registries will need to promote standards in semantic data management, maintain mappings between terms from different domains to support cross-domain discovery, support semantic linking of resources between different domains, and support semantic transformation of data resources into formats to be used in geoscience modeling.

A system for dereferencing identifiers will be integral to the evolving network of linked data. The dereferencing service simply provides a mapping from an identifier (URI) to a location where a resource or a representation of a resource will be found. In the web architecture this takes the form of a redirection service that maps an http URI (possibly with an accept header) to the current URL where a representation of the identified resource can be retrieved via an http GET request.

The Information Exchange Registry component maintains representations of the data schema (content models) that define the entities and properties of interest to the users of the platform. Databases can store objects (documents, records...) that conform to registered Information Exchanges, but may extend the standard content with other properties as necessary. Users can create new document types by defining new data schema often as a result of uploading some as yet unknown data into a resource repository. The Information Exchange Registry can assist this process and promote reuse of existing schemes by providing users with lists of already-defined properties they can use in defining new schema.

6.2.3 Data Processing System

The Data Processing System supports components used for the actual analysis and visualization of data. It is the foundation for designing new workflows and supporting repeatable science through reproducible data processing using composition of EarthCube components and workflows. User applications developed for specific research projects are included in this system. This system accesses the registry and repository system for component discovery and documentation-‘shopping’ in the marketplace analogy. More importantly, it provides the workbench/workspace support for the use of EarthCube resources in science research workflows. The Data Processing System must include high performance computing and cloud infrastructure to support complex geoscience modeling.

To be re-usable and to support reproducible science, workflows must be modular, flexible and configurable, formal and standards-based, and managed in the same way as other composite digital objects

in the system. A number of workflow systems have been developed (e.g. Kepler, Taverna) but their use in the geosciences is not yet widespread. In most cases, researchers follow published or ad hoc processing protocols (with mostly manual processing), or use specialized “model preprocessing systems” which support translation of available data into standard model inputs. Such routines or systems are often inflexible and not robust, difficult to configure and re-run, and do not encode provenance information, or rely on standard interfaces, which makes re-use problematic. Model composition into workflows relies on standardized semantic descriptions of models and mapping between domain information models that will be accessed from the Registry System.

6.3 System Management and Operations Subsystem:

6.3.1 Community Support System

The Community Support System supports all aspects of user training, collection of feedback, and interactions between users, resources, and other users. Its foundation is a single-sign-on authentication to establish user identity. Other community support components support rating, reviews, and annotation at the record or data item and data set levels, as well as community collaboration tools like wikis, question and answer sites, e-mail lists, etc. provide feedback from users to technology developers and to support the human communication needed for scientific enterprise. In the evolutionary marketplace paradigm, the community support system provides the feedback and communication capabilities that guide decision making by users and selection (survival) of the ‘fittest’ products in the resource catalog.

All community comments and discussion, as well as research products, should be linked to related system resources. These associations can be used to trigger an evaluation of existing workflows linked to new or changed elements. Updates to a resource should be propagated to users of components that might be affected by the update. Linkage of scientific publications to other system resources is demonstrated by organizations like VIVO, Mendeley and ResearchGate; this approach needs to be generalized to other research objects and other types of scholarly communications. We believe that encouraging community-wide consensus-driven infrastructure awareness and design is a promising direction.

Several suggested subsystems include:

- Education system: provides functionality for tutorials, access to data and software specifically designed for training uses, as well as for geoscience education at all levels.
- Reputation system: provides functionality for collecting, evaluating and reporting user activities (with appropriate authentication and permissions) that can be used to identify authoritative information sources and contributors; provide user profiles.
- Governance services: provides functionality to support governance processes like public announcements, calls for input, voting, and change requests.
- Support systems: functionality for helping users solve problems, both scientific and related to EarthCube usage. Includes help desks, Question and answer services, list servers etc.

6.3.2 Analytics system

The Analytics System includes components that record resource usage, service up-time, and other metrics on system performance and user behavior essential to management of the system to optimize performance and efficiently allocate maintenance and development resources. The Analytics System needs to allow model and software developers to track usage and performance statistics, and also support provenance tracing to original data sources, to ensure proper credit. The system provides hard data on what is being used as a criteria for ‘survival of the fittest’ in an evolutionary model.

6.3.3 Testing system

The testing system provides tools and test data to reproduce and validate that subsystems and components are correctly implementing target specifications, and respond to community expectations. The system includes components that run automated tests against various information exchanges and provide standard exemplar datasets that can be used to compare results obtained from different code implementing the same algorithms. For information exchange documents, interchange formats can be validated using XML schema validation, Schematron rules, or other formal rule encodings. Testing should be available as a service to make them easily available. The Open Geospatial Consortium TEAM engine (<http://cite.opengeospatial.org/teamengine/>) is an example of this kind of approach to dynamic testing.

6.4 Information view

Given the number and diversity of stakeholders involved, the ability to explain system design with a commonly accepted set of abstractions is critical. Simplicity and conceptual clarity of a high-level view of the EarthCube federation is a critical requirement for getting engagement. Effective communication about the technical aspects of an information system conceptual design requires a clearly define vocabulary for the entities, properties, and relationships in the system. The information viewpoint provides the basis of this vocabulary that will be used in subsequent discussion. At the top level, the information items of interest to EarthCube (Figure 13) include:

- E-Resources-- any item of interest that is represented by an identified information object in the system; usually referred to simply as 'resources'.
- DataResource-- An information object that describes some domain entity of interest, represented in an electronic form for use in computer information systems. Distinction of data vs. metadata is based on the intention of the provider.
- Metadata --Data that describe, explain, locate, or make it easier to retrieve, use, or manage an E-Resource. Data become metadata when they are used to describe other data in some set of circumstances, purposes, or perspectives. (ENVRI RM v1.1 definition). Metadata is intended as documentation of resources to support discovery (at the dataset level), evaluation (quality, provenance, fitness for purpose, trust), and access (how do I get it?).
- Annotation -- Data for which the subject is a resource, asserted by a party who is not directly re-

Figure 13. Top level information items

Figure 14. Data resource types and associations.

sponsible for the resource. Distinction of metadata and annotation is based on the authority of the party who is making the assertion.

- Link -- A resource that asserts a relationship between other resources.

Figure 14 presents some details of the **DataResource** model. A **DataResource** might be an **UnstructuredResource** (examples include natural language documents, email, speech, images and video) or a **RecordCollection** that is a collection of **DataItems**, which are the third kind of **DataResource**. A **RecordCollection** that consists of **DataItems** is a structured data resource called a **Dataset**. A **DataItem** is an identified unit of data in EarthCube. Each **DataItem** describes some **Thing**, which represents an identifiable entity of interest in the actual world. Some example kinds of things (Feature and Event) are shown in Figure 11 for illustrative purposes. This is not meant to be an exhaustive model, but a small section of an open world model that might include any entity of interest. The kinds of things shown are **Feature**, which is an entity of interest that has a **Location**; and **Event**, which is an entity of interest that has a temporal extent. **Location** is a property of special interest for most geoscientific information that associates a thing with a place in the Earth system.

6.5 Operational perspective

At any given time, a wide variety of software might be available that implements the various Earth-Cube abstract components and interfaces defined by the reference architecture (Section 6.1 above). Operational sub-systems will be built by deploying and configuring software components or connecting

to existing online resources to utilize existing functionality. New software development will only be required to implement processes for which existing components do not meet requirements. Implementing new capabilities typically will start with mapping required functional capabilities to the existing EarthCube abstract component model (reference architecture). This functional decomposition will lead to implementations that can utilize existing interfaces. Integration with the system involves implementing interfaces necessary for components to access other required system service, and interfaces for target user applications to access the component’s functionality.

In this section we explore the specification of interfaces that are the glue that will bind the system together. Communication between software components is based on a complex stack of conventions; the low-level parts of this stack are typically implemented by operating systems and existing network protocols like TCP-IP, and are thus treated as a given in this discussion. EarthCube specifications are mostly required at the Application layer in the Open Systems Interconnection model (OSI Model, [ISO/IEC 7498-1](#)).

6.5.1 EarthCube Information Exchanges

An information exchange is a set of conventions for transmitting content between machine agents that enables interoperability of software clients by defining the information model (semantics) for content, the encoding scheme for serializing content for transmission (syntax), and service protocol requests and responses to get content. The idea of information exchange models is in use for the USGIN National Geothermal Data System [Anderson et al., 2013], the [National Information Exchange Model](#) (NIEM) and the [EPA Environmental Information Exchange](#). Our specific use case is transmitting geoscience information between data provider servers and data consumer client applications. In a data network like EarthCube, registering structured descriptions of interchange specifications in a manner that allows information model components to be discovered and reused in new exchange definitions fosters interoperability. Development of systems for registering models and encoding schemes that would enable machine-processable mappings and transformations to be constructed between them would lay the groundwork for progressively greater automation of the data integration process.

Communication between components requires an information exchange that defines the message requests, the encoding scheme for message content, and the information model underlying the message content. The encoding scheme is an interchange format that implements an information model. Plugging into the system at the information level will require matching the information to be exchanged with an existing information model, then determining what interchange formats and transport protocols are available for that format, and what interfaces support the required protocol. Information models for EarthCube should be built on a community-vetted foundation along the lines of the example high-level model presented here.

6.5.2 Earth Cube Services

Table 6. Some example service interfaces for linking abstract components in the reference model. Including examples of actual interface instances of each type.

Name	Purpose	Examples
Catalog Service	Discover resources, obtain metadata that documents resources	CSW protocol; ISO interchange format
Map Image Service	Provides screen resolution visualizations of geographic data.	WMS, WMTS, TileMill
Gridded geospatial data	Provides geospatially registered gridded data	WCS

Name	Purpose	Examples
service		
Structured data service	Provides access to any explicitly indexed data, particularly multidimensional data.	OPeNDAP
Geospatial Feature Service	Allows query of and access to spatially-located entities - (their geometry and attributes)	WFS
Time series service	Provides query mechanisms unique to the needs of time-series data access	SOS
Processing Service	describe and invoke processing algorithms via a web based API; Includes brokering services that implement transformations between information exchanges	WPS

Table 7. Example programming interfaces for accessing system components.

API name	Purpose of API	Parameters of API
Group Membership	(Internal) API to retrieve group attributes of registered users	In: OpenId of user Out: Group membership list
Authentication OpenId	User OpenId provider service for user authentication	Standard Openid protocol support - YADIS discovery
Find Dataset	Search for datasets based on a (flexible) set of search facets	In: search facets Out: data sets matching
Get Download Script	Generation of download script for data description based on search facets	In: search facets Out: download script to be executed at client side (including security (certificate) handling)
Synchronize Search Index	(Internal API) Synchronize search indices across distributed servers	Part of distributed SOLR or other search engine installation (sharding mechanism etc.)
Processing Service	Discovery and access of processing functionality (e.g. deployed at larger data nodes)	Parameters and Protocol is defined by OGC WPS standard

6.5.3 Subsystem composition

The EarthCube consists of many individual systems that are designed for specific purposes; the purpose of EarthCube architecture is to enable the assembly of new systems by reusing existing subsystems or components. For this construction process to be viable, a methodology is required to describe components that allows a priori identification of interoperable components to guarantee that the assembly can effectively serve the purpose for which it is intended. We call this construction process **composition**.

The GEARs conceptual design views EarthCube as an infrastructure that supports the development, use, and maintenance of a collection of such compositions or assemblies, each a subsystem that is targeted for a specific research challenge. The resource inventory for the EarthCube marketplace will document the available subsystems that can be reused, and components that can be assembled to define new subsystems. EarthCube 'matchmaking' functionality will help users to find and evaluate subsystems and components that are most useful for their requirements. In managing the lifecycle of any system component, it will be necessary to have an accurate report of subsystems that use the component, and their expected time to live and service policies.

A large system that supports continuously changing research designs and computational requirements calls for a methodology to quickly determine if the system can support a new use case, and if not,

to quickly identify functional gaps that must be filled. The strategic goal is to fill gaps in a way that maximally uses existing capabilities and minimizes development costs. Options will typically include customizing or extending existing building blocks, developing new connections between existing components, and developing radically new capabilities and incorporating them into system operation. EarthCube will require a capability to track dependency paths in the system to understand the components and information exchanges required to support particular functionality. Dependency graphs will need to be dynamic, and automatically extended or transformed to account for new workflows, building blocks or interfaces. As discussed by the EarthCube SC, an initial focus could be on providing services for essential variables, i.e. those parameters and spatial layers that are used in multiple geoscience research scenarios. In particular, this will include data ingestion services for such variables, semantic descriptions, services for transforming them into different formats, validation services, and deployment services.

7 Metrics of quality and success

The key to managing an evolutionary federated system of systems and directing its behavior towards the desired goal is the development and acquisition of performance metrics as a basis for objective selection and cultivation of components that are the 'fittest'. The goal of EarthCube is increasing the efficiency and productivity of the Earth Science research enterprise, so selected performance metrics need to quantify progress towards this goal. The key general metric here is ROI into interoperability and expertise exchange (NASA, 2005; GridWise Architecture Council, 2009-09).

EarthCube performance metrics will need to be based on tangible products like publications, reproducible software, data in repositories, and satisfied customers, as well as intangible products like solved problems, learning, hazard mitigation, better data management, better quality of life. Some possible measurement approaches include impact factors, altmetrics, user polling, and review panels (expert opinion). Assessment of these metrics will be used to influence management decisions. The business model for EarthCube, with its foundation on funding through the NSF process, is different from most operational systems, and the management scheme for EarthCube is itself a work in progress. Exactly how system metrics and user feedback will be applied is not a technology issue and for the purpose of this design we can only say that a process needs to be in place and functional.

7.1 Some possible metric factors:

- How many resources are used for more than one research project
- How much effort is required to test hypotheses, measured by the cost of acquiring useful data, cost of developing software or reusing existing models, and the cost of IT support and training.
- How much effort (measure in time, or FTE cost) is required to curate data
- How much effort (measure in time, or FTE cost) is required to publish data and results
- How often is a resource used, measured by counting downloads, URL visits, program executions.
- What resources are changing the way scientists think, measure by counting citations, or positive mentions in the social media/community network.
- Do resources conform to documented practices for cross-domain use, measure with quantitative validation processes.
- How complete and useful is documentation for a resource, measure by surveys and counting help requests.
- Is the performance of system meeting user expectations, measure by means of surveys

7.2 Component evaluation with respect to interoperability readiness

Clear documentation and explicit test processes will be required for metrics used to assign interoperability readiness levels to EarthCube components. This assessment will be used as a guide to identify components that can be used in assembling new workflows and subsystem with minimal effort. We envision that as new components are developed and introduced for use in EarthCube, test procedures will be available to document conformance to declared specifications. The governance process can dictate requirements for branding with various levels of ‘EarthCube readiness’.

Following practice that has emerged in the Open Geospatial Consortium and ISO, test suites should be associated with conformance classes that are assigned URIs (e.g. OGC 08-131). This will enable software to unambiguously declare the functionality that is implemented and the interface connections it will work with.

The following sections suggest criteria for quality metrics for selected system components and functions.

7.2.1 Compatibility with standards

To what degree does the component utilize documented [‘standards’](#) within its target community?

Table 8. Criteria for standardization assessment

Do interfaces use existing interface specifications
Does interaction with component use existing interchange formats

7.2.2 Information model documentation

Does the component utilize a clearly documented information model? An information model defines the content used to represent some resource of interest in a computer system, typically by specifying a collection of entities (objects, features...), attributes (properties) associated with each entity, and relationships between the entities. The information model establishes a semantic basis for communication with the component. Cross – domain interoperability requires well-documented information models. Service endpoints developed for a specific purpose that do not communicate the full details of a data source are evaluated as ad-hoc.

Table 9. Information Model Conceptual ranking

Unspecified
Documented Domain/Conceptual Model; implementation-independent entities, attributes, relationships are documented in easily accessible formats.
Domain/Conceptual Model documented with diagrams using standard notation (e.g. UML), but not explained with text.
Schematic representation of implementation, e.g. XML schema or ER diagram, specific to particular logical implementation
Undocumented interchange document instance examples

7.2.3 Vocabulary utilization

Are the terms used in data clearly defined in a published (registered) vocabulary? Vocabularies are usually constructed as lists of terms to populate specific fields in an information model, and presented as web pages or excel spreadsheets. Common terminology might be stored in ontology formats such as OWL/RDFS, or SKOS. Ideally, vocabulary terms are managed, and have stable URIs assigned that can be

dereferenced to obtain definitions or other representations. A formal way of representing semantic information is a prerequisite for developing semantic cross-walks between vocabularies. If sufficient formal semantic representation is present, cross walks can be automated (e.g. using AgreementMaker, <http://agreementmaker.org/>).

Table 10. Criteria for ranking vocabulary quality

Concept vocabulary: concepts have definitions, source attribution, are assigned registered (dereferenceable) URIs, and have language and/or community-localized labels.
Web-accessible glossary: terms are associated with definitions, terms can be used to obtain definition on the web.
Glossary: terms are associated with definitions, accessible in off line resources
Authority list: list of terms defining a domain of values for a property, incomplete or missing definitions.

7.2.4 Component documentation

Is the component well documented in the EarthCube inventory catalog? The resource description (metadata) content should be complete according to conventions and requirements adopted for Earth-Cube technology and community conventions. The metadata should be discoverable and accessible through standard EarthCube discovery channels appropriate to the resource type.

Table 11. Criteria for evaluating component documentation

Documentation uses minimal metadata standard, such as Dublin Core
Documentation uses comprehensive metadata standard, such as FGDC, or ISO19115
Documentation is complete and informative
Documentation is sketchy
Documentation contains errors, broken links

7.2.5 Resource discovery endpoint

An important family of components in the EarthCube system will be necessary to support user discovery of resources. These are broadly referred to as catalogs. Catalogs can be available at several granularities: at the levels of data source, data series, and observational series. Metadata content accessed via a catalog should conform to some documented profile, and have a standardized query interface, such as OGC Catalog services for the Web, or Open Search. Some catalogs are simply a customized search web page.

Table 12. Catalog quality ranking criteria.

Catalog Search
Search Interface
Search API, not following a standard
Complies with Opensearch API
Complies with OGC CSW API
Catalog Harvest
Has a harvest API
OAI API
OGC CSW API

7.2.6 Data Access Services

Data services are a family of system components that provide granular ([record](#), [granule](#), [object](#), [feature](#)) access to the content of [datasets](#). Evaluation of services is based on support for data access at a record, observation or feature level, the ability of a system to run models using the service, and the ability to create visualizations using the service. A data service should provide methods to select and get a structured subset of a larger data resource, potentially with options for different encoding schemes or response content. Data services may offer content in encoding schemes ranging from comma-delimited text, or simple XML to complex data structures encoded in deeply nested XML, like GeoSciML or GroundwaterML. Services may use community-adopted content and encoding specifications, or non-standard schemes.

The simplest data access is file download via FTP or HTTP. At the second level, access to data is via a URL that follows some pattern allowing subsetting. The most sophisticated services allow complex filtering (e.g. bounding box, time interval), selection of specific attributes and various kinds of sorting. A processing service may also be utilized to subset the data.

Table 13. Data Access Service Ranking

Data Access API
Bulk download
Static URL
Web Service
Data Query API
Simple query subset
Complex query
Processing Subset

7.2.7 Processing Services

Processing services are components that operate on an input resource to produce an output resource. Processing services implement functionality ranging from simple data transformation to complex, multiprocess workflows. The processes may be run on a local machine, or execute on a grid or cloud system. These processes may be run for building a component or for validation and testing. In the case of validation and testing, the service would need a reliable repeatable service that allows testing on a sufficient number of parameters. Ideally, the process is exposed via a standard interface, such as the OGC Web Processing Service (WPS). This would enable standardized service registration, discovery and service chaining, and also support long-running processing requests.

Table 14. Processing Services ranking

Process Execution-Remote
Grid execution
Standard interface such as OGC WPS
Process Execution-Local
Local execution

7.2.8 Visualization Services

Visualization services are a kind of processing service that operates on a given input resource to produce a representation that can be made visible to a human operator using appropriate hardware. Typically a visualization service is tightly coupled with the output hardware that the user interacts with.

There are many options for visualization, from static graphics, dynamic mapping services, to advanced visualizations, such as interactive charts. A simple static graphic of the information is often used, usually as part of a catalog, to help users identify a dataset. At a higher level an image service, such as an OGC Web Map Service provides dynamic access to the data. At the highest level, the service provides visualizations that can be manipulated and explored in real time by the user, e.g. 3-D virtual reality projections.

Table 15. Visualization services ranking

Visualization
Thumbnails or static
Web map service
Interactive Visualization service

7.2.9 Identifiers

Identifiers allow for unique identification of resources, within the context of a data source, organization, or at a global level. Identifiers allow linking or asserting relationships between resources or facts about a resource. The most useful identifiers are globally unique and have a well known and easily used dereferencing scheme. The most commonly used scheme is the HTTP URI, which can be dereferenced using the ubiquitous web architecture. Internal and local identifiers are problematic, because organizational standards change, so local identifiers are regularly redone to meet new organizational requirements, and may lose the binding to their referent resource, becoming useless.

Table 16. Identifier quality ranking

Identifier- Persistence
Internal Identifiers, such as row numbers
Local identifiers
Global identifiers
Shared global identifiers utilized, such as handles, DOI, or DataCite

7.3 Identification of gaps in the federation of systems

The presented design enables identification of several types of bottlenecks and gaps in technical and social capabilities necessary to address in order to realize the self-organizing community-driven EarthCube system of systems. Efforts of the EarthCube TAC Working Group on Gap Analysis to identify and explain gaps based on a survey of EarthCube funded projects is presented in Smith et al. (in press). The key gaps derived from the conceptual design discussion are as outlined below.

7.3.1 System for consistently matching needs and capabilities

The absence of a social and technical platform for advertising, matching, and evaluating capabilities and expertise in the emerging science marketplace represents a major gap. In our view, the main reason existing capabilities are not fully utilized is the lack of an efficient system for expressing needs of geoscientists and matching such needs with available resources. In a narrow sense, such a managed platform for matching technical capabilities and expertise, on the one side, with needs of geoscientists expressed through a variety of use cases and research scenarios, on the other side, responds directly to the core mission of EarthCube.

7.3.2 Bottlenecks and gaps in key processes supported by EarthCube.

The traditional way to address capability gaps, within the established science enterprise, is through identification and implementation of new capabilities. The process is shown in Figure 15, and includes

development of proposals (which derive from known gaps, use cases, requirements, and research ideas), which, when funded, result in the development of new components. These components may persist through evaluation and natural selection cycles (supported by demonstrated research results, usage data and impact they make) and contribute to the body of community best practices, or they may disappear from wide use. This model has been hampered, however, by the lack of clarity and transparency in several key mechanisms of this communication process. The main gaps in the process include: procedures for communicating requirements, use cases and existing gaps to the proposal development and evaluation process; presenting new components for community validation and testing; deciding on which capabilities to sustain based on objective records of usage and impact.

Figure 15. Identification of gaps in the context of science enterprise

7.3.3 Technology to support dynamic assembly of existing resources

When a new user scenario is defined, developers must assemble components that implement required functionality, linking them to compose the components into an operational workflow. The technology required to assist users with this resource composition is a gap. This capability will require that the ‘resource composition wizard’ has access to characterizations of each component in terms of the functions and interface protocols it implements, and the interchange formats it uses for messaging. Identification of missing components, interfaces, or interchange formats can be used to define new development requirements.

To enable this approach, the system needs to adopt conventions for machine-actionable descriptions of components, interfaces, and interchange formats to enable virtual assembly of system components to model workflows. The lack of these convention is another gap that must be remedied to implement the GEAR’s conceptual design. What is needed is registry of existing components, interfaces, interchange formats, and network protocols, with tools for developers to understand how to integrate new components and for users to learn how to assemble existing capabilities into workflows. This registry is one of the central unifying elements for EarthCube, providing an inventory of resources and compositions of those resources.

7.3.4 Adopted standards for information interoperability

Multidisciplinary, cross-domain research will require that data is well documented and accessible in standardized formats. In many cases such standards exist already, but adoption is not wide spread. In other cases, conventions have yet to be defined and documented. The gap is in the development and adoption of standards for data documentation and data delivery. Remediating this gap is a complex problem with technical aspects in developing useful specification for formats, syntax and semantics, frameworks for testing conformance, and off the shelf software that utilizes adopted standards. The social aspect requires changing attitudes about utilizing existing specifications rather than developing new ones, and implementing professional reward and evaluation system that recognize the benefit of participating in standardization activities.

Part of a useful standards framework will be a system for evaluating the readiness of domain system components for utilization in the EarthCube federation of system. Evaluation will involve many aspects, including maturity, availability, stewardship, community adoption, and consistency with existing standards. Such 'interoperability readiness' evaluations will be important information used by resource consumers to evaluate products in the market place. Besides interoperability readiness, EarthCube will need to develop specific metrics, based on both tangible (publications, operational software, etc.) and intangible (solved research problems, improved learning, etc.) impacts, as discussed in section 7. Absence of such metrics that can guide further funding decisions in EarthCube is a gap.

7.3.5 Pain points in common research and data management/processing workflows.

Research workflows are constantly evolving to reflect changing research designs and infrastructure needs and improved technical capabilities. Capability gaps to support these workflows must be detected and documented, and supporting a mechanism to address such gaps through established NSF and community channels is a key goal.

While any meaningful composition of resources to address a science research scenario is allowed, the technology backbone (infrastructure) of EarthCube are those invariant components needed to support the resource marketplace. For the most part, actual Earth Science research will utilize products discovered and selected through this resource marketplace. The lifetime of any particular product will be dictated by the externally driven technology environment as well as its success in the market-place necessary to garner funding for its operation and maintenance. However, capability gaps in the services and compositions that implement the core principles of EarthCube, such as support for reproducibility of science results and methodology, provenance tracking and reporting, support of feedback on performance of various system components, must have priority compared with other capability gaps.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- 1) There could be several metrics that can be used for evaluating success and impact. Use of metrics should be judicious, based on addressing current gaps, and based on the ability to promote science.
- 2) The evaluation must be based on technical and current information that exists and not subjective, though qualitative assertions are possible.

8 Sub system composition

Since any EarthCube conceptual design will only be successful with sufficient buy-in and engagement from the community, we propose that a core subsystem in the EarthCube system of systems

should be a catalog of component building blocks that supports an application enabling users to find and evaluate building blocks, determine if they can be linked with other relevant resources to form problem-solving workflows, and to evaluate costs associated with building blocks selected to be included in a workflow. The components in the catalog will be categorized and described using standardized characteristics for functionality, supported interfaces, access and usage policies, expected lifetime, as well as associated maintenance or development costs. The CINERGI EarthCube Resource Inventory provides a foundation for this subsystem, and the Geolink and Earth System Bridge building blocks could provide semantic tools for the capability and compatibility matching functions.

This approach would allow users to select components from the inventory of available resources (software and data), and test various configurations to determine if a design composed for a specific research scenario can or cannot be implemented with existing components. If there are missing pieces, this process can identify those, and potentially provide assistance with estimating the costs of building them. This tool could be an integral part of research workflows to assemble EarthCube components for data processing, visualization, and analysis by different communities who need customized systems for their requirements. The Resource Inventory system will act as the primary resource for finding and assembling components to implement new workflows or duplicate a previously executed assemblies.

There are multiple cases where composition is necessary. First, consider the process of **constructing a digital workspace** by aggregating and integrating information from the catalog of digital objects. For example, a watershed is an important concept in hydrology. A digital workspace for a watershed will be an assembly of data, models and services from multiple geoscience subdomains including digital elevation models, meteorological and climate fields, geology, geochemistry, socio-economic layers, hydrologic networks, vegetation and paleo-biology etc., all as part of a single workspace. One can conceive of analogous digital estuary, digital aquifer, digital ocean basin, digital thrust belt, digital ore deposit, digital core complex, etc. workspaces. One outcome of enabling such workspaces is the ability to “hang” data into a context for interpretation. Recall the needs of domain users who requested the ability to organize and represent information to be used for analysis, modeling and visualization in a spatially and temporally registered virtual environment.

A different aspect of composability comes from the need to save and recall workflows as reusable units of computation that may involve data acquisition, transformation, model computation, analysis and visualization for specific purposes. All operations on the composition process, like gathering and maintaining metadata, indexing, search, documentation of the “glue logic” to connect compatible components, must be included in the 'memorized' workflows. For example the CIRDLES group (<https://cirdles.org/>) has developed a cyberinfrastructure for geochronological analytics. Their specific infrastructure consists of a sample registry, a sample processing workflow management centered around software packages, the ability to plug in instruments and acquire data from them into data reduction and analysis modules, a database specifically designed to store and retrieve geochronological information, and a data export mechanism. This infrastructure enables recording and replicating the entire data analysis process from raw sensor data obtained from the mass spectrometer to the data visualization that support age interpretations. The CIRDLES group engineered their system from the ground up, but we propose that many elements of this system can be modularized and used to compose custom workflows for other analytical systems. For example, a subworkflow to acquire and process data from an instrument (mass spectrometer in their case), a database specified through an XML schema, a graphical tool to perform data viewing, plug-in analytics and data export are fairly generic and can be acquired for customization from a repository.

We believe that a semi-automated compositor would be an invaluable part of the EarthCube architecture and can benefit the research community fully custom-develop their own research system on top of the building blocks already identified by the Conceptual Design.

8.1 EarthCube-mandated compositions

One of the principle challenges in defining EarthCube architecture will be achieving agreement on the core functions that will need to be implemented and maintained independent of any specific research project. In this conceptual design, we emphasize the role of the EarthCube infrastructure to support a market place for earth science research resources—information, technology, capabilities, and expertise—with services to monitor system usage, collect feedback, and match user requirements with resources that might meet those requirements. The consequence of this emphasis is that the components that support this marketplace and networking system must be a core subsystem in the architecture.

These components include:

- Entry point—users (producers and consumers) have to know ‘where’ to go to access the market place. In current technology practice, this will almost certainly be a ‘portal’ type web site that provides basic information about EarthCube, what it does, how it works and how to use it, with links to applications supporting basic user operations, some kind of search interface, and support for user-managed workspaces.
- Product inventory—essentially a dataset of product descriptions that can be used to implement discovery applications and support automated composition of components.
- Discovery services-- mechanism for consumers to find out what is available and learn about products to evaluate them for fitness-for-use.
- Specifications describing how the market place works. Foremost among these will be a specification of the requirements and procedures to get a product listed in the inventory (catalog).
- Registries for identifier dereferencing, shared vocabularies, information models, and ontologies that provide for semantic integration
- Utilities for monitoring and reporting on usage, performance and user feedback and satisfaction.
- Repositories for long term maintenance of products. The existing NSF data facilities are currently playing this role.

We envision that these functions will be implemented by compositions of loosely coupled components that enable adaptation to new technology and requirements as the system evolves.

8.2 Example application compositions

This section will review several use cases and demonstrate how they can be implemented using various functional components of the design presented earlier. In particular, we will describe common compositions that can be developed from EC resources taking advantage of registered functional components and data. These are more ‘granular’ kinds of user activities than the scenarios sketched in the preceding sections, and are provided as examples. We anticipate that in the actual, evolving system functional decomposition might actually be different.

The section is divided into 3 parts, with subsections cross references. First are scenarios from a geoscience research workflow viewpoint, second are scenarios from a technology viewpoint, third are scenarios and technological solutions from the view point of individual building blocks.

8.2.1 Geoscience user scenarios

8.2.1.1 *Groundwater and climate change*

The scenario is to design and conduct experiments to assess the influence of groundwater systems on climate change. Since controlled experiments at the necessary scale are impossible, these will have to be model-based experiments. The immediate target of investigation is the impact of ground water flux into rivers and to the ocean on sea-surface temperature. This requires a climate model with coupled surface water, groundwater, and marine systems. Constructing such a model will likely involve building a coupled model from existing models. The workflow might look something like this:

- 1) Establish a new project in an EarthCube resource discovery and composition workspace.
- 2) Find relevant models that relate groundwater and climate change in an EarthCube model catalog; also find related publications and evaluation of these models in previous research scenarios; add them to the workspace.
- 3) For input and output variables in each model, find matching components across models using EarthCube semantic registry to access the necessary ontologies and vocabulary mappings.
- 4) Using EarthCube data catalog, determine data sources that would provide model inputs, compatible with those described in the EarthCube data type registry for the selected models.
- 5) Based on model descriptions and characteristics of data sources, determine if any data transformations are needed to stream data between models, e.g. regriding, downscaling, format conversion.
- 6) Find such adjusters/transformation (broker) tools in the EarthCube resource catalog.
- 7) Determine infrastructure/platform requirements for running the linked model, and use EarthCube resource provisioning agent to negotiate necessary infrastructure (storage, compute cycles) based on an EarthCube catalog of infrastructure resource providers and their policies, costs and other characteristics.
- 8) Compile and test workflow for running linked models on the provided infrastructure.
- 9) Optimize for efficient execution of the research workflow, balancing performance, volume and resolution of the data, costs, etc., and relying on previous experience running model components as found in the EarthCube monitoring, reporting and annotation system.
- 10) Possibly connect with data and model providers, and with other researches having experience with the components of the workflow, using communication tools (including real-time) available from the EarthCube science workspace.
- 11) Build a container (Docker?) to manage the model workflow and future runs.
- 12) Execute the model (e.g. in a continuous integration system), so that usage and performance logs are recorded in the EarthCube monitoring system.
- 13) Use results.
- 14) Register coupled model workflow as a [potentially sustained] EarthCube resource (create metadata, get deployable container in a repository), and/or in appropriate EC-affiliated data repositories, based on recommendations from EarthCube repository broker.
- 15) EarthCube collects feedback on model usage using the monitoring system components.
- 16) Model is successful and is integrated into curriculum for climate science classes.
- 17) Project outcomes are automatically shared with collaborators, based on project settings and user collaboration preferences.

This model is a composition/assembly of existing components based on compatibility rules. A key prerequisite to enable this assembly is machine-actionable documentation of information model for each component, and for the interfaces used to input and output data and control directives.

8.2.1.2 Reproducible Science workspace: The EarthCloud

8.1.1.1 Support for collaborative teams

One of the implicit scenarios underlying virtually every EarthCube use case is basic research data project management. The funded research project is the core management unit in the grant-supported science enterprise, and presents a very useful granularity for thinking about user functionality. In this example we use the name EarthCloud for a technology environment enabling creation and maintenance of collaborative geospatial and other information resources in a project context. This might be the entry point for using EarthCube resources for many researchers.

One of the principle functions from the perspective of a user is a workspace environment that will allow a project team to gather resources for storage, access, and sharing, conduct threaded discussions, collaboration collaborate on document writing, and other activities in support of group collaboration. At its simplest, the workspace would provide a location to backup up information. The environment should also provide easy access to utilize existing repositories and services

The EarthCloud could integrate cloud-based storage and collaboration services that many scientists already use, like Google Docs, Dropbox and GitHub, into a single project storage area that provides a unified data management and collaboration interface, as it is done, for example, in the Open Science Framework project (<http://osf.io>), SEAD project spaces (<https://sead.ncsa.illinois.edu/projects/>), or in iRODS storage federation. Workspaces could be integrated with information mined from research networks providing notifications of related activity, feeds from the EarthCube catalog system providing notifications about new resources, and recommendations for useful resources. Utilization of EarthCloud workspaces will benefit researchers by providing targeted recommendations, a useful environment for collaboration, and input into the reputation system. Feeds and access controls could be used to broadcast information about the project to a targeted audience.

Key Requirements for a reproducible science workspace include:

- Synchronization between cloud and desktop should happen automatically; multiple clients can synchronize against one workspace.
- Real time collaboration on document editing, visualization and data exploration.
- Support for messaging, threaded conversations.
- Integrate transparently with existing collaborative services like Google Docs, Office 365, Dropbox, GitHub.
- Enable searching, pushing data to and pulling data from existing repositories.
- Provide support for development, implementation, and verification of Data Management Plans.
- Provide tools for metadata generation. When a file is added to the workspace, the system attempts to recognize the file and extract metadata, and prompts user to verify and add other required information.
- Tools to publish data through APIs.
- Linkage with modeling environments through standard interfaces to register and execute model runs, creating a package documenting inputs, parameters and other metadata, with links to or copies of model results.

- Link large files and data accessible through services to the workspace by reference, and only copy if necessary.
- Use cloud storage and containers to cache large service response datasets or model output for quicker access to workspace clients.
- Enable automated binding of data files to applications used to visualize and analyze that data type, including map-based tools for geolocated data.
- Package data, bundling necessary data artefacts, software, and metadata to publish data to archives or make available for others to use and reproduce.
- Push packages to selected archive or publication repository.

8.2.2 Technology scenarios

8.2.2.1 Identification of resources

Unique identification of resources is a key to data citation (see 8.2.2.4 Citation), linking between resources, and is the foundation for semantic information processing (see 8.2.2.2 Extending Semantics, below). Useful identifiers must be ‘dereferenceable’—that is there must be a known, easily available procedure for a person to determine what resource the identifier refers to. The most commonly implemented technology for this dereferencing uses the Internet Protocol, Domain Name System, resource path syntax, and Hypertext Transfer Protocol (http) that are the basis of the World Wide Web. One of the major challenges in this system is the fact that the physical deployment of the servers hosting resource representations is mutable, so that over time the ‘location’ of the resource bound to an identifier might change. To address this, indirection schemes like the Handle System and EZID have been implemented that provide a mechanism to maintain a durable, updateable mapping between an identifier token and a web location that will provide one or more representations for the identified resource. Widely used identifier schemes like DOI, IGSN and ARK are based on this technology. EarthCube will need to establish policies and recommended practices for assigning and maintaining bindings between identifier strings and resources, leveraging, for example, work on harmonizing identifier schemas at the Research Data Alliance.

8.2.2.2 Provenance of workflows

Data provenance in workflows is captured as a set of dependencies between data objects. Provenance of workflows is implicitly captured in an event log. For example, these logs record events related to the start and end of particular steps in the run and corresponding data read and write events. Using the (logical) order of events, dependencies between data objects processed or created during the run can be inferred. Protocols such as OPM, PROV can be used to capture provenance and describe them. Integration efforts of provenance generated from different sub-systems can be merged using more recent semantic efforts such as D-PROV.

8.2.2.3 Extending semantics

At its root, the basis for semantic interoperability in automated systems is agreement on the binding between particular, machine-actionable symbols (bit streams in digital computers) and meanings as understood by a community of humans who interact with the automated system. A collection of such bindings can be thought of as a sort of vocabulary. In EarthCube, the registry components implement this binding by linking the machine-actionable symbols (identifiers) with representations that convey meaning to humans (i.e. ‘definitions’). These representations are typically text definitions, but might be sound recordings or images of various sorts for some kinds of entities. Extending semantics in this view con-

sists of adding new bindings between definitions and identifiers. To increase the utility of these bindings for automated computer processing, formal, machine actionable representations of definitions and relationships between entities can be constructed using languages such as OWL.

A variety of EarthCube building blocks are extending semantics in various ways (see 8.3), and are working on converging schemes for a shared approach to the vocabulary foundation for semantic processing. In addition, the GEAR project implemented an EarthCube semantic wiki (http://earthlexicon.sdsc.edu/wiki/Main_Page) as a mechanism for converging on common definitions that can be used by geoscientists and information scientists, and as a way to expose such agreed upon vocabularies in a machine-actionable way to other EarthCube components.

8.2.2.4 Data citation

One of the major purposes of a citation scheme in a distributed, electronic information system is to be able to uniquely identify, and ideally retrieve, a cited resource. The context for such citation might be to establish authoritative sources, or to implement reproducible science. EarthCube components to support this citation use case include the repository system, which provides reliable, long term curation of cited resources so they may be recovered. A second component is the identifier dereferencing component of the registry system. The existing system of data facilities and libraries associated with academic institutions provide a foundation for the repository system. Identifier schemes such as the Handle System (<https://www.handle.net/>) and EZID (<http://ezid.cdlib.org/>) provide models for systems to provide long-term maintenance of dereferenceable identifiers.

8.2.2.5 Scaling to a larger number of sensors.

A common technical bottleneck in geoscience research scenarios is related to scaling observations, analyses and models from proof-of-concept designs to larger data volumes, higher-resolution data sources, real-time high-frequency data streams, etc. For example, a volcano monitoring system needs to add sensors due to increased activity. The additional feeds need to be integrated into a visualization system used by human monitors to identify precursors to eruptive behavior. Implementing this scenario using an EarthCube platform, the user would first access the EarthCube catalog to find available visualization and sensor middleware management software that is scalable and supports EarthCube-adopted information exchanges. This discovery would be based on characteristics of software resources advertised by their providers, on experiences of other users who deployed the software in similar circumstances, and on estimates of customization efforts required to deploy the software in the targeted scenario. After deployment, debugging and operational experience user provides feedback about how the system worked, which, together with deployment logs captured by the EarthCube system, would assist new users in making their software choices.

8.2.2.6 Build large 3-D geospatial index

As demonstrated by analysis of user needs, there is an increased demand, in several domains, to build comprehensive 3D representations of various geoscience objects from all available data. For example, a developer building a digital crust application needs to index 3-D spatial objects, with the ability to scale to millions of objects. The key difficulty is that 3D/4D subsurface structures have to be constructed not by direct measurement but by modeling geometric, geochronological and attribute information from different types of measurements done by different research groups using different methodologies and following different semantics. A pre-requisite of such modeling at a regional or continental scale is a large 3D geospatial index into these resources. Using the EarthCube registry of data types, a

researcher should be able to identify those types of data that would contain information about 3D structures, and information on stratigraphy, geochronology, porosity, and other characteristics relevant to building a comprehensive 3D index, then dereference data sources that contain this information. Further, using the EarthCube catalog, the researcher would find available 3D indexing models that would take the identified resources as input into an index construction, at appropriate spatial and geochronological granularity. While this work is now being conducted in the EarthCube Digital Crust project, its main goal is to create resources that would make derivation of such indexes simpler for a broad group of researchers relying on EarthCube data type registry, EarthCube catalog, collection of model resources, and conversion and gridding tools. Once the index is constructed and demonstrated to produce meaningful responses to queries about subsurface structures, the new resource would be registered in EarthCube resource catalog, and experience constructing and using will be recorded for the benefit of future users and developers.

8.2.2.7 Integration with researcher networks

The academic landscape is being enriched by various research networking applications like academia.com, researchgate.net, stackoverflow.com, Google Scholar, Vivo, and others. Many of these systems provide APIs allowing automation of information retrieval and integration with other systems. EarthCube monitoring and feedback components can utilize these APIs to access the content and activity in these systems. Such information is a critical link to close the loop between user requirements, system strategic planning, and resource allocation. In a common scenario, an EarthCube user who needs to reuse unfamiliar data in her own research would be able to connect with other researchers who could help. The 2013-14 EarthCube survey demonstrated that, while majority of respondents use data and tools from others, even if they don't completely understand them (in fact, only 12 respondents, or less than 2% of those who responded to this question, claimed that they never use data or tools from others that they don't completely understand), common strategies to clarify uncertainties with the data are: 1) consulting with colleagues (77% of respondents to this question); 2) contacting authors directly (72%); 3) finding their other papers (75%); 4) searching online for previous applications of the unfamiliar data (69%); and posting questions in an online forum (16%). These numbers demonstrate that geoscientists actively use various research communication channels to clarify meaning of data and tools they use. However, in the absence of a comprehensive system for managing feedback and annotation of resources, this additional information does not contribute to a knowledge base about EarthCube data and other resources. In the GEAR model, communications about geoscience resources are captured through the monitoring and annotation system. Also, once researchers register and advertise their expertise and research interests through EarthCube member directory (e.g. as in our earlier EarthCube Member Connection application), connecting with them and building a knowledge base about resources would be more consistent and straightforward.

8.2.2.8 EarthCube certification and validation

Compliance with documented standards and best practices for exchanging information about resources, the ability to retrieve and process information in an unambiguous way, and to invoke and deploy services from different publishers is the backbone of EarthCube ecosystem. To implement a system for promoting the use of adopted standards, EarthCube will need applications to test conformance to adopted specifications. These applications should be deployed as service that can be invoked to test the operation of another service, or to validate a provided file for conformance with an interchange format. Having resource validation and certification will ensure that an EarthCube resource has known availability and is interoperable with other registered resources.

8.2.2.9 Long-tail engagement

The typical ‘long-tail’ researcher is engaged in individual or small-group research projects, operating on a minimal budget. In the current academic framework for recognition and professional evaluation, the products of these projects are first and foremost publication in high-profile journals, followed by the education of students and their progress through a degree program. Data management and curation are typically after thoughts. One of the aspirations of EarthCube is to provide technology that enables data collected by such researchers to be documented, deposited in repositories, and curated to make them available and useful to future researchers not only in the community within which they were originally acquired, but to the full spectrum of Earth Scientists. Availability of this technology will need to be accompanied by data management training in the undergraduate and graduate curriculum, and by changes in the framework of professional recognition, evaluation and rewards to place higher value on data as a product.

EarthCube will play a role in this transformation by adoption of practices for integrating data documentation capabilities into technology components in all phases of data acquisition, and the development of machine assisted, ‘smart’ resource registration and curation processes in the repository system that minimize the demands on researchers time.

8.2.2.10 Support for collaborative teams

While a number of user interfaces have been developed to support researchers’ work in specific domains, we believe there is a need to develop EarthCube-wide user environments to support cross-domain research and information integration. These interfaces will let users explore resources available from different domain systems, construct, visualize and persist composite resources, launch various processing tools and models, share digital objects with others within a research group or a wider community, and create workspaces for gathering related resources for project work. An often used metaphor for such a user environment, as appears from end user workshop, is a 4D (space-time) virtual globe. A key feature of this EarthCube front-end would be its configurability to customize ‘faces’ for different communities, connecting with domain specific applications while preserving spatial and temporal focus and ability to overlay and juxtapose information retrieved from EarthCube registries across spatial and temporal scales. Following the modular loosely coupled design principle, the application

would be extensibility via a set of APIs and a plugin design.

Figure 16. Discovery, collaboration, communication and project management entry points for EarthCube users.

8.3 Mapping EarthCube Building Block projects to design components

Although EarthCube Building Block solicitations did not specify the infrastructure to be built in details, the set of funded projects appears to cover several areas critical for EarthCube, and to contribute different components to the overall vision. Figure 17 presents the list of funded building block projects (as of 2015), organized by six general areas of focus. These areas are too broad for evaluating the scope of EarthCube covered by the ongoing projects, or understanding capability gaps. Each BB project leverages and/or develops a number of technical components that can be used within the larger EarthCube ecosystem. We made an initial attempt to list such components that can be used EarthCube-wide, and created a schema and a set of controlled vocabularies for systematically describing the offered capabili-

Projects	Data Access	Data Discovery	Data Integration	Data Management	Modeling	Semantics
BCube	√	√	√	√		
CINERGI		√	√	√		√
DisConBB	√	√	√	√	√	√
Earth System Bridge			√		√	√
GeoDeepDive	√	√	√			√
GeoSoft	√				√	√
GeoWS	√	√	√	√		
ODSIP	√	√	√	√	√	
GeoLink	√	√	√	√	√	√
CyberConnector	√	√	√		√	√
CHORDS	√	√	√	√	√	
Digital Crust	√	√	√	√	√	
EarthCollab		√				√
GeoDataSpace	√	√		√		
Geosemantics for Long-Tail		√	√		√	√

Figure 17. Functional categories addressed by the initial group of EarthCube Building Blocks (blue: funded in 2013; light green: funded in 2014). Checkmarks point to technical areas addressed by each project based on a survey of building blocks in spring 2015

ties, developed by both EarthCube funded projects and by relevant projects funded through other NSF programs, or commercially-available (see the spreadsheet at <http://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1KQ0ILse2we73PAGk5STcssbANib6XEiHTtR0voHob5o/edit#gid=1919540330> and the viewer at http://pivots.azurewebsites.net/hli_sheet.html#pv-file-selection). For the EarthCube system of systems to function, geoscience users and developers should be able to discov-

er these capabilities in an EarthCube registry, understand and access them outside their parent building blocks, via a documented API.

An additional way to examine complementarity of BB projects and their contribution to the overall EarthCube infrastructure is to overlay them over a draft high-level diagram of EC components, e.g. as presented in Figure 11. Selected projects are shown on Figure 18. For example:

- BCUBE develops brokering infrastructure (a component of the cross-domain integration layer) and a collection of accessors that enable querying individual information systems via a uniform interface.
- CINERGI develops a federated catalog of information resources (at the SoS level) by harvesting catalogs of individual information systems; metadata in this catalog is enhanced via a cross-domain geoscience ontology (at the SoS level) integrating vocabularies from multiple domains
- GeoDataspace provides infrastructure to conduct reproducible and shareable geoscience by creating repeatable Docker containers of geoscience workflows that can be replayed on the cloud testbed and/or community infrastructures.
- GEOSOFT organizes geoscience software tools developed in different areas of geosciences into a collection with consistent descriptions based on a cross-domain software ontology (Ontosoft, an SoS component)
- GeoWS develops web service wrappers for several key information systems to support uniform space-time discovery across them, based on a simplified service specification that can be used across domains (cross-domain integration component)
- GEOLINK is working with several data repositories to enable cross-domain navigation by presenting their content as linked data, based on semantic design patterns and a collection of domain vocabularies
- CHORDS focuses on one of the key interfaces between real-time data feeds generated in research projects and monitoring systems, and data facilities, and makes them discoverable and accessible in a uniform manner
- ODSIP enhances data access interface for gridded geospatial data with a range of pre-processing functions, which could serve as a model for other geoscience data services.
- DigitalCrust develops an information model and infrastructure for 3D/4D geospatial data, usable in several geoscience communities, to enable dynamic updates of the model from measurements of several types described in a data type registry (an SoS component).
- EarthCollab creates an SoS-level infrastructure to integrate information about researchers and their expertise as recorded in different researcher profile systems and institutional databases.
- Earth System Bridge (ESB) (Figure 19) presents an interesting example of a similar development in the earth system modeling space. Indeed, similarly to the previous diagram, we can consider established modeling frameworks (CSDMS, OpenMI, ESMF, etc.) as current information silos, each of them containing a collection of models that share information models and semantics. The challenge is to couple models across such frameworks (i.e. at the SoS level). ESB addresses this challenge by developing several SoS-level components for model integration, which include: the Basic Model Interface (BMI), a standard interface for heterogeneous models; Model Coupling Metadata (MCM), a information model for dynamic models to support discovery and machine-actionable coupling; and CSDMS Names, a uniform vocabulary to ensure semantic consistency and precision of variable description in a chain of models.

Figure 18. Selected building block projects mapped against generalized component of EarthCube system.

Figure 19. Earth System Bridge components mapped to generalized EarthCube architecture

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) To contribute to EC system of systems development, EarthCube Building Block and other development projects will ensure that data exchange formats and protocols they use are documented and registered in the EarthCube standards registry; that building block components are described according to the standard resource description template and included in the EarthCube catalog, with references to the established spatial, semantic and temporal frameworks providing identities and definitions for each term used in the descriptions; and that initial usage information and annotation is provided along with the resource description.
- 2) To ensure availability for geoscience projects and to assess how they fit with EarthCube architecture (in particular, whether the provided functionality is at the level of system of systems, vs individual system level), such building blocks should also specify their functional role, lifecycle stage, stewardship arrangements, and available expertise to customize and deploy.
- 3) The initial template for registering geoscience infrastructure components should be expanded and include machine-actionable descriptions so that to enable discovery of appropriate components, assessment of their compatibility, creation and deployment of compositions addressing a given research task, and usage annotation.
- 4) This “bottom-up” registry should include software components developed by EarthCube building blocks, by other NSF projects, as well as commercial and open source projects. The descriptions should utilize registered EarthCube vocabularies ensuring that functional role, information models and formats used, data exchange APIs, etc. are defined precisely.

9 Initial Roadmap: toward a Geoscience Marketplace

Going forward, we believe that the current EarthCube capabilities can be transitioned into an enterprise, market system based on a platform for matching science user needs with technical capabilities and available resources. The platform will include a registry of resources for interoperability (vocabularies, information models, ontologies), a resource catalog, and a system for monitoring and evaluating resources and their usage in specific research scenarios. The essential element to enable market driven system evolution is the analytical data from system monitoring that is the basis for evaluation of resources to select 'the fittest', and for identifying alignments between research requirements and resources in the catalog. Several components supporting such a system have already been developed in various EC projects, namely:

1. Registry of resources –being developed in CINERGI, Digital Crust (3D resource types), in various metadata models and specification registries, Earth Systems Bridge (model types), as well as several projects defining a formal semantic framework to be shared across projects (GeoLink, GeoSemantics, EarthCollab)
2. A comprehensive catalog of information resources - being developed by CINERGI and several other projects, and through TAC and SC use case efforts .
3. Work on an evaluation system has been started in an earlier Roadmap project focused on readiness of geospatial resources for interoperability, and in several ongoing efforts focused on comprehensive maturity models, resource annotation and usage monitoring. In CINERGI, a community engagement strategy involving annotation of information resources, has been implemented through the CINERGI annotator, Community Resource Viewers, and the Provenance and Validation subsystems – it can be enhanced with usage information attached to each resource.

We advocate building a Geoscience Marketplace platform consisting of the three components described above as the main focus of the first phase of EarthCube construction. This phase will enable organic EC development in the second phase of EarthCube.

9.1 Specific strategies for building the first phase marketplace platform

- 1) Engage systems engineers and developers who have experience in web based market platforms like Uber, AirBnb, Amazon.
- 2) Define the roles, rights, and responsibilities for participants in the EarthCube resource market place. These need to address information requirements, privacy concerns, access controls, user authentication, arbitration, security, service-level agreements, and funding.
- 3) Implement infrastructure to assign persistent identifiers to all EarthCube resources, and promote their use to document usage, citation, and enable annotation and feedback.
- 4) Implement user profile system, with appropriate privacy and authentication capabilities, and opt-in policies, that can be used to improve relevancy of search results and accuracy in resource-requirements matching.
- 5) Implement annotation system to collect comment, feedback, and usage data both from human users, and from software agents that utilize resources. This can be based on technology used in the CINERGI provenance server.
- 6) Organize an initial marketplace by engaging early adopters who provide resources and capabilities, and publish use cases (already assembled in EC). Focus on good quality resource descriptions and documentation in the catalog.
- 7) Clearly define what resources are in the scope of the EC system of systems infrastructure platform (maintained as EarthCube), and what resources are geoscience capabilities made available through the EC platform (maintained by projects, institutions, and other organizations).
- 8) Keep the platform as simple as possible, to not constrain the “shared economy” ideas at the beginning, and to reduce the cost of sustaining the system.
- 9) Define startup metrics to quantitatively document resource usage and impact, recognizing that new metrics will emerge. Metrics might be based on automated validation/interoperability readiness tests, user feedback, data mining from references in the literature and from online blogs, e-mail lists, and forums, or user surveys. Different participating organizations can choose how to integrate the available metrics data, based on their priorities, to assign value to resources.
- 10) Integrate metrics data into the catalog system so that search results might be ranked based on one or more metrics, and the metrics data are available with search results.
- 11) To better integrate with commercial search engines, expose the EarthCube catalog via sitemaps that provide html resource descriptions with semantic markup (e.g. schema.org), including the metrics data. Work with search providers to promote usage of EarthCube metrics in page rank algorithms for search results identified as EarthCube resources.

9.2 Geoscience marketplace: counterarguments

Science marketplace is a controversial concept. Common counterarguments suggest that the science world is not used to market approaches, in particular:

- Scientists are used to getting everything for free; they are unlikely to pay for services if they think a student would do it for free. However, cyberinfrastructures such as Globus are changing this view with the freemium model, which provides free services for individual scientists but charges large science organizations and funded groups.
- Services in science are typically unique and use-case driven, thus there is no basis for consistent pricing and marketing of such services. Also, availability of resources and especially expertise, is unpredictable, which hinders liquidity.
- Unlike with Uber and AirBNB, matching needs and resources is a process of mutual adjustment rather than a simple match. Due to the typically unique needs of research projects, customization and personalization is typically required.

While these are serious concerns, we want to stress that “shared economy” has been rapidly advancing in many areas, some of which are similar (e.g. health care, education). We don’t envision that all services will be offered on the market from the start; rather there will be a gradual transition to a larger share of activities becoming available as market services – especially driven by standardization and increased transparency of information exchanges as envisioned by EarthCube. We also expect that private companies would increasingly provide services on the geoscience marketplace, along with more traditional researchers and research teams. For example, this approach has been consistently promoted in Europe through programs like FP7 and H2020, which in many cases require involvement of private companies. Further, as information processing, especially with big data, becomes more complicated, it is less likely that graduate students would be able to do it efficiently. In any case, we envision a period when the more traditional research award and contract arrangements will coexist with the emerging marketplace, with the latter increasingly focused on providing infrastructure services that EarthCube will need.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) For the first phase of EarthCube implementation, follow marketplace platform development strategies outlined in section 9.1
- 2) Defining schemas and rules for registering different types of capabilities appearing on the marketplace, and seeding the marketplace with such capabilities supported by EarthCube stakeholders, is a core component of the first phase.

Summary

EarthCube will be a federation of systems designed to incorporate existing operational systems both within and outside of the NSF geoscience portfolio as well as new components that may use competing approaches. The presented conceptual design is a high level view of the system that revolves around a marketplace for resources. Success in this marketplace will depend on the level of compatibility and interoperability of candidate technologies on offer. Market demand and user input can be used to identify gaps in capabilities (unsuccessful searches) and establish development priorities. As an NSF federation of systems operating in the context of a larger earth science research infrastructure, a key commodity in this market will be the technical specifications and implementations of the gateways (interfaces and information exchange agreements) that connect components, enable interoperability, and support scholarly communication and feedback. EarthCube components offered in the market will need to be modular and loosely coupled, reducing the barriers to plugging in new components, and allowing new component assemblies to address new challenges. The operational architecture of the research environment will be an evolutionary artifact driven by decisions made by producers and consumers in the market

place, enabling continuous change to adapt to new research techniques, priorities and technology innovation.

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Appendix 1 Theoretical Approaches and Design Frameworks

Key design principles

The GEARS project team identified a number of informal principles that underlie our conceptual design:

- EarthCube is designed to support the Earth Science enterprise
- EarthCube is an evolving, federated system of systems.
- EarthCube operates in the larger context of the Internet, World Wide Web, and the global science enterprise.
- User participation in EarthCube is motivated by benefit to users, by requirements from research funding organizations, and by professional performance evaluation criteria.
- Membership of a resource in the system requires registration in the EarthCube catalog, and compliance with one or more registered EarthCube practices.
- Funding allocation for EC development and maintenance should be guided by quantitative metrics on resource impact. The community should understand and endorse the metrics used, but funding agencies determine final allocation processes.
- The EarthCube infrastructure is a platform to support evolution of the system.
- The EarthCube infrastructure is a platform for finding, connecting and matching scientific and technical expertise, information and other resources to advance geoscience research and education
- The EarthCube infrastructure enables multiple compositions of available resources and expertise, following a set of architecture design patterns that answer key system requirements

The enterprise approach

Enterprise architecture is the organizing logic for business processes and IT infrastructure reflecting the integration and standardization requirements of the company's operating model. The operating model is the desired state of business process integration and business process standardization for delivering goods and services to customers (Weill, 2007).

Various viewpoints for describing enterprise architecture are identified in the Reference Model for Open Distributed Processing (RM-ODP, ITU-T Rec. X.901-X.904 and ISO/IEC 10746, [<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/RM-ODP>]). These views include 1) The Enterprise View, focused on vision, mission, policies, and business requirements; 2) Information View, focused on structures and semantics, the information content of the system; 3) Computation View, focused on decomposing the system into functional units and the interfaces and workflows through which they interact; 4) Engineering View, focused on the processing and mechanism used by the system to implement functionality; and 5) Technology View, focused on the specific technology used to implement system components and function. The Enterprise and Information views are dictated by use cases and requirements emerging from the EarthCube Roadmaps, Charrettes, domain workshop meeting reports, input from domain scientists, and participants in the planned design review and working meeting of system architects.

Spatial Data Infrastructure

EarthCube conceptual design adopts and extends Spatial Data Infrastructure patterns and best practices, developed within multiple projects at the global, national, regional and local scales. SDI emphasize interoperability between distributed system components, including datasets, processing codes, models, client applications, based on agreements about information models, encodings, exchange formats,

metadata profiles, as well as formats and protocols for data collection, stewardship, publication, discovery, access and processing.

Figure 20. The standard Spatial Data Infrastructure architecture pattern (1:metadata discovery; 2: common services; 3: standard exchange formats). Image source: National Environmental Information Infrastructure Reference Architecture, Consultation Draft, 2014. p.

EarthCube implementation will need to expand and elaborate this general pattern in the following ways:

- extend patterns to geoscience data collection and processing, including specific patterns related to fieldwork, sensor measurement, samples (including physical samples), as well as model-generated data
- extend the social and governance components of the infrastructure, including research profiles, Q&A systems, annotations, collaboration and consensus building
- include tightly-coupled processing and high-performance computing components
- treat the design and development of the system as a process, where different components emerge and are selected, evolving towards better support for cross-domain interoperability and best practices (and that progress with respect to such support is continuously evaluated)
- Ensure that EarthCube functional components for handling key geoscience information types are well-documented and available for compilation into working “plug-and-play” systems responding to specific science tasks.
- ensure that the SDI patterns included in the system meet the requirements derived from a compendium of EarthCube use cases

Systems of Systems

A system of systems is a composite system in which the component parts are heterogeneous, independently managed, and independently operable on their own, but are networked to achieve shared goals. An open system is a system that can exchange energy, material, and information across its boundaries. Characteristics of an engineered system of systems include (Azani, 2009):

- The system cannot be understood by studying the component parts in isolation. The whole is greater than the parts.
- Requirements and behavior are both emergent and prespecified. The entire system cannot be designed a priori.
- Has an encapsulated, self-contained, and cohesive structure
- Network-centric: network-based discovery and dynamic adaptation capabilities of system components
- Subject to predetermined blueprints and interface standards. Can't start from scratch, have to build on existing resources and institutions.
- Depends on symbiotic relationship and open interfaces to function and evolve in an uncertain environment. Participants must get value in return for effort.

A federation of systems is a system of systems in which the component subsystems are independently operated, owned, and funded. The goals of the federation are commonly overlaid on and may be secondary to the original design purpose of the subsystems. EarthCube design must be network-centric (or net-centric), that is it must support network-based discovery and dynamic adaptation capabilities of system components. The adaptability of the system of systems is contingent on its ability to integrate new components, capabilities, and workflows without disrupting existing operations. In many ways its design is a dynamic configuration management problem.

1.1.1.1 Decentralized coordination approaches.

Because EarthCube is an open federation of systems, the system architecture must be designed to provide technical support for decentralized coordination of system elements. Some of these approaches are described in DeWolf and Holvoet (2006).

The market that is more interesting from the architecture/technical development perspective is the market of technology products. The virtual currency in play in this market is a complex quantity combining researchers' time, available funding and the effort necessary to obtain funding. If the perceived value that can be gotten using a particular hardware or software technology is high, consumers will be willing to pay more (from a project budget) or spend more time to get and learn to use the technology. If the perceived value is too low, the technology will not be used, and will wither and disappear.

Another approach to decentralized coordination is called 'tagging' by DeWolf and Holvoet (2006). A tag is a label associated with an agent, or information resource that can be adapted or created by other agents in the system, and can be observed by agents in the system. Coordination emerges because agents make decisions about interactions with resources based on tags. Tagging can promote self-organization by clustering of similarly tagged agents, and discourage selfish behavior (Hales and Edmonds, 2005).

1.1.1.2 Open Systems and modularity

(from Robbins, Charlie, 2013-06-21, npm: innovation through modularity: accessed at <https://blog.nodejitsu.com/npm-innovation-through-modularity/>, 2014-05-06): "When one looks at the dramatic sustained growth of the npm module ecosystem, the obvious question is: why? The reasons are both technical and social. When you depend on a node.js package in your application you don't have to worry if it is compatible with some esoteric concurrency library because all modules are designed to work the same way: fast and asynchronously. You don't have to worry about multiple versions causing conflicts because npm will automatically partition them. In other words: it just works.

There are social strengths that outstrip the technical strengths. Every developer who publishes a module to npm feels a sense of ownership that is much greater than that from contributing to a larger codebase. It is theirs; they own it. The focus on ownership through modularity is the cause of the dramatic, sustained growth of packages published to and activity on npm in “node.js userland.” This wealth of diverse functionality has ensured that node has a vibrant community of developers making the platform and ecosystem successful.”

Emergence

“A system exhibits emergence when there are coherent [results] at the macro-level that dynamically arise from the interactions between the parts at the micro-level. Such emergents are novel with respect to the individual parts of the system.” [DeWolf and Holvoet, 2005]

“Social clusters with local cultures reinforce and promote cooperation...social differentiation is a success principle that promotes cooperation...The hypothesis to be tested is that increasing spatial homogeneity would destroy the natural forces keeping a social system together, [requiring] other cooperation-enhancing mechanisms [to be strengthened] in order to stabilize the system. [A] possible solution.. to solve the cooperation problem in social dilemma situations... would be reputation-based social networks. Considering the rapid development of the Web 2.0, it seems that such a mechanism is currently being established (particularly among the younger generation), and that it may replace local interactions to some extent.” [Helbing et al., 2011, p.202]

“Emergent knowledge processes are organizational activity patterns that exhibit three characteristics in combination: “deliberations” with no best structure or sequence; highly unpredictable potential users and work contexts; and information requirements that include general, specific, and tacit knowledge distributed across experts and non-experts. Examples include basic research, new product development, strategic business planning, and organization design.” [Markus et al., 2002].